

Doctorate of Business Administration (DBA)

Implication of Employee Engagement and Management Performance on Millennials

Retention: A study of SMEs in UK.

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Submitted: June 2021

Abstract

This research explores the dominant view of effective employee engagement, motivation, and management performance on the retention of millennials. Several previous research indicates that there has been a decline in the motivation and satisfaction of millennial employees, consequently impacting their commitment, quality of performance and retention within the organisation. Millennials and Small to Medium Enterprises (SME's) are growing rapidly and causing dramatic change worldwide. Especially considering the current global pandemic circumstance, where SMEs, specifically e-retailers, are becoming the major agent of economic development and employability in the UK economy. Many researchers have repeatedly studied both; however, little research has been made considering the global impact of COVID-19. This research explores the issues SME's face in retaining millennial generation as well as aims to understand the current employee engagement and management performance strategies of SMEs in an effort to tackle dramatic pandemic crisis.

Additionally, the research provides guidelines on how SME's can improve their relationship with millennials by establishing effective employee engagement and management performance. Every enterprise needs to attract and retain millennials as they are taking an active part in organisational activities. Therefore, this thesis aims to fill the gap by exploring current strategies which SMEs are implementing on improving the commitment level of millennials within the organisation after the global pandemic. An exploratory qualitative method research design is used to explore the relationship and experience from the viewpoint of both managers and employees. Data for the study was collected through semi-structured interviews, where ten employees and four managers were selected from SMEs within the e-retail sector of Birmingham (United Kingdom). The phenomenological research method was employed in the study, which allowed researchers to explore the deeper experience of each individual through their current work experience and by identifying the emerging themes and pattern while conducting the interviews. Data collected was textually analysed using the thematic network method and QSR thematic analysis approach.

The findings of this study provide deep insight into the current working experience of employees and managers in e-retail. Findings revealed the need for technological

advancement as a major factor, alongside implementing a clear career path and career development culture within the organisation. To gain more commitment, it is suggested that managers should pay attention to their current hardware and software, enhance their training, and career development opportunities and offer a flexible working environment especially considering the pandemic faced globally. Additionally, it was suggested to place in effective leadership to build friendly work culture instilling effective communication throughout the organisation. Further, the research recommends further quantitative research and the need to explore COVID-19 impact on Generation Y and Generation Z aspect of this phenomena.

Keywords: Millennials, Culture, United Kingdom, Qualitative Methods, Phenomenological Research Method, Opportunities, Employees, Managers, HR, COVID-19.

Acknowledgement and Dedication

“In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious and the Most Merciful.”

All Praises to Allah and His blessing for the accomplishment of this thesis. I thank Allah for giving me all the opportunity, courage, and strength to complete this arduous journey. I accomplished so much during this PhD process from the educational aspect and the aspect of my personality.

Firstly, my sincere gratitude goes to all my family members, especially my dearest father, Amjad Ali and my precious mother, Shahida Amjad. You truly are the best and most special parents anyone could ask for. Your constant support, applauses and motivation over the past four years was more than I could have ever imagined. I will always forever remember the encouragement, help, and assistance you have provided on this journey. I want to dedicate this work to them and show my gratefulness, appreciation, and gratitude. Thank you for holding my hands and supporting me physiologically, emotionally, and financially. I would also like to thank my brothers Zeeshan Amjad and Essam Amjad for helping me to get to where I am today.

I would like to sincerely thank my Supervisor, Dr Bronwyn Betts, for the guidance, understanding and patience throughout this journey. Most importantly, she has provided me with positive, confident encouragement and a sincere spirit to complete this thesis. It has been a great pleasure and honour to have her as my supervisor. My research study would not have been possible without my supervisor and her willingness to help me with this journey of becoming a Doctorate.

I would also like to thank all professors, close friends, colleagues, the admin department, and the research department for the constant support, encouragement, friendship, and understanding throughout.

“May Allah blesses all the people above mentioned and me with more success.

Amen”.

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Chapter 1

1.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the background and significance of the research topic. Background sections establish information on millennial, retention, and employee engagement issues. After that, this chapter highlights the research, aim, objective, and questions, including this thesis's overall structure. The research objective, questions and aims are derived from the research issues and then highlighted by outlining the theoretical concepts.

1.2 Background

Employee engagement is a significant determinant of business success. A workforce of highly engaged workers tends to be innovative and proactive in solving problems, and are likelier to stay with their employers for longer (Young, et al., 2018). On the other hand, disengaged workers perform at a lower level, are more susceptible to conflicts, and are likelier to seek opportunities in other organizations (Young, et al., 2018). Invariably, organizations that have lower rates of engagement among their workers tend to have higher turnover rates (Young, et al., 2018). Many organisations are increasingly emphasising reducing the turnover of their employees (Nelson *et al.*, 2018; Jano *et al.*, 2019). Retention and turnover challenges have been researched for decades (Eilbert, 1964; March and Simon, 1958). The model exploring the concept of employee turnover was introduced in 1958, and its foundation was based on the rationale decision making of the administrative theory process (March & Simon, 1958). In that theory, turnover resulted when the employee-employer relationship became out of balance (March & Simon, 1958).

Millennials are becoming an increasingly prominent part of the global workforce. As older generations age out and retire, millennials now constitute the majority of the workforces of many organizations (Young, et al., 2018). This is particularly true for industries and economic sectors that are relatively new, such as online retail (Rather, 2018). Certain characteristics distinguish millennials from older generations of workers. Millennials tend to change their jobs more frequently than older workers (Jerome, et al., 2014). The generation of workers demonstrates a higher technological

acumen, which makes them highly adept at operating in organizations that feature technological tools and processes (Rather, 2018). However, this also means that millennial workers tend to be occupied by their devices, and they keep themselves busy in them (Rather, 2018). Their job satisfaction factor changes very frequently and thus retaining them becomes difficult for modern organizations (Sinkovics *et al.*, 2018). The employee retention in case of the millennial is an important topic of study as many organizations struggle to retain them due to their varied preferences (Young, et al., 2018). Most millennials leave their jobs within 10 years of their employment and only a portion of 28% stay with the organization for more than five years (Young, et al., 2018). The millennial has different notions and expectations from their workplace. They mostly run after the salary and perks that they receive in organizations (Young, et al., 2018). They do not look into the long-term goals in their careers; rather they look into the short-term goals (Young, et al., 2018). As the current workforce continues to age out, millennials will eventually comprise the majority of workers and managers in many industries (Hershatter & Epstein, 2010). As such, it is imperative for employers to recognise the factors that contribute to high rates of employee turnover among millennial workers, and to implement the necessary measures to remedy this problem in their workforces.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in March and Simon's Organizations Journal.

Figure 1:**Source: March and Simon's Model (1958, p99)**

March and Simon's Model (1958) put forward two factors for turnover. First, perceived ease of movement and perceived desirability of movement. Perceived ease of movement is the assessment of opportunity/alternative employee have and perceived desirability is related to employee job satisfaction. March and Simon (1958) believe that if inducement is increased with the organisation, it will automatically lower these two factors of employee turnover. All the other turnover models, including the most recent ones (Mitchell and Lee, 2001; Allen and Griffeth, 2003), significantly indicate the link between employee satisfaction, commitment, and performance on turnover.

Therefore, many motivational theories have also been developed over time, including Maslow (1943) and Herzberg (1964) and have been recognised as one of the most studied phenomena by many researchers to date. Motivation theories assist organisations/managers to better understand the satisfying and dissatisfying factors among employees. For years managers have been trying to identify a blueprint to sustain employee retention within an organisation. This is because employee turnover negatively impacts organisation's profitability, productivity, and production cost (Allen *et al.*, 2010 and Vitale, 2008). Furthermore, millennial generations are increasing at the workplace; they grew by 50% in 2020 (Barbuto and Gottfredson, 2016) and more than 70% in 2025 (Johnson, 2015) and became an essential part of the workforce. As millennial are perceived as one of the most confident and risk-taker generations than ever before, especially in terms of frequent job change and career change, it becomes considerably important for organisations to understand them.

In the recent times the attitude of the millennial of the retail sector of the UK has changed reasonably. The change has come due to the impact of COVID on the point of view. In the normal times the millennial of the UK retail industry used to leave their jobs due to various aspects of expectation fulfilment but in the recent years they have developed a static approach towards their jobs for the purpose of which their retention has become quite easier (Stoller 2021). The employees of the retail sector of the UK, of whom millennials comprise a majority, are still hard to retain as they are more motivated towards the aspects of growth and increment (Jerome, et al., 2014). SMEs in

the UK still contend with the fear of losing many employees due to lack of resources and other facilities in their organization (Zutshi, et al., 2021).

As millennials perspective/outlook are different to the other generation, it becomes critical and much more challenging for organisations to appropriately adjust their strategies to meet/fulfil the expectations of millennials (Kuhl, 2016; Lawson, 2018). Many organisations use various cognitive, aptitude and personality testing to identify talent for the appropriate job role. Raina and Chauhan (2016) highlighted that frequent job changes are expected by millennial; however, this also leads to greater job fulfilment. This is because when one millennial will be leaving the job, and the other might be looking for same role opportunity in the market, thus, quickly filling the job role. Although, quick job filling may not necessarily result in finding the right person for the job/role. It is critical for an organisation to find the right fit for the job role, as doing so will save cost and time, whereas hiring the wrong fit can double the expense of the organisation (Carter, 2015).

This research will focus on millennial impacts and expectations in the workplace regarding employee engagement and management performance. Employee engagement and management performance have been among the greatest issues faced by HR managers in the workplace. This is because managers typically set one policy of engagement and management performance for all their employers. Furthermore, Mann and Harter (2016) pointed out in one of their articles that the world is facing an employee engagement crisis, which is causing a potential impact on the global economy. The authors pointed out that only 13% (Craptree, 2013) of the employees are engaged effectively worldwide. They tried to re-instate the employee engagement problem by highlighting several reasons; however, one reason was recognised as the most potential: technology. They reinforced that technology is the best way to measure engagement within the organisation, especially where millennials are part of the organisation. However, it will only allow them to measure engagement but will not necessarily provide them with the strategy to improve it.

Mann and Harter (2016) stated that organisations are now focusing excessively on measuring engagement rather than improving it. Much recent research by Stange (2020) also indicated that some steady employee engagement and low employability had been recorded in 2019. However, the current global pandemic has resulted in employee

engagement falling dramatically. The current COVID-19 pandemic and differing outlooks of each generation are causing a dramatic shift at the workplace and urging managers worldwide to re-consider their existing employee engagement strategy to maintain and sustain a high level of performance and retention within the organisation. Murphy (2012) also reaffirmed that it has become necessary for organisations to retain millennials to maintain and sustain competitive advantage.

1.3 Significance of the Research

The research focuses on the aspects of the employee engagement and retention of the millennial in the e-retail sector of the UK. This is a relevant topic of research as the retail sector has struggled to retain millennial employees in the recent times (Rikleen, 2020). In the other industries like the automobile sector, millennial employee retention have been quite easy, as it has been noticed that millennials are staying in their jobs more years than earlier in these sectors (Anitha & Aruna, 2016; Shipton, et al., 2021). This suggests that under the right conditions, millennial workers can demonstrate greater loyalty and commitment to their employers and remain with their organizations for longer.

In case of e-retail industry the scenario is different. Small business organizations in the UK typically manifest lower rates of employee retention as they are unable to pay the desired amount and offer growth, which are key incentives for millennial workers (Shipton, et al., 2021). Considering the integral role that millennial workers play in the modern workforce, and emphasizing the importance of SMEs to the UK's economy, it is important for SMEs in the retail sector to optimize their work environments to suit the needs of millennial workers. The current study is significant in this regard because it provides crucial revelations that can inform strategies for retaining millennial workers for longer, and for increasing the productivity of their millennial workforce.

Huyler (2015) stated that millennial has been of keen interest for many organisations. They have realised that future success is significantly dependent on them, as they are becoming an active part of every organisation, especially in terms of e-retail organisational development. Much research (Ng *et al.*, 2010; DeVaney, 2015; Liu *et al.*, 2019) have been conducted on millennial; however, little research has been made on how millennials future is dividing into two generations. One generation is reaching

adulthood, such as pursuing their careers and contributing to the workplace (Generation Y). In contrast, the other generation is at home and progressing to adulthood (Generation Z).

Generation Z is not contributing to the workplace currently but will eventually become part of the workplace in the e-retail industry. This further divergence in the millennial's generation has been profoundly seen impacting workplaces. Organisation inability to understand and retain Generation Y will cause them great stress and difficulty recruiting and retaining Generation Z even further. Generation Z perspective and outlook have been significantly impacted after the pandemic, especially due to unprecedented education disruption and escalated serious concern for security and achievement speculated after COVID-19 (D'Orville, 2020; Sakdiyakonet *al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, according to White (2016), millennials are increasing dramatically in the workplace, resulting in driving changes, especially digital transformations. Continuous and rapidly evolving work system due to millennials has resulted in managers setting the highest priority in effectively engaging with their employees. This is because it is very hard to retain millennial because their expectation from the workplace is far more than the older generation. In addition to that, SHRM (2016) survey indicated that maintaining a business has become much complex than ever before. This is because managers, instead of understanding the millennial generation of employees, misinterpret them and stereotype them as lazy and arrogant. Because of this, managers failed to retain them. The e-retail industry does not pay the desired amount to the millennial, and they are unable to observe a career growth due to this. Thus, the organizations are unable to retain the millennial employees. Their involvement in the workplace of the e-retail sector is already very low and the lack of career objective fulfilment is also very low. The e-retail sector is the focus of the study as it holds a certain amount of relevance in the business especially after the pandemic (Sakdiyakon *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the purpose of the research is to study the aspects of employee retention in the e-retail sector. The organizations in the e-retail sector are unable to create the career opportunity for the millennial which is the main reason behind their avoiding the e-retail organizations.

The millennial are the generations that have the most potential and energy. The organizations desire to retain them as they can provide better performance than other

people. The confidence of the millennial is better than other generation employees and they often have an arrogant attitude towards their career and jobs. Thus, their approach to the jobs of the e-retail sector is different (D'Orville, 2020). The failure of the organization and manager to recognize their talent often disappoints workers (Shipton, et al., 2021). The organizations are unable to satisfy the desire of the employees, which is a key factor behind the unsuccessful employee retention (Arachchillage & Senevirathna, 2017). The SMEs in the e-retail sector of the UK are the less explored aspects of the study. Thus, this topic holds a certain amount of relevance.

Organization like Amazon is focusing on recruiting more millennial in the organization as they are the most energetic individuals on the organization. The organizations are aware of the abilities of millennial in uplifting the performance of the organization (Rhodes, 2017). It is also a fact that the SMEs in the e-retail sector of the UK do not give much priority to the employee engagement of the organization which impacts the employee retention of the organizations. The SMEs of the e-retail sector have very few resources and time to pay attention to the aspects for which they are unable to retain the millennial employees (Maiers 2017). Thus, this study will focus on the aspects of the SMEs and their retention of the employees. As little to no research has been conducted regarding the employee retention of the millennial especially in the e-retail sector of the UK considering the impact of COVID-19. Thus, this topic holds a certain kind of relevance.

1.4 Research Aim

The aim of the current study is to identify the challenges that hinder employee engagement among millennial workers in the UK's e-retail sector. As part of this focus, the study will explore current levels of job satisfaction, engagement, and commitment among millennial staff working in small and medium e-retail businesses. The findings of the study will be aggregated with credible research evidence to provide recommendations that SMEs in the sector can use to manage their millennial workforces more effectively.

1.5 Research Objectives

Objectives of this thesis are as follows:

- To understand the issues SMEs are facing in retaining the millennial employees.
- To gain knowledge on the current strategy of the SMEs in the e-retail sector in retaining the millennial employees.
- To understand the relation between employee engagement and performance management of the millennial employees in the UK SMEs of e-retail sector.
- To understand the performance management strategy of the millennial of the e-retail sector of the SMEs of the UK.
- To explore the interconnection between employee engagement and management performance with millennials' job satisfaction and retention in SMEs.

1.6 Research Questions

The research question for this thesis is “What and how different outlook of millennials is causing an obstacle to organisational current commitment, satisfaction and performance in the evolving UK market especially after COVID-19 and what can be done to improve it”.

- What issues SMEs face in retaining millennial employees within their organisation?
- What is the current strategy of the SMEs specifically in e-retail sector in retaining the millennial employees?
- What is the relation between employee engagement and performance management of the millennial employees in the UK SMEs of e-retail sector?
- What is the performance management strategy of the millennial of the e-retail sector of the SMEs of the UK?

1.7 Thesis Structure

Figure 2:

Chapter 1 focuses on providing the general background and significance of the research topic. It further contains the research aim, objective, and research questions of the current study. Chapter 2 focuses on providing theoretical background on the evolution of employee engagement and management performance. It starts by providing information on millennials and other sets of generations at the workplace and then reviews millennial impact on current engagement and performance. Different literature on the dimensions of HR will be reviewed, including motivation, organisational citizenship behavior and performance. A conceptual framework is also being provided in this chapter. Chapter 3 focuses on the methodology of the current research. It presents the justification for the method, design, and sample chosen for the study alongside the study's reliability, validity, and ethical concern. Chapter 4 reveals the interview's preliminary outcome and then presents, interprets, and analyses the data. Discussion of the finding of the study is also presented in this chapter. Chapter 5 consists of conclusions and recommendation of the study. It further contains limitation and scope for further research and self-reflection of the researcher in the end. References and Appendices of research will be included at the end of the report.

Literature Review**2.1 Introduction**

This chapter presents the literature review on millennials, employee engagement and performance management. This chapter also discusses small-to-medium enterprises in the UK, their growth and importance in the country's current economy. Various contemporary theories have been reviewed and critically analysed in this chapter to better understand the research topic and research problem raised in Chapter 1.

2.2 Who are Millennials?

According to Alsop (2008), a researcher studying generations has categorised people into different groups, such as people born in the 1940s and 1960s as baby boomers; people born in the 1960s to 1970s as generation X and people born in the 1980s and 1990s as millennial, and so on to the upcoming generation. Till now, baby boomers and generation X have been active parts of every organisation. The researcher categorised them to be optimistic and habitual onto working individual and in organisations with long hierarchy. However, new generations “Millennial” has been recognised as pessimistic and believe in working in teams. Greenberg and Weber (2008) considered millennials as a unique generation. Authors recognised that millennials have a different outlook on their lifestyle, such as contributing to society, work life balance etc. Moreover, they are identified as innovative, as they possess high skills, such as technology and multi-tasking.

Furthermore, millennials believe in contributing to society as a whole (team), not just as individuals. As the millennial generation grows rapidly and becomes an active part of organisations, managers need to make significant adjustments in their strategies, such as employee engagement. This is because millennials redefine the workplace regarding how employers engage with their employees and how they cope with technology advancement (Karsh and Templin, 2013).

2.3 Differences between Millennial and other generations

As previously suggested, today's workforce consists of three different generations: baby boomers, generation X and millennial. Multi-generations at the workplace are recognised as one reason for making system much more complex for managers to deal with. Therefore, managers must identify the differences and characteristics of every generation to ensure miscommunication and conflicts are avoided. Furthermore, identifying these differences will allow managers to develop effective and successful strategies for their organisations. Differences are as follows: Demographic change in the workplace; due to hyperactive and digitally connected culture generation, results in having different desires from employees.

Lynch (2008) stated that the millennial generation prefers socialising with people even beyond their workplace. In contrast, the older generation believed and viewed socialising with people beyond their work as a lack of loyalty to the organisation. Moss (2016) further reinforced the need to reconsider generations' different outlooks by indicating that older generations, such as baby boomers, generation X, and the millennial generation, have different desires. Older generations desire achievements and promotion, whereas millennials desire to contribute through social interaction and rapid outcomes. The older generation wants a structured workplace, whereas millennial want flexibility in the workplace. Millennials' high priority is to work in the organisation, which perceives flexibility with high regard, whereas the older generation's high priority is income and job security. Even though the older generation has experienced technology, millennials are identified as the Master of the Digital era.

Furthermore, the digital era has allowed them to access information instantly, making millennials much more creative and innovative than any other generation before. This digital era has drastically changed the social mindset of a new generation. Unlike the older generation, Millennial always look forward to facing new challenges and work towards finding solutions. Millennial embrace changes and development, whereas old generations were repetitively seen resisting changes.

In addition to that, Narayanan (2014) stated that millennial also have a different outlook for feedbacks. Millennials expect frequent feedback on their work whether they are in the university or the workplace. They want to be frequently appreciated when they have done an excellent job, whereas the older generation does not desire such frequent

feedback. They are used to getting infrequent feedback and prefer a semi-annual review of their work. Not only that, but millennials also have a different expectation for feedback in terms of its receptive. They prefer clearer feedback from their managers. They do not want just mere words or gesture feedback that they have done an excellent job but rather expect managers to give feedback on how they can improve as well. Whereas the older generation expects and were used to receiving precise feedback on their work. Therefore, managers need to design feedback for millennials in a way, which will result in frequency and clarity. Other expectations of millennials may include a sense of purpose, collaborative culture, empowerment, etc. (Alesso-Bendisch, 2020).

Tolbzie (2008) recognised one of the major differences between the generation's attitudes by stating that millennials are more wired together than baby boomers. They encourage and embrace participation culture within the organisation; therefore, millennials are sometimes referred to as 'Trophy Kids'. In contrast, the baby boomer generation is more concerned about the competition than wining. Millennials acknowledge teamwork and prefer to move together as a team than trophy an individualistic win. Arguably, as Jones and Barrett (2016) highlighted in their article, there is a significant need to change the leadership approach to the millennial generation. According to them, a significant change has caused a complex environment to be formed in the workplace in time, technology, and societal changes. Effective leadership for millennials must begin and moves with an effective and strong team concept, where everyone is provided with the opportunity to participate. Therefore, Jones and Barrett (2016) recognised that the millennials generation believes in building success for everyone.

2.4 Turnover

According to Gilbert (2011), turnover can be costly to a business; it can be dangerous to the organisation. This is because it can slow down reaction time, ultimately resulting in competitors taking advantage (Kiessling *et al.*, 2012). Especially, turnover of the millennial generation as they are become an active part of organisations like Baby Boomers and their actions significantly impact future competition in the economy (Westerman *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, millennials need, and demands are changing due to having different outlook, as identified above. As suggested earlier, many e-retail

sectors are facing the retention issue of millennials especially after COVID-19, thus, making it essential for organisations to study the retention issue, especially in SME's where time and resources are limited. Failure in millennial retention may consequently result in an organisation losing its competitive advantage and performance level in the market. Therefore, signifying the need to have an effective employee engagement and management performance for millennials retention for future success.

2.5 Criticism on Millennials

Geyer (2016, p.2) criticised the millennials generation in one of their articles, referring to them as “narcissistic, immature, selfish, authors have assigned to them, such as “the selfie generation,” “generation me,” and “the peter pan generation.” This author criticised millennial to be over-inflated egoistic generation. However, even though everyone does not voice this opinion, it is part of a major older generation work group opinion. They consider millennials “to do whatever it takes attitude” as an immanent frame. On the other hand, others see them as passionate, creative, and hardworking individuals and praise them for their diversity and collaboration (Moon, 2014; Dellen, 2019). These individuals recognised millennials importance and appraised their different mindset as the generation with the ability to change the world.

Shepard (2018) pointed out in his article “Motivated Properly, Millennials Will Become Your Killer Employees” that the millennials generation desire to give back to the workforce and highlighted their workforce behavior by diving into the millennial impact report. He stated the following:

- 94% of millennials prefer to use their full potential of skills at the workplace.
- 77% of millennials acknowledge working in a team.
- 47% of millennials were seen volunteering for cause and non-profit charitable work in December 2017.

Furthermore, the article voiced millennials by pointing out some of their opinions, such as.

- Millennials are more solution-oriented rather than just focusing on problems.
- They believe everyone has a responsibility towards their society and country.

- Millennials want to work in an organization that believes in the institution's ability to create change.

Hewlett *et al.* (2009) also described millennials as a socially conscious generation with a very optimistic and confident personality. Nielsen (2017) also portrayed the millennial generation as more conformed to corporate socially responsible behavior than any other generation. They prefer to work in a CSR initiative organisation regardless of what product or service they offer. They consider societal wellbeing issue significantly and perceive it as one of the major factors they consider in the organisation when applying for a job.

Gavatorta (2012, p.62) states:

“Rather than immediately jumping to conclusions about your generational differences, focus on your similarities. That's not to say that all generational differences will go away. However, by taking the approach of looking for that common ground, you can lay the foundation for open communication and is to build trust.”

2.6 Employee Engagement

Albrecht (2010) pointed out that increased research momentum for employee engagement has been seen in recent years. Such and Wollard (2010) defined employee engagement as the employee's behavioural, cognitive, and emotional energy towards the organisation's success. A wide range of authors (Lancaster and Stillman, 2002; Johnson and Johnson, 2010; Atay and Ashlock, 2016) have been publishing books and journals claiming the importance of understanding generational differences to improve recruitment, retention, communication, management succession and engagement with employees.

According to Gatenby *et al.* (2009), employee engagement is one of the most concerning problems faced by managers worldwide. Employee engagement has captured many researchers' attention for many years because its effectiveness promises well-being for the individuals, stakeholders, and organisational performance (Lockwood, 2007). Employee engagement potential has been well recognised by many organisations, and its effect on Organisational performance has been well communicated in the past few years. However, regardless of the decades of research, it is still one of the emerging concepts.

Employee engagement first major article was published by Kahn (1990) while conducting his ethnographic research on engagement and disengagement, published around 31 years ago. According to Saks and Gruman (2014), two key themes have emerged from the term employee engagement in the past few years. Firstly, the success and importance of employee engagement on the organisation's success and second, from time to time, a decline in employee engagement has been seen within many organisations. Authors like Bates (2004) and Richman (2006) reported that profound disengagement occurs among employees in today's workforce. Bates (2004) also highlighted that the engagement gap is becoming an apparent problem, especially in the US market, causing the businesses to lose billions of dollars due to lost productivity from disengaged employees. Kahn (1990) employee engagement theory focuses on studying employee behavior and observing employee engagement while performing specific tasks throughout the day.

Schmitt *et al.* (2016) also agreed and shared similar opinion on employee engagement by stating that understanding the factors of employee's level of behavior and commitment at work will allow leaders to discover an index through which they can better motivate their employees, ultimately allowing them to boost employee engagement within the organisation. On the other hand, Riyanto *et al.* (2021) assert that job satisfaction and work motivation create a positive impact of the employee engagement. When the employees would feel that their efforts are being valued in the organisation, they would try their level best to increase their engagement for the better improvement of the company.

Employees' personal involvement/ engagement is crucial at the workplace (Kahn, 1990). If an employee is engaged fully, they will be able to assert their full effort in fulfilling their role and focus on finding ways to improve themselves or the overall organisation's performance (Hughes and Rog, 2008). In contrast to that, according to Kahn (1990) and Sonnentag and Fritz (2015), disengaged employees are likely to withdraw from work and focus on things/problems outside of their working environment. Therefore, authors like Milliken *et al.* (2015) suggested that organisations understand the concept of employee engagement and re-enforce organisations to establish a tool to better analyse their employee engagement and its effect on their organisation.

Employee engagement, job performance and organisational performance are closely related to each other. According to the view of Al-Dalahmeh et al. (2018), satisfied employees are likely to stay in the company for a long period of time. Most of the employees decides to leave a company when they realise that the organisation is not concentrated about their needs and wants which creates a dissatisfaction about their organisation. Therefore, they plan to leave the organisation and joined somewhere else where their efforts would be recognised properly. On the other hand, it has been found that Tepayakul and Rinthaisong (2018), it is the responsibility of human resource to retain the employees properly in the organisations by meeting their needs and wants properly. In order to hold back the effective people in the organisation for a long-term period it is necessary for them to provide good salary, rewards, bonus and appraisals to keep them to keep them happy and convince them to stay in their organisations for a long time. Retaining effective and satisfied employee would help the organisation in developing its performance.

According to Cook (2008), the passion and willingness of the employees towards the organisation success represent employee engagement. It is all about how stable employees are in their discretionary effort to help the organisation achieve its aim. Author characterised engagement as employee willingness to do what it takes to achieve organisational success. It can be in terms of going above or even below the expectation to ensure outstanding performance is contributed. It is a psychological contract between employee and employer. Cook (2008) reinforced that engaged employees are more concerned about organisation objective and are more prepared to invest more effort and time. Wellinset *al.* (2005) further stated that employee engagement provides affirmed connection between organisation, leaders, and employees.

Whittington *et al.* (2017) highlighted the importance of employee engagement by stating that disengaged employees indirectly impact organisation performance. Disengaged employees less likely to take part in productivity and are likely to withdraw themselves from work by having a high level of absenteeism. Disengaged employees can result in poor decision-making and can take excessive time to complete the job (Pech& Slade, 2006). Ayers (2007) also shared a similar opinion and pointed out that disengaged employees are likely to give a half per cent of their performance while receiving full wages. Therefore, it is crucial to set effective employee engagement, as

it allows the manager to align their employees with the organisation goals. According to Garber (2012), effective leadership is crucial for effective engagement. He stated that employee engagement is not just about motivating employees; it is also about making sure that employees' potential is fully utilised, such as their skills, creativity etc.

According to Kang and Sung (2017), employers use employee engagement to connect with their employees and implement and initiate a sense of empowerment within employees by instilling them to feel that their voices are heard and matters (Jiang and Luo, 2018). This will benefit employees in gaining their employees' loyalty and will allow them to strengthen their relationship with their customers (Stephens, 2020). Mazzei *et al.* (2016) highlighted the importance of employee engagement by stating that employers who engage effectively with their employee have a greater chance of success as their workforce will support them for growth and are likely to put more effort and innovation. In addition, highly engaged employees have contributed significantly to organisation performance and success due to increased productivity. Hakanen *et al.* (2018) further highlighted that engaged employees are likely to react positively and quickly to any change. Whittington *et al.* (2017) also highlighted that there is an interconnection between employee engagement, retention, and performance. Organisations are struggling to effectively engage with employees recently due to their inability to understand the culture of engagement within the working environment.

The managers and leaders of the organisations need to communicate clearly with their employees so that they can understand the needs and expectations properly. According to Moletsane et al, (2019), organisational productivity and employees' engagement are interrelated to each other. It is necessary to improve the engagement of the employees by increasing their satisfaction with the job as well as instilling a sense of pride in the company. The organisation needs to introduce effective leadership by following an effective human resources strategy, which encourages employee interaction, communication with the management as well as developing their organisational environment (Moletsane et al, 2019). Jena *et al.*, (2018) asserts that transformational leadership is very effective in encouraging employee engagement. This leadership allows the organisation to understand the psychological needs of the people and keep them happy in the organisations for a sustainable period. This kind of leadership is also very effective in creating a trustworthy bond with the employees (Jena *et al.*, 2018).

Proper recognition of the employees' efforts allows the employees to provide more productivity along with better performance to the company. Keeping the employees satisfied is vital for increasing the performance of the organisations. In fact, it also helps in increasing the employee strength of the company (Jena *et al.*, 2018).

On the other hand, Chin, et al. (2019) suggest that transformational leadership and employee engagement are co-dependent, meaning that inasmuch as transformational leadership inspires a highly engaged workforce, a workforce that manifests high levels of engagement also enables a transformational leader to function more effectively (Chin, et al., 2019). For example, a transformational leader requires workers who are open to communicating and interacting closely and frequently. Engaged workers demonstrate inherent tendencies that make their work environments more favourable for transformational leaders.

2.7 Four Different Models of Employee Engagement

2.7.1 Kahn (1990) Need-Satisfying Approach

Kahn's (1990) model is one of the first and widely adopted employee engagement models (Harter *et al.*, 2002; Rich *et al.*, 2010). Kahn (1990, p. 700) defined engagement as "*the simultaneous employment and expression of a person's 'preferred self' in task behaviours that promote connections to work and others, personal presence, and active full role performances*".

Kahn (1990) pointed out three domains of psychology affecting engagement at work as follows:

Meaningfulness: Sense of fulfilment at work through role/job performance. Kahn (1990) suggested that employees are likely to go the extra mile to do better when employees are offered meaningful work and are aware of its importance. Paukert *et al.* (2021) recent study reaffirms Kahn (1990) and considered meaningful work as one of the millennial expectations alongside appreciation, feedback, and career path.

Safety: Freedom to state oneself without fearing a negative impact on one's reputation or career. Kahn (1990) pointed out the need for employees to feel safe at work not only physically but also emotionally and cognitively.

Availability: Employee's sense of possessing appropriate skills and resources to do the job. Kahn (1990) suggested that employees should feel they have the skills and tools to do the job. Availability of resource is not enough employees must understand them (Wagner and Harter, 2006). Employees can appreciate their resources when provided with effective training and developing opportunities (Czarnowski, 2008). A recent study by Resicket *al.* (2007) further added and considered appropriate degree or educational background as another major factor required to do the job effectively.

According to Rich *et al.* (2010), Kahn suggested that employees can be emotionally, physically, and cognitively engaged, and the factors mentioned above can improve this engagement. May *et al.* (2004) were the first to publish empirical test result of Kahn's (1990) engagement model. Their research indicated that safety, availability, and meaningfulness have a positive impact on employee engagement at work. However, a more recent study done by Rich *et al.* (2010) pointed out and suggested that meaningfulness through job involvement, satisfaction and motivation through intrinsic means have failed to show any high impact on the level of engagement employees have at work. Regardless of that, Kahn (1990) model is still one of the most emerging frameworks of employee engagement,

2.7.2 Maslach *et al.* (2001) Burnout-Antithesis Approach

Maslach *et al.* (2001) was the first major researcher on employee engagement after Kahn (1990). He conceptualised engagement as positive antithesis burnout and defined engagement as employees' high activation and interest level due to a positive affective state of mind. Burnout at that time was characterised in two ways. First, it was linked to professions where employees were responsible for closely interacting with people in stressful situations.

Second, burnout was recognised as an antithesis to engagement at work as conceptualised by Maslach *et al.* (2001). Maslach *et al.* (2001) considered employees ineffectiveness and burnout to be the major reason for the destruction of engagement at the workplace. He tried to point out that employees' sudden change in how they feel about their current job is critical to know the cause for disengagement, such as why the once so important and meaningful work has turned unpleasant for the employees.

Maslach *et al.* (2001) characterised three dimensions of burnout which are as follows:

Exhaustion: Overusing or depletion in one physical and mental state.

Cynicism: Detaching oneself from a certain job or task or depersonalising the work by ignoring various important aspects of the job

Ineffectiveness: It was directly influenced by the other two burnout dimensions and recognised as feeling lack of achievement and incompetence at work. This framework was later tested by Schaufelli *et al.* (2002) and Shirom (2003), and they redefined engagement by characterising it to employee's dedication, effort, energy, and absorption at work. Employee's state of mind plays a critical role in engagement. Schaufelli *et al.* (2002) and Shirom (2003) renamed it as work engagement.

Maslach *et al.* (2001) model was criticised for de-voiding Kahn (1990) cognitive process of engagement and focused solely on employee emotion and physical state.

2.7.3 Harter et al. (2002) Satisfaction-Engagement Approach

This is the third perspective model of employee engagement. This was developed in the early 21st century and is a widely studied and cited piece of engagement literature. Harter *et al.* (2002) first studied employee engagement with the business outcome and profit. His study indicated that employee engagement has a significant impact on the organisation's productivity and profitability.

Harter *et al.* (2002) model was further extended by Luthans and Peterson (2002). They examined the relationship between effective leadership and employee engagement. Their study indicated that there is a positive impact of leadership effectiveness and efficiency on employee engagement.

Luthans and Peterson (2002, p.376) stated that “the most profitable work units of companies have people doing what they do best, with people they like, and with a strong sense of psychological ownership.” This model has been continuously studied and the most updated by many authors, including from (Jones and Harter, 2005; Wagner and Harter, 2006; Fleming and Asplund, 2007, Avolio and Avey, 2008)

2.7.4 Saks (2006) Multi-Dimensional Approach

The fourth and final model of engagement is put forward by Saks (2006). His model emerged from the multidimensional perspective of the engagement of employees at the

workplace. Saks (2006) was the first one to differentiate and separate job engagement from Organisational engagement. His research was the first to examine employee engagement consequence in the literature and connected body work into practitioner research to study the connecting drivers of engagement with the consequences of employee engagement.

Saks (2006, p602) defined engaged as “*Distinct and unique construct consisting of cognitive, emotional, and behavioural components . . . associated with individual role performance.*” His definition was derived and developed from all the previous model (Kahn, 1990; Maslach *et al.*, 2001; Harter *et al.*, 2002) and extended current thinking and literature (Saks, 2006) of engagement by developing a three-component model; cognitive, emotional, and behavioural.

Saks (2006) study indicated that job satisfaction, Organisational support through positive climate and fairness at the workplace impact employee engagement and significantly influence the outcome such as performance and productivity. Saks (2006) research model is also one of the widely used and cited models, especially when studying emerging employee engagement (Dalal *et al.*, 2008; Macey *et al.*, 2009). Regardless, each framework suggested achieving absorption and concentration at the workplace; employees must be physically, emotionally, and resourcefully ready and updated to do and complete the work.

2.8 Comparison of Models

Currently, no single model has been seen to be dominating over the others. However, according to Christian and Slaughter (2007), Maslach *et al.* (2001) model is the most widely cited. In addition to that, all four models may seem to have a different perspective, but they all conclude to similar results/findings that employee engagement has a potential impact on organisation performance (Maslach *et al.*, 2001; Harter *et al.*, 2002; Saks, 2006; Arakawa and Greenberg, 2007 and Christian *et al.*, 2011). All these frameworks assist HR managers in scaffolding their organisation by conceptualising how their employees relate to work and then assist them in developing strategies accordingly to fulfil three-component models of employee engagement (behavioural, cognitive and emotional).

Evolving current century workplaces and uncertain and challenging environments makes it difficult for organisations to engage with their employees regardless of industry. As a result, it has become necessary for organisations to reshape their employee engagement strategy. These four models can assist organisations in doing so regardless of being in the state of continuous evolution (Shuck *et al.*, 2011).

2.9 Employee Engagement Impact on Job Performance

According to Crawford *et al.* (2010), job performance and employee engagement are co-related. Bailey *et al.*'s (2016) review on employee's work history indicates that employees are likely to do better or even beyond expectation when they understand their work role. Bolino and Grant (2016) further indicated that when employees feel their opinions are heard and valued, they are likely to be more concerned about business performance. When employees input is considered in the future direction of the business, they are likely to feel empowered. They tend to work more on making decisions considering the betterment of the organisation.

Leaders play a critical role in employee engagement. According to William and Thompson (2017), only leaders who understand and recognise the connection between employee engagement and job performance will be able to identify those least effective policies within the organisation and then be able to make changes accordingly to improve them.

Walumbwa *et al.* (2018) further indicated that engaged employees are likely to outperform their competitors and assist organisations by continuously thriving and sustaining success. This is especially important for millennials as they can contribute significantly towards the organisation success. Millennials want their opinion to be heard, and only by communicating and effectively engaging managers will be able identify the potential skills and abilities of each millennial. This is because they can only fully utilise their positive qualities and creative ideas to their advantage by effectively engaging with them such as they can apply their technology-driven knowledge to smoothen their overall business procedure, consequently resulting in more cost-effective productivity (Espinoza *et al.*, 2010; Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010; Balda and Mora, 2011; Gregory, 2012).

2.10 Leadership and its Impact on Organisation Performance

In most companies, whether small or large, leaders are often mainly judged based on how their employees are performing (Tuet *al.*, 2012). If an organisation is not performing well, then leaders are held accountable for it. Managers from the top hierarchy may address such issues by either terminating underperformed leaders or retraining them (Amankwah-Amoahet *al.*, 2016). Leaders play a critical role in the organisation, and they significantly influence employees. Managers who understand their influence on employees are likely to have a greater chance of success than those who do not (Stephens, 2020).

According to Jones (2017), the organisation needs to introduce effective leadership to develop the performance of the organisations. The leadership has the ability to influence the employees to develop their work and bring positivity in the attitude and behaviour of the employees properly (Jones, 2017). When employees recognise that the employers are very concerned about them, then they reciprocate by trying their best to provide better outcomes to the company to meet the organisation's goals and objectives (Jones, 2017). Leaders play a crucial role in every organisation. It is the responsibility of the leaders to motivate their people positively towards the organisational goals by encouraging them to improve their career opportunities. Paais and Pattiruhu (2020) further explain that motivation mediates job satisfaction and leadership. In effect, good leadership results in a more motivated workforce. In turn, a more motivated workforce comprises workers who are more satisfied and engaged with their jobs. The significance of this revelation is that it emphasizes the importance of effective leadership in fostering employee engagement, and consequently inspiring improvements in organizational performance.

Chiniara and Bentein (2016) indicates that leadership is directly involved with employee's performance and satisfaction. According to Maurer and London (2018), there are three types of employees at the workplace. First, employees are motivated and work towards the organisation's success (Buckingham and Goodall, 2015). Second, who are less motivated but work to keep their position within the organisation (Ni and Van Wart, 2015) and employees who are not motivated or regards their work (Van Wingerden and Van der Stoep, 2018). Bolden (2016) highlighted those only leaders who engage effectively will be able to categorise their employees accordingly and will be able to develop them over time by connecting with them. Leroy *et al.* (2015) also re-

instated the importance of leadership by stating that how leaders interact with employees can significantly impact overall organizational culture and work environment.

Tung *et al.* (2017) emphasised that effective leader usually adopts various leadership style to manage their employees' needs and wants better. This is because they know that they will improve their employees' overall quality by effectively managing them. According to Kumar and Krisharaj(2018), different leadership style are necessary to manage multiple individuals; therefore, large organisations tend to hire different people with varying personalities to better manage their workforce (Erickson, 2017). Stephens (2020) also reinforced the importance of leadership by stating that ineffective leadership can significantly impact an organisation's overall performance. Cloutier *et al.* (2015) underlined that organisation tends to invest a lot of time and resources in recruiting and selecting employees and spending even more resources when training them within the organisation. Therefore, making it important for them to retain them.

2.11 Employee Engagement and Millennial Workers

CIPD (2017) specified that the employee engagement as proposing a strategy, which will result in creating a win-win for both employees and employers. It is not just about motivating employees, but it is about creating positive experiences for employees, such as emotion, commitment, and meaningful connection. Meaningful connection should not solely be formed between employers and employees but also between employees. According to Miryala and Gade (2016), employee engagement is of major concern by HR managers. This is because it has been proved and seen on numerous occasions that engaged employees are more likely to be productive than those who are not engaged (Miryala & Gade, 2016).

Employee engagement is not merely a product of the environment in which an individual operates. Rather, certain individuals are better suited to specific roles and jobs due to their inherent traits (De Jong, et al., 2019). This means that workers whose inherent traits are a good match for the jobs that they perform are more likely to be engaged on the job compared to those who work in unsuitable positions (De Jong, et al., 2019). It is the responsibility of the organisation to recruit the right employees in the vacant position (Shipton, et al., 2021). They need to focus highly on their

performance and provide proper training so that they can understand their responsibilities more effectively (Shipton, et al., 2021). Every employee has a unique talent, but it is the responsibility of the organisations to give them the right opportunity at the right time to make the most out of these talents and abilities. The organisation needs to understand the skills gaps in the employees and train them accordingly so that they do not face problem handling their responsibilities (Shipton, et al., 2021). Apart from this, the company also needs to include various scheme such as increment, promotions and many more so that the employees get the motivation to improve their performance continuously. Shriar (2016) stated that approximately 87% of employees were seen not being engaged or were actively seen disengaged at the organisational workplace in many countries. From this, it can be said that management performance along with employee engagement is becoming a highly critical issue as well as the deepest concern for several organisations.

Macky *et al.* (2008) pointed out that ineffective employee engagement is because managers fail to understand and address their employees' fundamental issues and questions. These issues and questions can be differences or misunderstandings between multi-generations employees and employers (Bersin, 2014). Therefore, considering employee engagement carefully is critical. To explore more about employee engagement, different HRM practices will be discussed in alignment with the millennial generation.

2.12 Recruitment

According to CIPD (2018):

Good recruitment is vital for every organisation - finding the right people for the right roles at the right time. It ensures that the workforce has the relevant skills and abilities for its current and future needs. Effective recruitment is not just about filling an immediate vacancy but about having an impact on longer-term issues, such as future skills development, Organisational performance, and employer brand.

Management plays a critical role for the organisation as they are responsible for incorporating business goals and ideas to achieve them through their workforce (Shafter *et al.*, 2016). In other words, they are responsible for managing the organisation workforce and their performance. According to Ohler and Levinson (2012), the best possible way for an organisation to achieve its performance objective is by making its

employees feel comfortable at the workplace. Their goals and values should fit with the organisations, referred to as “person-organisation fit” by Arthur *et al.* (2006). Carr *et al.* (2006) also shared a similar opinion by stating that organisations tend to have high job satisfaction, commitment, and reduced employee turnover when an effective person-organisation fit is present.

An organisation always aims to achieve success, not just at a certain point in time. Therefore, it is critical for managers to continuously work towards achieving performance objectives within the organisation to ensure success is sustained in the future. Schneider *et al.* (2013, p.362) also re-emphasised the criticality of having effective employees for both current and future performance by stating that “the shared basic assumptions, values and beliefs that characterised a setting and are taught to newcomers as the proper way to think and feel.....”

Among all managers, selection and recruitment managers play the most discreet role. They are responsible for making sure they hire the right candidate for the role considering Organisational culture and needs and providing information to the candidate. This will allow them to determine if their needs/goals/value matches that of organisations (Schaubroeck *et al.*, 1998, Compton:2009).

Millennials are one of the most challenging generations. They have different values; therefore, managers must move away from traditional recruitment strategies to approach them. Millennials are digital native; thus, the online recruitment process should be adopted. Silvestre (2016) claimed that millennial, regardless of being satisfied at work, seek opportunities elsewhere. They look for opportunities on social media, such as LinkedIn, and online job portals like Indeed.com etc. Therefore, Buckley *et al.* (2016) advised that managers must ensure they use up-to-date recruitment methods to recruit potential millennials into the organisation. With social media recruitment, it is also necessary for managers to communicate clearly about the job responsibility, career progression opportunity and salary. Effective use of the word to attract potential candidates plays a critical role when hiring through social media.

2.13 Organisational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Leaders are required to continuously engage with millennials to remind them why they need to remain with their organisation and have them look at the benefits available

within their current organisation rather than the competitors. (Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011; Thompson & Gregory, 2012). Govaerts *et al.* (2011) highlighted that millennial like supervisors who appreciate them and offer them more freedom and authority. Rewards and support from Organisational leaders can increase worker devotion for blue-collar and white-collar specialists (Joshi, 2012).

Ambrose *et al.* (2013) further state that to maintain Organisational citizenship behavior, especially millennials, it is critical to have a strong relationship between managers and employees. Gilbert (2011) reinforces, to retain employees, managers must understand the different generation of employees and are required to have an ability to continuously engaged with each set of generations. Mayfield and Mayfield (2014), states that OCB is achieved when employees believe in the Organisational value and work toward the organisation's progress. The author further highlighted the benefit of OCB by stating that it contributes significantly towards the performance of the business, lower turnover, and cost.

2.14 Diverse and Inclusive Workforce

According to the view of Agbontaen (2019), workplace issues create a negative impact on the organisations along with employee performance. Organisations need to introduce a diverse workforce to create a sustainable and diverse organisational environment. Every people have the right to get equal opportunities in a company. An inclusive and diverse workforce has the ability to create a positive impact on the employees and thereby it allows the organisations to increase their employees' strength properly. On the other hand, it has been argued by Das (2019), diversity is a huge power that helps in developing the success of an organisation. Employees are the main source of any company as without employee support a company would not be able to operate its business. It is necessary to promote diversity and inclusion in the organisation to create a positive image in every employee. Diversity and an inclusive workplace have the ability to motivate the employees. Every group of people need to be valued equally in the workplace despite their religion, gender and many more. The company need to introduce an inclusive leader for developing the engagement of the employees and providing them with the right to participate in decision making.

According to CIPD (2020), "Diversity is about recognising the difference. It's acknowledging the benefit of having a range of perspectives in decision-making and

the workforce being representative of the organisation's customers." The concept of diversity came into existence back in the 1980s, which is nearly three decades ago. It started in the US to create a more positive and broader perfective workplace with equal working opportunity for immigrant and minority groups. However, it caused complexity in the strategy process for HR, especially as they must re-evaluate their process, leadership, and Organisational culture.

"Diverse workforce is now a global phenomenon" (Sharma and Mann, p1). More organisations are embracing a diverse workforce to benefit from the varied skills. Another reason for it to rise is due to the increase in globalisation. The diverse cultures within the organisations are now dramatically changing and shaping marketing worldwide. According to Etsy *et al.* (1995), a diverse workforce is beneficial for organisation and employees as it increases opportunities, innovation, and employability. The association of employees with different cultures will result in an organisation having an extensive pool of knowledge, expertise, and skills that will allow them to go beyond the verge of management and HR aspects at the workplace and broaden employment opportunities.

According to the view of O'Donovan (2019), diversity and inclusion have the ability to improve the employees' turnover rate of the organisations. It provides the opportunity to the company to improve the cost-saving, reduce absenteeism and many more. It provides the opportunity for the company to create a friendly environment and allow the employees to work cooperatively toward one goal. Inclusion and diversity help the organisations in improving creativity as well as innovation and increase flexibility. A better understanding relationship is being created between the employees and employers. Moreover, the organisation gets the opportunity to increase commitment, business growth and market expansion as well.

On the other hand, it has been stated by Jonsen et al (2021), inclusion and diversity help in employer branding. Employer branding creates a positive impact on organisational performance. Diversity allows the organisation to create value by providing more importance to its employees. The employees prefer to work in an organisation the company give importance to their people and provide equal opportunities to everyone.

According to Patrick and Washington (2018), *"millennials have not only opened the floodgates on the definitions of diversity and inclusion, but they've also begun to shape*

the workplace to reflect those definitions.” Deloitte (2020) indicated in their global Human capital Trust report that the significance of diversity at the workplace has increased up to 74% over three years (Deloitte, 2020). Their research shows how diversity and inclusion play a critical role in the workplace and significantly increase employee engagement, performance, and profitability. Recently, diversity and inclusion are seen as major driving factors for employee engagement, performance and even retention.

Regardless of the advantages, a diverse workforce is not without its negative aspects. It requires effective management to be put in place to ensure an extensive set of skills and knowledge are utilised properly, and harmony between each member is built irrespective of disparities. They are responsible for creating a safe and friendly environment for their employees and avoiding any issue that may hinder them, such as workplace discrimination and making the most of their employees' different experiences and unique talents.

2.15 Talent Management

Talent management is defined as a process where management attracts, identify, and retain potential individuals by nurturing, progressing, and rewarding them. The key aim of talent management is to aid talented employees in developing an organisation's sustainability (Beardwell and Clayton, 2014). A simpler approach is a process where management identifies potential individuals and then facilitates them to ensure high performance and contribution are added to the organisation. Generation Y also known as millennials, born between 1982-2004, are seen to be the ones dominating the workplace. As mentioned before, the millennial generation is causing dramatic change because of their completely different prospective toward work. Therefore, organisations must develop knowledge on millennials and how their talent can be managed to succeed in the future. Marchington and Wilkinson (2012) identified two approached to talent management, exclusive and inclusive approach.

2.16 Exclusive Approach

According to Poole (2010), the ‘war for talent’ idea is the basis for this adaptation. The term war for talent originates from the battle in which organisation fight to grasp limited talented individuals. An organisation with effective talent management aims to achieve

a competitive advantage over competitors by developing and retaining right talent within the organisation, which sync with the idea 'war for talent'. The exclusive approach is used widely by many organisations worldwide and ranks employees based on their talent.

For instance, high potential employees are ranked as first and are given the most resources in succession planning, whereas, on the other hand, least potential employees are ranked as third. However, this approach is identified to possess many dangers as managers tend to invest more in their expected talented employees than those who may have potential but are overlooked in the talent pool. Furthermore, it will gain favouritism and biases within the individual, thus, causing demotivation and unwanted emotion. This can result in organisations being ineffective in using their current talent and losing their undiscovered potential employees to competitors.

2.17 Inclusive Approach

The inclusive approach varies from the exclusive approach and considers all their employees as talented. Management using this approach aims to use all their workforce to full potential. They consider each of their individuals to have potential and will unleash its full potential when necessary. To do this, HR manager tends to invest more time and money in carefully recruiting, engaging, leadership and career development.

Mayangdarastri and Khusna (2020) indicated the significance of career development by stating that it is essential for organisations to create an environment for millennials that offer clear career paths and career development. An organisation can fulfil millennial needs of appreciation and satisfaction by creating such an environment, ultimately building healthy relationships within the organisation. This approach can be effective; however, it can be very expensive in practice. Furthermore, everyone receives fewer resources as they are spread to every employee working in the organisation (Clake and Winkler, 2006).

2.18 Hybrid Approach

Thunnissen *et al.* (2013) concluded in their research that both exclusive and inclusive approaches have their benefits and drawbacks. They should consider all the variances, including the number of generations working for them, their business climate, and the

type of industry they are operating in. Managers need to understand all these variances before deciding which approach to adopt, as sometimes, not one approach is suitable. In that instance, a hybrid approach should be adopted. According to Tansley *et al.* (2007), both approaches may seem to be on the opposite end of the spectrum, but in practice, they both are appropriate when aligning with the organisation's need.

The millennials generation is becoming more apparent in the workplace, resulting in organisations gaining strong awareness regarding their requirement. Thunnissen *et al.* (2013) also raised millennials' talent management by stating that changes are necessary to ensure millennials are integrated into the strategy and should be modelled just as equal as the organisation objective.

2.19 Talent Attraction

Talent attraction involves putting effective recruitment and selection techniques in place to identify the skills required and attract them through a wider external labour market to meet HR needs. Attraction is primarily based on two factors: financial and non-financial. Financial reward was recognised to be the major factor in attracting employees. However, according to Kadakia (2017), things have changed, and today's workforce, such as millennials, has different expectations from work. Furthermore, there are skill shortages and climate changes, resulting in financial reward not being an effective method for attraction on how it used to be.

On the other hand, as non-financial rewards are based on how organisations brand themselves, such as attribute and quality organisation, make them distinctive from other organisations, especially their competitors. One of the main employer brand factors is corporate social responsibility, one of the most discussed topics. Nowadays, people are becoming increasingly concerned about how an organisation is impacting society and the environment. Especially millennials (generation Y) are more driven very much by values (Gouldner, 2016). They are recognised to have a serious concern for society than any other generation before. McGlone (2011) research states that CSR concern should be genuine and transparent between the organisation and their commitment to offering back to society. CSR commitment should never be used solely to gain business success, as it will backfire by getting a bad image from the press and millennials.

2.20 Learning and Development

CIPD (2012) highlighted that learning and development is all about how an organisation develops skills, capabilities, and competencies within its workforce to ensure a high-quality workforce sustains success. Tulgan (2009) pointed out that millennials do not characterised victory by climbing the corporate step, resulting in them not being fulfilled by repetitive work under the pretense of “paying dues” with the promise of advancement. Tulgan (2009) further reinstates that millennial are trying to find more prompt rewards, but not necessarily by financial means. Millennials are more willing to work on ventures that give learning and development opportunities (Baldonado&Spangenburg, 2009). Millennials, who seen their boomer and older Generation X guardians persevere the primary wave of major cutbacks, have gotten a handle on the thought that lifetime employment is generally a myth (Tulgan, 2009).

Therefore, it was identified that millennials are not concerned with what part they fulfil by moving through the organisation; instead, they centre on the company's part in their life story. To successfully attract and retain millennials, Tulgan (2009) re-in states that managers are required to illustrate how working on a given project will provide the opportunity for them to learn something new or at least give a valuable set of “resume points” for them to cite when competing for future assignments or positions.

Brack and Kelley (2012) described millennials as continuous learners, diverse thinker, and active team player, conscious about their society and very much oriented toward achievements. Feiertag and Berge (2008) considered millennials to have a hypertext mindset and suggested a learning procedure based on frequent activity changes than traditional tutorial-lecture style format. Millennials were raised with technology and are influenced by it. Therefore, Shaw and Fairhurst (2008) pointed out that technology influence on millennials has raised the need to increasingly develop structure and assertive assignment for them.

Skiba and Barton (2006) considered millennials to align with the active learning style because of their proactive nature and innovative-fuelled personality driven by curiosity, discovery, and exploration. Some researchers recommended and emphasised that managers should engage with millennials when developing learning strategies within the organisation. They can achieve involvement by millennials by giving them choices and collaborative opportunities. In other words, millennials will feel part of the process and will likely create their learning within the courses. On the other hand, Monaco and

Martin (2007) concern millennials' involvement by stating that it might cause hindrance to decision-making skills through over-utilization of group activities.

Ezikova and Martinello (2020) and Jacob (2020) also signified the importance of development and suggested that organisations should invest in millennials' professional and career development. When millennials are provided with personal and professional development opportunities, they tend to feel motivated and connected with the organisation and put more effort towards achieving its goals and objectives. Additionally, the development will enhance the skills and abilities of current employees, consequently resulting in increasing productivity and improving the organisation's overall procedure (Adkins and Rigoni, 2016). After numerous research, Spiegel (2011), CEO of corporate training and leadership development company, put forward millennials expectation from an employer as follows:

2.21 Coaching

Whitmore (2002, p.41) defined coaching as *“unlocking a person’s potential to maximize their performance. It is helping them to learn rather than teaching them.”* According to Singh *et al.* (2012), millennials expect autonomy for their managers and expect development opportunities for their managers. Unlike the previous generations, millennials expect more from their leaders than just direction. They are recognised as active learners as they are digitally native and have multiple sources of information at hand. They do not expect their managers to be experts but still expect some form of coaching and mentoring. Coaching is recognised as one of the most effective ways to satisfy millennials' expectations of autonomy and development. Millennials expect continuous coaching and feedback from their employer. Coaching keeps millennials on track, boosts their morale, and keeps them engaged in their work (Brack and Kelly, 2012). Spiegel (2011) further suggested that coaching does not have to be time-consuming and can be done through simple means of short email. Berger (2019) suggested four ways to coach millennials in one of his articles which are:

- Understand millennial and empathise with them. The millennial generation is different from other generations and focuses significantly on positively impacting society. They look for more than money at the workplace and seek out coaching from their leaders. They expect to have a good relationship with their leaders and share more transparent communication with them. They expect

their managers to listen to them and understand them and recognise their passion. They prefer to have a relationship of trust and compassion with their leader (Balda and Mora, 2011).

- Encourage free thinking to millennials by empowering and challenging them. Unfortunately, millennials tend not to respond efficiently when they are told what and how to do it (Gregory, 2012).
- Encourage their creativity and help them tap their imagination by listening to their ideas. As a result, millennials have been recognised as champions of creative ideas (Espinoza *et al.*, 2010).
- Focus on their effort. In an eagerness to achieve something, Millennials tend to miss important details or overlook some important details. Therefore, managers, instead of criticising them for those thin details, should nurture them with a can-do attitude by encouraging them (Gupta, 2020)

Atay and Ashlock (2018) millennials look for coaching culture within the organisation as it shows that company value their employees and offers one to one relationship to them. Coaching, when placed effectively, allows millennials to identify the potential development areas. It allows millennials to gain insight as individuals and identify their development barriers and pathways. It also helps millennials overcome their lack of sense of responsibility and accountability, as has been criticized by many authors (Deal *et al.*, 2010).

2.22 Collaborations

Peccianti (2020, p.26) stated collaboration as “*collaboration is achieving something with other people, experiencing power through other people, not by ordering a group of followers to do your bidding.*” Millennials are considered natural collaborators. Nicholas and Lewis (2008) pointed out that millennials like working in a team and prefer work collaborations with their colleagues. Alsop (2008) also pointed out that millennials prefer to work in groups to give them a sense of unity and avoid risk. Howe and Strauss (2007) research further indicated that millennials value technology and relationship significantly more than any other generation. Group work value stems from that, and millennials prefer to socialise more and work together as a team than any other

generation before. Millennials have been brought up in a teamwork environment and find working in group fun.

Therefore, collaborations and teamwork have become part of their lifestyle. To ensure effective collaboration is achieved, employers should communicate the purpose of group collaboration, goals, deadlines, and any business boundaries. In general words, effective communication is the key. Millennial generations have also been recognized to be efficient in multi-tasking and productive use of technology; therefore, on several occasions, it can be seen in producing quality work even at the last minute (Heskett, 2007). Gavitorta (2012) also suggested that millennials work more efficiently through collaboration as they are family-centric and has been raised working in teams.

Tapscott (2009, p1.63) pointed out that “*Collaboration is how Millennials get things done.*” Grotkamp *et al.* (2012) also reinforced the importance of collaboration by saying that having people with different experience, opinion and knowledge can result in a better and more innovative outcome. Diversity is also one of the preferences millennials have when working in a team (Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010). They expect their employees to offer a team working environment and autonomy, flexibility, and power (Connor and Shaw, 2008; Twenge *et al.*, 2010).

2.23 Measures

Structure and measuring system are part of millennials nurturing and is accustomed to these systems. They expect employers to communicate how their performance will be measured and assessed. In general, they expect their employers to make them fully aware of job assessment criteria (Brack and Kelly, 2012). Deloitte (2015) research indicates that only 51% of companies were developing and aligning their goals to employees. Most of the companies were seen setting annual targets and were only seen revisiting their goals and targets at the end of the year. As millennials prefer frequent feedback, they expect their leaders/managers to communicate goals and provide clear guidelines for achieving the target. They expect to be part of goal setting, want the goal to be communicated transparently, and expect to revisit goals more often, if not monthly, then quarterly at least.

Deloitte (2015) research further indicated that companies who were seen to be revisiting their goals quarterly were seen to have higher productivity and retention than those who

did it yearly. Sun (2017) highlighted in one of his articles that high-performing organisations like Google and Intel had been seen adopting a transparent and straightforward goal-setting process called OKR (objective and key results). They are one of the most successful companies and adopted simpler and effective processes to set ambitions and measurable objectives for their employees. Deloitte (2015) reaffirms that employees feel comfortable when they know what they are doing and can see what their peers are doing and are aware of the performance measurement process.

2.24 Motivation

Millennials, as mentioned several times above, are one of the dramatically different generations of all time. They are not driven by money and are very socially conscious. Millennials have numerous expectations from work, and comfortable working environment through a friendly and engaged workplace rather than a bureaucratic structure is one of the expectations they may have. Gupta (2020) reaffirms that a friendly atmosphere is one of the expectations of millennials. Spiegel (2011) suggested that organizing simple lunch gathering as a pizza party or even giving them a day off for a job well done will boost their motivation.

Even though major millennials attitude and perspective on money are different from other generations, some millennials are still influenced significantly by financial rewards and considered money an important motivational factor. (Rainer and Rainer, 2011). According to Desjardins (2019), motivational support is becoming crucial for managers, especially when managing millennials. This is because their motivational drivers are shifting dramatically from the previous generation. Motivational support here supplies foundational support to leaders as it directly links to employees' willingness to put a certain level of effort into completing the task. Millennials prefer working hard to meet their level incomes for leisure time and health. They expect the work-life balance to be offered by their managers/leaders.

2.25 Leadership

According to Solaja (2016), managing a multi-generational workforce demands strong leadership, recognition throughout the organisation that different generations may need different management styles, and a transparent performance management system that demonstrates how performance is rewarded. Leaders must establish a climate within

the organisation that encourages employee retention and motivates employees of all generations (Kogan, 2007). Yukl (2010) reaffirms the importance of leadership by saying that leaders are directly linked to how motivated, developed, and capable their employees are in carrying out tasks and projects they are offered.

According to Newman (2010), millennials were raised with supervision and are influenced by effective leadership. They expect effective leadership to work with and look up for leader who are honest, have integrity, and treat them respectfully by making them feel part of the team and success. Newman (2010) considered leaders to play a vital role in the learning and development of millennials. They should engage with them by communicating vision and big pictures to what and why they are doing and how important their roles are towards achieving that vision. Leaders should offer projects that will provide them with meaningful learning components and challenge them to progress further.

2.26 Psychological Contract

A psychological contract is often defined as a mutual agreement between employer and employees regarding expectations and obligation towards each other. This contract is based on mutual understanding and allows better alignment and reliance between the employee-employer relationship (Rousseau, 2004). The effective psychological contract often leads to high productivity and support by employees. On the other hand, Ye *et al.* (2012) highlighted that if the contract is missing or not been mutually agreed upon, such as in the case of the previous generation where only direction was given than employees, especially millennials, tend to feel demotivated, eventually resulting in having a major influence on their attitude and the performance outcome.

To foster mutuality, it is essential to have open and frequent communication between both employees and employer. This is because only then its substantiality can be achieved (Persson&Wasioleski, 2015). Different generations have different expectations and schema from the workplace. This is because each generation faced different circumstances, such as, in the case of millennials, they saw the dot-com bubble burst in 2002 and the global financial crisis in 2008 (Gosse, 2017). These incidents, apart from the societal evolution of the trend, significantly shape the psychological contract. Therefore, managers must define, evaluate, and communicate those shared

mutually understood beliefs, expectations, and emotions sensibly. Effective coaching can also assist the organisation in cultivating mutuality in a psychological contract (Jones *et al.*, 2016; Kahn, 2014).

Kombarakaran *et al.* (2008) pointed out that effective coaching results in employees' better understanding of their strengths and weaknesses. Kombarekaran *et al.* (2008) reaffirmed that when there is an increase in need of self-awareness among employees through clear personal insight, consequently resulting in their confidence to boost up, potentially influencing the physiological contract between the employee and employer. This is because employees will reciprocate their sense of beliefs, expectations, and obligations much more clearly when forming a contract with their managers or working to resolve any difference between them.

2.27 Millennial Criticism on Learning and Development

Hoover *et al.* (2016) criticised millennials by stating them as “complexity avoider” Author proclaimed millennials to be impatient, adequately affecting the learning standard set by educators. Millennials have become prone to quick solutions for any query; they would instantly search for answers on Google. Their behavior pattern is more prone to delivering to attitude than seeking to. Hoover *et al.* (2016) stated that millennials do not have the requisite digging out information skills. Millennials are super-fast data receivers as they were raised playing video games and are undoubtedly highly proficient in processing images and eye-hand coordination skills. However, on the other hand, if the game is infinite in its manifestation or has been effortless, then millennials will lose interest in the process. Hoover *et al.* (2016) tried to reinstate that millennial get bored easily. The only way to strive for their attention is by making sure their objective is interesting.

Furthermore, communication is necessary; if the transition of information is systematic complex, millennials might lose track because of lack of interest as they are prone to super-fast information processing. To further add to it, Hoover *et al.* (2018) considered millennials to be narcissistic as they are super sensitive to information and can resist information that might disconfirm their pretentiousness.

Another criticism of millennials is that they expect frequent feedback but only positive feedback. Many managers reported that it is difficult to communicate any negative feedback to millennials (Anderson *et al.*, 2016).

2.28 Pay, Rewards and Motivation

According to Nicholas and Guzman (2009), employers should consider taking the traditional 9-5 work schedule out of the box. Technology-driven generation millennials prefer flexibility at the workplace. They expect their employer to control how they prefer to work and get work done instead of timing their presence at the workplace. Millennials have grown up with rigid scheduling parents, which often find it challenging to balance their time out of work. They prefer a balance between work and their personal life. They do not like working extra hours but prefer to keep their timelines on getting work done. Employers should reconsider flexibility in the workplace and develop strategic flexible time. For instance, working hours for a week on the desk should be allocated with scheduling variation. Employees can choose between the early morning shift or late night to ensure they come to work with a refreshed state of mind and perform at a high level at work.

Espinoza and Ukleja (2016) suggested that timely promotions should be offered to millennials. Support and recognition thrive millennial to work hard and expect their efforts to be timely praised by employers. Managers can do this by praising them regularly, offering a slight pay rise or even a slight title change will encourage them. Offer success milestone and give them advance celebration to motivate them. Furthermore, the employer should offer a learning opportunity to millennials. EdAssist research stated that 41% of millennials voted to choose for the workplace that offers higher pay (EdAssist, 2015).

In contrast, the rest of the millennials opted to choose a career and workplace that offers personal and professional growth. For example, Hosie (2017) pointed out in one of her articles, *“millennials are struggling at work because their parents gave them a medal for coming last.”* Sinek (2016) stated in his article that he knew one of the millennials who went to his boss to get a promotion regardless of a pay rise. Sinek (2016) pointed out that social media influence millennials, and on platforms like Facebook or LinkedIn, they want to show how fast they are progressing.

Overall, millennials prefer to work in an organisation with positive colleague relationships and managers who appreciate them. They want incentive compensation in the form of learning development, in the form of a rise in the title or even a ticket to

their favourite sports or concert. Developing effective pay, reward and motivation strategy is crucial for millennials retention. As the millennial generation loses interest easily, managers should ensure effective motivation strategies is put in place with striving goals that will offer them progressive growth at work. Managers should find the right balance between monetary rewards and recognition. To do this, it is significantly important for managers to be engaged with employees.

Furthermore, offering effective incentive compensation will allow employers to retain millennials and allow them to keep track of how they are progressing. Lastly, regardless of regular feedback, the manager must recognize that achievement should be made special for outstanding performance. Doing this will ensure that other employees are encouraged to reach the same level of outcome in future.

2.29 HRM-Regular and Irregular Inflexibility

An increasing number of HR are considering having flexible HRM at their workplace. Flexible HRM is a much newer context, and not many employees are fully aware of it. Hill *et al.* (2008) described flexible HRM as where organisations allow employees to decide when and how they want to work. Before discussing the advantages of flexible HRM, differences between regular and irregular flexible HRM will be highlighted.

According to Kooji *et al.* (2013), irregular HRM practice is where organisation facilitates their employee to pursue personal goals by reducing their workload, i.e., by allowing them additional exceptional leave, unpaid leave or even exception from working overtime. This practice is widely used by other organisation as; it does not require fundamental adjustment to the workplace (Macdermid *et al.*, 2000). On the other hand, regular flexibility HRM practice aims to provide employees with the freedom to choose their work routine daily and the opportunity to flexibly job share.

According to Hewlett *et al.* (2009), Harvard Business Review published their study, which indicates that the vast majority (87%) of millennials prefer to have a flexible work schedule and consider it an important factor when looking for a job. Tulgan (2009) also highlighted that millennial are likely to work with organisations that allow them freedom and flexibility in how and where they can work. Hewlett *et al.* (2009) also shared a similar opinion and stated that most millennials prefer to work in an office environment, however, they prefer to have an option to work from home once a week

or when needed. Tulgan (2009) highlighted that other generation often misunderstands millennials and considered them to be lazy. This is because they do not often see them working from 8-5 in the office environment.

However, Tulgan (2009) supported millennials by suggesting that they tend to be more productive when working from home. As they appreciate organisation allowing them flexibility, they put in extra effort to complete the work as an appreciation. Tulgan (2009) further recommends that leaders/managers will have to alter their mindset on how they see “work time” to retain millennials. Tulgan (2009) further suggested that leaders need to allow millennials the flexibility to set their schedules. However, it is not unreasonable to ask where they will be working from and to ensure that the quality of their performance is not declining when millennials are offsite.

Numerous research indicated that millennials are one of the most prominent generations than the Baby Boomer. (Tulgan, 2009). Despite misunderstanding their work ethic and poor manners, millennials are recognised as one of the most talented and well-educated generations. Erickson (2008) stated that millennials are developing and progressing to become the next generation leader. Tulgan (2009) suggested that managers/leaders should engage with them most effectively to retain them.

Burkus (2010, p.5) further stated that:

By providing Millennials with meaningful and growing experiences, respecting their contribution, utilizing mentoring, giving feedback, and staying flexible, leaders can retain millennials as followers who will develop into future leaders.

Casper and Harris (2008) pointed out a significant link between high employee engagement and flexible HRM. This is because employees, when given incomplete information, such as the organisation’s intention etc., tend to use cues to conclude. For example, an organisation giving employees access to flexible HRM will be perceived positively, as it will signal its intention. On the other hand, employees will perceive it as organisation concerns about them (Takeuchi *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, flexible HRM allows the organisation to balance their personal lives and the demand for their job. When employees are given freedom and autonomy in how they work, they are likely to be more satisfied, ultimately resulting in a high engagement at the workplace (Crawford *et al.*, 2010).

Conservation of resource theory (Hobfoll, 1989) also explains the effectiveness of flexible HRM. Conservation of resource theory pointed out that employee's concern significantly about protecting and accessing new resources (Halbesleben *et al.*, 2014). Access to resources is considered a major factor of motivation, and when employees are provided with resources, they are likely to invest more to gain more resources. Flexible HRM acts as a gain in employees' resources and counteracts potential stress for employees when balancing work and personal obligations. Thus, encouraging employees to invest more energy and time in the workplace.

Flexible HRM can be used for any generation; however, it may play a significant role in maintaining a relationship with the millennial's generation at the workplace. Generation Y (millennials) are considered as having completely different values, perceptions, and expectations from the workplace than any other generation before. As mentioned before, they are considered a generation with high self-esteem and are often recognised as a generation that tends to be more "narcissistic". They prefer to have flexibility and autonomy at the workplace.

According to Lyons and Kuron (2014), events such as 9/11, recent wars, and seeing parents working for long hours have completely changed millennials' mentality about work. They have re-evaluated their life priorities and prefer to balance their work and personal life, this results in urging needs to have flexibility at the workplace. Millennials are aware that not many organisations provide this opportunity. Therefore, when any organisation does give them access to work flexibly, they tend to value more and feel more emotionally attached to the organisation, thus resulting in high satisfaction and high engagement. Davidson *et al.* (2010) also shared similar opinions. They reaffirmed organisations to have more flexibility at their workplace by stating that when younger generations are provided with more resources, i.e., more freedom, on how they work, they tend to be more proactive motivated and engaged.

2.30 Retention

SHRM (2021) defined retention as:

Managing employee retention involves strategic actions to keep employees motivated and focused, so they elect to remain employed and fully productive for the benefit of the organization. contribute to an organization's productivity and overall business performance.

According to Adkins and Ragoni (2016), personal development is more important for millennials than free food or ping pong etc. A survey was done by Stewart *et al.* (2017) on millennials showed no positive relationship between work environment and Organisational commitment. However, a few years back, PwC (2011) research suggested a positive relationship between organisation work environment and retention. They highlighted in their research that organisations that effectively engage with the employees and create a comfortable environment tend to have a higher retention rate than those that do not.

PwC (2011) research also indicated that millennials are attracted to work in those organisations that brand themselves as having extrinsic motivations. Their research significantly highlighted that millennial highly valued those organisations that offer training and development opportunities alongside flexible working hours. Adkins and Rigoni's (2016) and Stewart *et al.*'s (2017) research is more recent; thus, their work will be considered more valid. With time, millennials have advanced more towards career progression opportunities and other diversionary tactics at the workplace than “bells and whistle” (Comaford, 2016).

2.31 Performance Management

According to CIPD (2020):

Performance management is the activity and set of processes that aim to maintain and improve employee performance in line with an organisation's objectives. It is strategic and operational, as it aims to ensure that employees contribute positively to business objectives. Ideally, performance should be managed holistically throughout the range of HR activities and processes.

Garrad and Chamorro-Premuzic (2016) pointed out in one of their articles in Harvard Business Review that employee engagement greatly influences the performance and retention of an organisation. However, highly engaged employees will not always result in organisations delivering the expected performance level. Garrad and Chamorro-Premuzic (2016) in their article tried to reinforce that there are other factors than employee engagement which can affect organisation performance. Organisation, which solely focuses on having a high level of employee engagement, such as connecting employees, will not succeed. With highly engaged employees, organisations should have effective management performance in place. Managers need to create a balance between employee engagement and management performance. This is because

motivation means nothing when an organisation's vision and objectives are not set and monitored.

Furthermore, fun, and challenging tasks are essential to retaining the millennials generation of the workforce. Millennials are less preferably to an organisation that resists healthy competition, causing them to feel bored and eventually leave the workplace. In one of the articles, Elliot (2016) also stated that the UK productivity level had dropped significantly in the past few decades. A high gap can be seen in productivity between the UK and other economies. This gap was identified due to the UK's inability to create quality jobs for their employees and manage their economic outcomes. Thus, this shows that an organization with a clear vision and highly engaged employees will only be beneficial if managers monitor and manage their employee performance. Therefore, managers should put effective management performance in place.

2.32 Performance Management and Millennials

As mentioned by many authors, communication with millennials is vital to retain them (Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010; Simmons, 2015). Millennials were raised with real-life talk. From childhood, their parents and friends advised them in their personal lives and encouraged them to share their opinions. They expect the same in their professional lives. Frequent communication motivates millennials as it keeps them aware of current issues, changes, success, or even failure. Hassel (2018), CEO and Founder of 15 Five, pointed out that only 15% of millennials were happy with their organisation communication. He also pointed out that 81% of millennials preferred to work in an organisation with open communication (Hassel, 2018).

Furthermore, traditional means of communication, that is, face-to-face communication, is another reason for communication failure as millennials consider it outdated. Therefore, to incorporate modern performance management into the system, managers have started to use different business instant messaging services like slack etc., to permit instant feedback within the organisations.

Clarke (2018) also pointed out in one of her articles that Wendy Hamilton, CEO at TechSmith, comments:

Social platforms like Facebook and Instagram, which rely heavily on visual content for engagement, are the go-to way of connecting outside of work

because this is how people prefer to communicate. Not only that, using images, screencasts and videos in workplace communications makes it easier to get a message across clearly and concisely. With millennials making up the largest generation in the workforce and Generation Z now moving through organisations too, its time leaders sat up and adapted to their new, image-hungry audiences.

2.33 Feedbacks

According to Erickson (2008), Millennials crave foreknowledge and seek guidance from their managers or leaders. Tulgan (2009) highlighted that millennial are one of the most supervised generations. They were raised in an exceedingly organised manner and experienced child-centric nurturing. According to Tulan (2009), as a child, millennials generations were involved in many activities before and after school, as proficiency in these activities and school will allow them to enrol in a good university, ultimately earning them a successful career. As a result, millennials are used to receiving feedback regularly on how they are performing, where their qualities lie and where they require to improve. Within the work environment, they look for this same criticism, particularly positive feedback. Tulgan (2009) also highlighted that leader are looking to attract and retain talented millennials would have to alter their strategies on how regularly they should convey criticism or feedback. Alsop (2008) also shared similar opinions and suggested that frequent feedback will help millennials to remain engaged in their job and discourage them from looking to other organisations to fill this need.

Millennials are motivated by feedbacks. Buckeley *et al.* (2016) pointed out that millennials grew up with constant feedback on their school performance. They are used to instant feedback given to them throughout the semester at school through a single click online, instead of waiting weeks to get a report card to see their progress through their grade. As a result of which, millennials expect the same from their managers at the workplace. They expect their managers to give constant digital feedback to them instead of one yearly appraisal. Continuous feedback also helps the manager in building effective communication with millennials.

Continuous performance management allows managers to keep in line with their employees and allows the frequent exchange of ideas and information. Furthermore, continuous communication in the form of feedback enables managers to understand their employees better and recognise different means of reward and recognition

accustomed to each of their employees. Managers can also measure and address behavioural issues, such as signs of depression or workload, which will help manage them effectively.

General Electronic introduced numeric appraisal for their employees and were very successful in doing so for several years. However, recently, due to an increase in millennials, they realised this method is no longer appealing and decided to adopt a faster, frequent mobile-enabled feedback. Hernandez (2015) pointed out that 40% of millennials want more specific feedback, 32% want more open dialogue during the review, and 31% want feedback to feel less biased. According to Willyerd (2015), a survey was conducted on 1400 millennials by Success Factor in 2014, and their research indicated that more than 50% of millennials expect more frequent feedbacks than other generation employees.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at the Harvard Business Review.

Figure 3:

Harvard Business Review (2015)

2.34 Development Opportunities

In one of their articles, the Access Group (2021) highlighted that skill gap performance management analysis is no longer enough. The millennials generation expect modernised and strength-based performance management. They want their managers to not only identify areas where they need improvement but also their talent area. They simply do not want to learn and develop new skills but also want to develop the existing skills that might assist them in future. When millennials see their measurable impact on

the organisation's success, they are likely to feel motivated. Line supervisors can do this by setting objectives for millennials connected to business results, continuously inspecting, and revising these objectives as business technique changes and giving input to every representative about how they are getting along in accomplishing these results. Deloitte (2015) millennials survey also indicates that 53% of millennials want career progression and are ambitious about becoming leaders in their organisation.

2.35 Flexible HRM

Flexibility HRM effect was also seen on management performance. When given access to flexible HRM, employees, such as millennials, are likely to reciprocate high engagement, thus, ultimately resulting in improving job performance. When employees are given flexibility in their work-personal life, they are likely to be highly motivated, resulting in them being more proactive at the workplace. Even though they may not use it, it will act as a signal of motivation to access it whenever they need it. Flexible HRM also benefits the organisation in improving older generation performance. Throughout life, individuals are faced with gains and losses in physical and mental capabilities.

According to Lyon and Kuron (2014, p. 13), “To minimise losses in outcomes due to the age-related losses in abilities people experience, they select fewer goals so that they do not have to spread their diminished resources over too many goals and can thus remain productive contributors in the organization.” Flexible HRM for the older generation will counteract age-related problems, improving performance and allowing an organisation to manage their performance effectively. This shows that flexible HRM is significantly important for the older generation to maintain their functioning level. Thus, it is recommended by many authors (Allen *et al.*, 2013; De Menezes and Kelliher, 2011), as it is expected that the availability of flexible HRM will guide a leader to high engagement and effective job performance.

Small or Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)

Globally, a rise in the SME's has been seen significantly, especially in the economy of Great Britain. They are considered paramount to the wellbeing of the UK economy. According to Rhodes (2017), the UK economy consists of 5.7 million businesses, and 99% of the organisation are SME's. Furthermore, Liam Fox, The Secretary of State for

International Trade, stated his opinion on SMEs in one of the article by UK Export Finance *et al.* (2017) by saying that:

Small businesses are the backbone of our economy and giving them the support, they need to seize international trading opportunities is a prioritythat's why we're partnering with the five major high street banks to make government-backed finance from UK Export Finance readily available in a matter of seconds, opening new global contracts to businesses across the UK.

FSB (2017) also shared a similar opinion and pointed out that SMEs contributed significantly in 2017. SMEs in UK combined turnover was noted to be £1.9 trillion in 2017. This shows that SMEs are contributing significantly to the UK economy. The continuous support provided by the UK government will result in more SMEs forming and rising in the next few years. Hampshire Trust Bank (2017) also forecasted in one of their articles that SMEs are expected to grow significantly by 2025 in the UK and are expected to contribute £241 billion (DSTL, 2020). As mentioned earlier in the thesis, SMEs are facing difficulty in retaining millennials within the organization. As SME's are increasing dramatically in the UK economy, they need to consider millennials. Millennials are an increasingly active part of organisations, and to ensure further success is achieved and sustained, employers need to develop effective employee engagement and management performance strategy.

Considering the increasingly important role that millennials play in modern organizations, it is necessary for small and medium companies to focus on their strategies in order to retain millennials in their organisations effectively. According to Krona & Virbert-Kronqvist (2019), employees play a vital role in the organisation for monitoring the business systematically in the market. SMEs are required to improve their strategy so that the employees find interest to stay in the company for a sustainable period. Organisational culture must be developed so that the people can find the motivation to work there flexibly and comfortably. On the other hand, work-life balance is very important to maintain the job satisfaction of the employees (Tirta & Enrika, 2020). Small and medium-sized companies have to be very concerned about the employees' mental and physical health. They need to introduce proper rewards, recognition, and work-life balance to improve the job satisfaction of the employees along with the employees' retention level. However, in many cases, smaller employers do not pay as much attention on employee welfare concerns as larger employers (Penning, 2016). Due to the poor employee welfare strategies of many SMEs, the

companies face difficulties in retaining the employees and thereby the employees' retention level is highly affected.

2.36 E-Commerce Retailers

E-commerce is the process of the supply of good and service through the Internet (Moid and Dixit, 2018). According to Sabanolgu (2020), the most advanced e-commerce market in Europe is in the United Kingdom. In 2019, online sale solely in the retail market was constituted to be 19.5 % of all retails and was expected to grow even higher level due to the impact of COVID-19 pandemic issue worldwide (Dangleish, 2021). Sabanolgu (2020) further highlighted that online shopping is becoming more enriched, and more people are going online for shopping after the current global crisis. In 2020, it was noted that around 87% of household made their purchase online (Statista, 2020). This was the highest penetration country the UK has reached in its 11 years and is expected to grow more. Statistica (2020) forecasted online shopping to grow by 34.5 % in 2023. Therefore, this research is conducted on e-retailers SMEs as e-retailers are increasingly growing, especially after the pandemic. Thus, further signifying the need to conduct the study in the UK economy's e-retail sector (SME's).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework below shows the direction of the current study and brings into light the interconnection between employees' satisfaction, commitment, and performance. This conceptual framework was then used to explore the current UK economy of SME's considering the millennial retention and how the difference in their outlook is influencing and impacting the need for adjustment within the organisations.

Figure 4: Conceptual Framework

A different set of generational employees are dramatically changing the workplace. Much research has been done on millennial and how to manage and retain them in various sectors like hospitality, university etc. (Turner and Thompson, 2014; Stephens, 2020). However, little or no research has been done on managing them in SME's (e-retail industry) in UK, where time and resources are limited compared to large organisations. In addition to that, this research will consider the dramatically increasing demand of online retailers and the global pandemic situation's impact on the current UK economy.

To understand employee engagement, different integration of dimensions including leadership, learning & development, recruitment, pay, rewards & motivation, and organisational citizenship behavior are closely observed and analysed to examine how these dimensions have a direct or indirect association with employee engagement. In

addition to that, employee engagement impact on organisation performance and employee retention, especially on millennials, is examined and analysed.

The result lead by the investigation of these integrated dimensions will significantly add knowledge to the literature. It will assist organisations in understanding and formulating employee engagement strategies that will allow them to improve their organisation's performance and retention. Limited dimensions of HR and working environment were considered in the integration and analysis of this research due to the certain limitations faced (can be seen in detail in Chapter 5). However, the dimensions chosen/considered in this study had the most significant influence and impact on millennial retention.

2.5 Summary

Millennials are becoming crucial for an organisation's future success. They are becoming an active part of the organisation, and by 2020, they are expected to become more than 50% of the global workforce (PwC, 2011). It is also evident that SMEs are increasing significantly in the UK (United Kingdom) economy. The E-retail sector has also grown significantly, especially after the global pandemic issues faced worldwide.

The increase in the millennial generation and online shopping, especially in current market conditions, urges managers worldwide to dramatically change their strategies to meet consumers' and workers' changing attitudes and lifestyles. With an increased millennial turnover rate, it has become critically important for managers to carefully understand and develop their employee engagement and management performance strategies. This is especially important for SME's managers as hiring a new employee can be costly and time-consuming. Especially in the current pandemic, managers worldwide must re-consider their current strategies to meet the changing demand and need of a dramatically changing environment. Different HR (Human Resources) and working environments have been studied, integrated, and examined to better understand the implication of employee engagement and management performance on millennials.

Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

As seen in the previous chapter, the research aims to understand the impact of the millennial generation at the workplace and how effective/ineffective management is in retaining them by effectively engaging and managing their performance. As a result, this chapter will focus on describing the method used in this study by justifying the appropriateness of these methods over others.

According to Opoku *et al.* (2016), choosing an appropriate research methodology is one of the most confusing and complicated decisions for a researcher. The most suitable research methodologies are usually dictated by the type of research being undertaken and the type of data collection method being adopted. Researchers need to adopt techniques and tools which will provide them with relatively adequate information to accomplish their research aim and objective. Chapter 3 will build on the discussion formed in the last two chapters (Chapter 1 and Chapter 2).

In this chapter, the theoretical foundation will inform different research design and approach practices and how critical they are in aligning the methodology view adopted in the research. This chapter will also highlight the research philosophy and research approach underpin in this study. The research methodology will further indicate the research processes, which will be undertaken to collect the data for this research, including from sampling method and data analysis tool adopted. Lastly, ethical consideration will be discussed, indicating that study will be conducted and represented ethically.

3.2 Philosophical Approach to the Study

According to Saunders *et al.*, (2009), research philosophy refers to the assumptions and beliefs on how research should be gathered, developed, and analysed. It helps in answering specific questions on the ways of conducting the research. The qualitative approach is suitable for the purposes of this research because it provides a basis for nuanced inquiry that provides an extensive understanding of the phenomenon being studied. Furthermore, despite the absence of numerical data, qualitative research has

the capability to respond to human instinct that is necessary for understanding a phenomenon like employee engagement. The aspects of different thoughts and its implication on the activities of the millennial can be better understood. This method enables the research to assume the employment behaviour of the millennial through this philosophy.

Every researcher forms some assumptions throughout their research, whether consciously aware of it or not, which guides them to develop/adopt certain approaches to their research (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). Grix (2004) also shared a similar opinion and highlighted that every research reflects a certain philosophy, whether they are clearly recognized or not. According to Saunders *et al.* (2009, p.124), “these include assumptions about human knowledge (epistemological assumption), about the realities you encounter in your research (ontological assumption) and the extent and the way your own values influences your research progress (axiological assumptions)”.

All these assumptions highlighted by Saunders *et al.* (2009) allows individuals to shape their research and better understand their research questions. He further pointed out that consistent research philosophy will allow researchers to underpin their methodology, data collection technique and data analysis much more effectively, ultimately assisting them to fit all element together throughout the research. Johnson and Clark (2006) further highlighted the importance of research philosophy by stating that research philosophy commitment is critical. It will significantly impact individuals' understanding, such as what they do and how they understand the area they are investigating.

According to Kivunja and Kuyini (2017), the research paradigm refers to how researchers view the world and interpret and act on it. Every researcher constitutes certain beliefs and assumptions. Research paradigm and philosophy act as a conceptual lens, allowing the researcher to examine research methodology and determine research methods and data analysis techniques. Denzin and Lincoln (2000), often recognised as the guru of qualitative research, stated paradigm as a source of human construction. The research paradigm indicates researcher ideas and perspective and how they embed in the construction of meaningful data. Therefore, making paradigm as important. Fraser and Robinson (2004) also depicted paradigm as a set of individual beliefs, which guides

them to present certain problems or situations and assist them in complying with those situations when examined.

In addition, Kivunja and Kuyini (2017) highlighted that the research paradigm dictates and disciplines researchers on how they should conduct research and analyse the data gathered for their research. They re-enforced the research paradigm and philosophical significance by indicating its implication on every stage of research, such as through means of how a researcher should gather and analyse data based on an individual's experience. Therefore, making our research study data collection selection to be influenced by the paradigm chosen. These assumptions or beliefs will allow us to form notions about knowledge and construct meaningful data.

Who are millennials? Why are organisations finding it difficult to retain them? These are the ontology of this research, which focuses on the nature of reality and individual personality. As shown in chapter 2, the millennial generation was recognised as different from the other generation. This was due to their different outlook and attitude toward their life and even at work. They were seen to be redefining workplaces by some authors like Karsh and Templin (2013) and were recognised as a technology-driven generation (Greenberg and Weber, 2008).

SHRM (2016) also indicated through the mean of their surveys that workplaces have become much more complex than ever before as differences in generations, attitude, and outlooks especially after COVID-19, is forcing management to re-consider their strategies at work. However, as highlighted in Chapter 2, small to medium enterprises were growing rapidly, especially in the UK economy after global pandemic (Rhodes, 2017). Therefore, as per the perspective of ontology, relative reality exists in millennials and their impact on organisation success in the future in a large business sector.

In addition to that, considering the purpose of study, which aims to study and gain insight into the current employee engagement and performance management strategy employed by SME's and how successful/unsuccessful they are in retaining millennial. Therefore, it was realised that in detail collection of data is necessary to provide a holistic overview. Thus, to achieve the purpose of our research, it was identified that a holistic approach is needed and necessary to gain a better understanding of individuals working in SMEs, both management and employees. It is important to allow both

management and employees to give in-depth information regarding their experience at work in their own words and perspective. Hence, making constructivist paradigm to be considered most appropriate for our research.

3.3 Methodology

Crotty (1998) used epistemology as the base to distinguish between different grounding frameworks of research. Crotty (1998) highlighted that researcher should first form epistemology for their research as it provides the foundation to the research. Once epistemology is decided, a researcher can build a theoretical perspective based on their research area. Later, they can select their methodology and method for their research. Crotty (1998) tried to highlight the significance of each element and how crucially connected they are, as one element form the base for the next.

Epistemology concerns in providing the ground to the researcher with the knowledge possibility and its adequacy (Maynard, 1994). Guba and Lincoln (1998, p.201) simplified the term understanding by stating that “*epistemology is about the nature of the relationship between the knower or the would-be-knower and what can be known.*” According to Crotty (1998), epistemology is the philosophy of knowledge underlying the research, such as objectivism, subjectivism, or constructivism. Once the philosophical position is formed, a theoretical perspective can be built to provide context to the research. Theoretical perspectives are positivism, feminism and interpretivism.

Once a theoretical perspective has been built, the researcher can select methodology to plan the overall action strategy for their research, such as survey questions, ethnography, etc. After methodology, the researcher can choose the actual method for their research, including questionnaires, interviews, etc. By using this scheme by Crotty (1998), a researcher can conceptualise the foundation for their research and understand how they can underpin consistency within different layers of their research. Higgs (2001) research paradigm is similar to Crotty's (1998) scheme but slightly different. Higgs (2001) paradigm consists of three distinguished cores: empirico-analytical, interpretive, and critical. This paradigm assists researcher in identifying what knowledge can be used and how that knowledge can be generated validly. Higgs' (2001) research paradigm also reinstates the importance of each core and how

significantly connected they are in building upon each other. Both Crotty's (1998) and Higgs' (2001) scheme of philosophical and theoretical perspective are equivalent to Gadamer's pre-understanding.

Higgs' (2001) philosophical stance is equivalent to Crotty (1998) concept of epistemology and theoretical perspective. The research paradigm is the first factor discussed above. Empirico-analytical paradigm is based on the positivism philosophy of theoretical perspective and objectivist epistemology. This paradigm believes that meaningful reality exists globally and can be discovered through the mean of consciousness. This approach is deductive and has dominated as a successful mean of research. However, with time, this approach was recognised as inadequate when understanding the live experience, such as in this underlying thesis research where the aim is to explore millennial and management expectations.

Empirico- analytical paradigm is useful when the research object is known, and the researcher's goal is to discover the meaning surrounding that objective. However, when researchers aim to study the constantly changing sense of the world and human actions, this paradigm appears to have serious problems. This is because, human actions when studied either in-group or individually, can inhibit different meaning when looking in different circumstances. This completely contradicts the idea of the empirico-analytical paradigm, which believes that fixed meaning can be achieved regardless of time and place. This highlights the limitation of the empirico-analytical paradigm and how inadequate it can be when studying human actions and interpretation. The research goal and approach in Higgs (2001) scheme is also equivalent to Crotty's research methodology. Considering these constructs, the selection of methods and the structure those methods will take can be believed to have a coherent basis consistent with the basic epistemology or paradigm.

Again, this can assist with guaranteeing thoroughness in the research.

This study will be conducted using an interpretative paradigm. This is because, according to Higgs (2001, p49) aim of the interpretive paradigm:

is to seek to interpret the world, particularly the social world, (and where) knowledge ... comprises constructions arising from the minds... generated through a search for meaning, beliefs, and values, and through looking for wholes and relationships with other wholes.

The current study aimed to explore the context and live experience of the individual, such as through the conscious feelings of both employees and management, thus making interpretative paradigm the most appropriate method for addressing the research questions of this study. Furthermore, this paradigm considers the human world and allows the researcher to explore and address the study richly and in a deeper context, unlike the empirico-analytical paradigm.

3.4 Epistemology- Constructivism as Research Paradigm

Ontological and Epistemological assumption was initially examined by considering the nature of social science to study whether they fall into subjectivist and objectivist. It was discovered that it is hard to separate these two assumptions: the ontological and epistemology approach. By looking at the research questions of this study, it was realised that it falls toward the subjectivist approach as it aims to understand the reality, context and life experience of individuals through the mean of comprehensive insight. However, at the same time, it was realised that the objectivist approach could not be entirely ignored for our research. This consequently results in the positivism paradigm concept being rejected because its ontological is based on the assumption that objective reality exists (Dyson and Brown, 2005). Crotty (1998) proposed a solution to this dilemma by putting forward the constructionist approach, which considers both ontological and epistemology conceptual issues. According to O'Brien (2001), constructivism epistemology is rooted in interpretivism.

According to Burrell and Morgan (1979), the subjectivist view solely focuses on the consciousness residing within the individual. The objectivist view focuses solely on the reality that exists outside the consciousness of an individual. On the other hand, the constructivist approach proposed by Crotty (1998) focuses on the construction of the reality of nature rather than solely focusing on being subjective or objective. Constructionist only emerge when individual interact with the object of the world (Crotty, 1998). In general, this approach is the fusion of subjective and objective mind. The constructivism approach is where subjective and objective information, when used solely, is considered meaningless.

Crotty (1998, P.45) further re-enforced this by stating that:

Because of this essential relationship that human experience bears to its object, no object can be adequately described in isolation from the conscious being

experiencing it, nor can experience be adequately described in isolation from its object.

On the contrary to this point of view, authors like Halcomb and Andrew (2005) and Weaver and Olsen (2006), who support the positivism paradigm, believe that meaningful reality exists and is predetermined that can be easily measured. However, considering the research context of the study, it is clear that the current research aim is not to measure any existing measuring or predetermined outcomes but rather to study individual experience, which cannot be measured or analysed through statistical means or figures. Therefore, again rejecting the positivism paradigm for our research and proceeding constructivist perspective. This is because the constructivist perspective is where individual construct meaning considering the refinement objective of the research and mindful consciousness of the individual.

Guba (1990) further pointed out three bases of the constructivism approach. Firstly, reality only exists in the individual context of the construction of a mental framework for thinking about it. Secondly, there is no one reality or perspective in the construction of meaning. Crotty (1998) further agrees with Guba (1990) point of view and stated that different individuals could construct different meanings from one reality, concluding that human interpretation can neither be considered valid.

According to Guba (1990), data construction does not necessarily mean the researcher seeks a single truth but identifies one reflection of the meaning. Thirdly, the value inherent in individual concern can significantly drive in certain perspective to be formed. Finally, constructionist allows the researcher to unveil different realities and study and see how they relate. This further does not comply with our research aim as the positivism paradigm believes in single truth or reality of the objective and believes in common truth and explanation (Dyson and Brown, 2005). Healy and Perry (2005) also further highlighted that the positivism paradigm examines the world through one-way mirrors and examines reality through single reality. Ontologically looking, this is irrelevant to the current study as individuals experience may vary from each other and multiple reality may exist. Guba and Lincoln (1989) three bases of constructivism go parallel with our research. We aim to base assumptions on reality and how we interpret it according to our understanding by grounding millennials as the main factor for constructivism. This signifies that interaction is necessary to better understand millennials' insight and expectation. Interacting with both management and employees

will allow us to gain better insight into their views on their behaviour and experience. This further underpins the ontology and epistemology of this research to be relevant with constructivism which believes in the interaction between the researcher and the individuals involved in the study.

In other words, the study seeks to explore the relationship between management and employees in terms of how effective/ineffective they are in retaining them. Successful managers are currently tackling the impact of COVID-19 restrictions on organisation and as well as tackling millennial retention issue within the organisation. Nevertheless, both management and employees will have varying experience or opinions as everyone may perceive things differently in the way they are possibly influenced by, as Crotty (1989) highlighted. Therefore, it is expected to have a dissimilar view in the current research regarding how every individual may perceive things.

Theoretical Assumptions	Positivism	Constructivism
Ontology	Believes in researcher to be independent of the research being conducted and consider the researcher and reality to be apart.	Believes in researcher and reality to be connected from each other.
Epistemology	Believes in the existence of objective reality and analysis and consider meaning to have a single reality.	Believes in the interpretation of the world through the understanding of the individual experience and believes multi-reality exists.
Method	Uses structures method to explore single and objective reality. Methods usually adopted in this paradigm are	Use multiple methods to construct and interpret multiple realities. Methods usually adopted in this

	questionnaires, surveys, and mathematical graphs etc.	paradigm are interviews, ethnography etc.
Goal	The research aims to achieve objective or generalised data, such as in numeric values.	The research aims to explore data through exploring and interpreting an individual's life experience and perspective.

Table 1: Comparison of Positivism and Constructivism (Interpretivism) by Creswell (2007)

3.5 Research Approach

3.5.1 Qualitative and Quantitative Research

The term “research method” is very broad. A research method is a strategy of analysis that allows researchers to discover answers to known and rediscover the unknown into research design by applying the scientific procedure. Choosing an effective research method is critical to implement a research plan and to ensure fundamental results are obtained. According to Sahu and Singh (2016), even though every research has its objective and purpose, but they are categorised into one of the four broad objectives:

Research methods taken here are very broad which makes it

3.5.1.1 Exploratory Research

Research being carried out to gain familiarity on certain areas or to gain insight into unexplored phenomena.

3.5.1.2 Descriptive Research

This research is carried out to describe event, individuals, or situation. Therefore, this type of research is usually based on events or situation that has already been happened.

3.5.1.3 Diagnostic Research

This research is carried out when the researcher aims to study the pattern of events or frequency of certain associated studies with another event.

3.5.1.4 Hypothesis Testing Research

This type of research is conducted to study causal relationships between certain variables (dependent and independent variables).

The current research aims to understand the issues SME's face in retaining millennials generation and gain insight on the current employee engagement and management performance strategy employ by them in COVID-19; therefore, this study objective falls more into exploratory research. According to Kothari (2004), although various types of research, including applied research, empirical research etc., quantitative, and qualitative research are the basic approaches to any research. Therefore, the researcher needs to select an appropriate research approach depending on their research questions and objective. Considering the nature of study, qualitative research was the most suited research approach. However, before justifying the choice of a certain research approach, both quantitative and qualitative research approach will be briefly discussed.

According to Labaree (2009), a quantitative method was developed to systematically and statistically examine social phenomena to develop, gain and refine natural sciences. Quantitative data was initially developed to mathematically study and investigate natural incidental (Bhattacharjee, 2012). In contrast, the qualitative research approach was originally designed to understand the social experience, such as how they are created and given meaning (Labaree, 2009). The qualitative research method was early developed by the researcher in the Western world who would travel to explore different cultures and people etc. They would put together their experience and compare the common pattern (Bhattacharya, 2012). Both methods are recognised to be effective; however, with time, qualitative research gained significant interest. However, according to Hall and Howard (2008), none of the methods was superior to others. It all depends on the nature of the research and its objective (Creswell, 2002; Kothari, 2004).

Consequently, it is very important for any study to employ the right methodology to understand the relying issue researched. Bhawuk and Tirandis (1996) pointed out that

the researcher should consider factors like whether the area has already been studied, whether existing knowledge is accessible, and the extent to which previous research is accepted for using a specific research method. Many researchers widely adopt the mixed method. Mixed method research is used when using one research approach is not enough to explore diverse perspectives and to reveal relationships between multi-faceted research (Shorten and Smith, 2017). As the current research aims to explore the in-depth understanding of the current study field and not measure any existing social phenomena, this method is not appropriate for the study.

Qualitative study is widely used to study the day-to-day context of society. Bhattacharya (2012) considered qualitative research to be valuable when recording social and cultural trend. Merriam (2009) defined the qualitative approach as naturalistic and interpretive. Both deductive and inductive approaches are included in qualitative research, which offers a more holistic view of the study and simplifies relationships between responses by categorizing them (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Grbich (2012) underpins one of the qualitative research characteristics by stating that research must hold subjective value. Both researcher and the subject who are being studied opinion should be respected and acknowledged.

Generally, the qualitative method primary objective is to gain an accurate and multiple understanding of the subject being studied. Therefore, it is very important to choose an approach and tools to interact with the study to gain in-depth insight into it. For instance, in the present study, multiple realities will come up, such as management's perspective, the perspective of a different set of employees, and the researcher's perspective. Therefore, qualitative research asserts in gaining better understanding by the individuals being studied from their perspective.

Domegan and Flaming (2007) further pointed out that qualitative data seeks to explore unanswered question or knowledge or problem, which has not been studied in depth. Myers (2009) also shared a similar opinion and stated that qualitative research assists researchers in seeking answers by understanding individuals through their experience and perspective. It allows the researcher to explore and analyse complexities in the context of the study. The difference between quantitative and qualitative research has been highlighted by many authors (Bryman, 1988: Easter by Smith *et al.*, 2009). However, three distinct differences were recognised to be (Saunders *et al.* 2009):

- Quantitative data is based on numeric values, whereas qualitative data is derived through expression in words.
- The data collection method is standardised in quantitative data. In contrast, for qualitative data, a non-standardised process is adopted where the response is categorised to understand in-depth and multiple realities, such as individual experience (Aliaga and Gunderson, 2002).
- Quantitative data is usually analysed through statistics and graphs, whereas qualitative data is generally analysed through conceptualisation. Quantitative data is usually collected through surveys, questionnaires etc. and then turned into numeric value to be analysed later (Hope and Waterman, 2003). Qualitative data are collected through interviews, observation, etc., and then analysed by setting objective and themes.

Dey (1993) further pointed out that the more ambiguous and elastic the concept becomes, the more it becomes difficult to use numbers to derive meaning. Qualitative research allows the researcher to explore concept richness and fullness, making the outcome more realistic. Creswell (2014) also shared a similar opinion and stated that qualitative data effectively explores individuals in their original settings. According to Creswell (2014, p.4), *“those who engage in this form of inquiry support a way of looking at research that honours an inductive style, a focus on individual meaning, and the importance of rendering the complexity of the situation”*. Gibbs (2007) further stated that qualitative research takes the context under study very seriously. Research is mainly based on texting and writing study notes and then transcript research into presentable finding.

Characteristic	Quantitative	Qualitative
Research framework	The aim is to test the existing hypothesis.	The aim is to explore different realities and phenomena
Reality	Believes in a single reality	Believes in multiple realities

Study-setting	Research is conducted in an artificial context.	Research is conducted in the live/natural setting of the context being studied.
Format of Data	Numerical and statistical data	Descriptive words and texts.
Data Method Collection	Questionnaires, surveys etc.	Interviews, ethnography etc.
Aim	Generalising data to envisage causal relationship, depicting generalisation through means of the feature of populations etc.	Generalising data to understand the individual life experience.
Relationship with the study	The researcher is independent of the study being conducted and shares no relationship.	Research is connected to the study being conducted.

Table 2: Comparison of Qualitative and Quantitative data by Creswell (2013)

3.5.2 Selection of Qualitative Data Research Approach and its Justification

From the prior section of this chapter, it is clear that the current study is exploratory research. To explore and understand the study effectively, the researcher must adopt an appropriate research approach to comprehend an individual's experience, feelings, and opinions. Guba (1981) also highlighted the importance of choosing appropriate research methods by stating that they must employ a proper paradigm to gain effective results, which fits well with the subject/area investigated. Considering the exploration study process, qualitative research was considered well suited than quantitative method (Patton, 2002). In addition to that, the nature of this study is to explore the social world rather than the scientific world, ultimately making qualitative research to be most suited.

According to Drew (2007) and Mehrad and Tahiri (2019), the study of social life differs from the study of scientific data. This is because the study of social life focuses on the interactions, reality and social context of the phenomena being researched over a period. Furthermore, it focuses on human beings and process and concentrates on how it evolves with time. For instance, in the current study, managers used the same strategies or made slight differences to adjust to the different workplace generations. However, due to drastic differences in outlook and demand by millennials, management finds it difficult to implement the same strategies to retain and satisfy them. This further indicates the qualitative method to be best suited considering the natural phenomena of the current study.

According to Austin and Sutton (2015), qualitative research is best suitable when researching social inquiry, especially when researchers seek to convey individuals' thoughts and feelings. For instance, in this study, the researcher aims to understand the experience and feeling of both management and a different set of employees, especially millennials. The researcher also seeks to convey their needs, demands, and feelings to managers to assist them to understand the generation better and set policies that will result in trouble generation “millennial” as recognised by management to be satisfied. Merriam (2009) also stated that researchers mostly adopt qualitative research when their concern is understanding and constructing a human experience, especially in their setting. However, on the other hand, the quantitative research approach does not offer that and focuses on scientific outcomes, such as testing in the laboratory or passing out questionnaires to individuals in artificial settings.

Some authors like Patton (2002) and Leedy&Ormrod (2005) put forward some conditions for students to consider when selecting a qualitative research approach. The researcher should choose qualitative data when:

- They seek to gain insight into an individual’s experience.
- They seek to investigate human emotions and feelings about certain events or how they perceive certain situations.
- They seek to study their subject in their original settings, such as the workplace, etc.
- There is little or no information available on the phenomena being investigated.

The above view highlighted by authors (Patton, 2002 and Leedy&Omdy, 2005) parallels the current study. This research aims to explore and understand the individual experience at the workplace from management and employees' perspectives. The study investigates how satisfied current employees, such as millennials, are at the workplace and how successful management manages and retains them. In addition to that, qualitative research methods offer a wide range of techniques to the researcher that assists them to study individual's perceptions, experience, motivating factors and behaviour (Clisset 2008). It offers the researcher to study the factors that influence individuals to do or behave in a certain way (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003).

Sandin (2003) further pointed out that the qualitative research method allows the researcher to focus on individuals being studied and assist them in understanding personal and theoretical assumptions of the subject being studied and their relationship with other participants involved in the study. For instance, this current study will help in evaluating the millennial relationship with the workplace's management. This shows that opportunities will be created for the researcher to explore and understand in-depth personal views of individuals and evaluate the relationship between them by using the qualitative research method.

It was further highlighted by Mohajan (2018) that qualitative data is well suited when studying the human and social problem. Another author shared this perception like Schwandt (2007), which further highlighted and considered “understanding” as the focal point in the qualitative research approach. However, according to Evely *et al.* (2008), these factors are not considered when using a quantitative research approach. Understanding the perception and relation between managers and millennial is critical for this research as only by understanding the perception and emotions, the researcher can gain insight of any existing or arising problem which can hinder the process of millennial retention. Moreover, qualitative research is considered the most suitable for this study due to its ability to gather and analyse a large amount of text being carried out (Liamputtong, 2010 and Miller and Daly, 2013). Liamputtong (2010) further pointed out that it is challenging to represent and analyse human emotion and perception in numeric figures.

Quantitative data is undoubtedly very useful when studying fixed variables. However, this is unsuitable for this research, as the aim is to explore and gain a better insight into

the phenomena (Mcmillan and Schumacher, 2006). In addition to that, the natural setting for quantitative data is not fixed and is usually artificially created, which is further not suited for our research. Aneas and Sandin (2009) also agreed with that and stated that individual experience could not be sufficiently understood when not conducted in its original setting as individual experience only evidently occurs when defined in their social/working area.

Tavellaei and Abu-Talib (2010) further agreed with the statement by stating that the qualitative research method is only suitable when conducted in a natural setting. Hatch (2002) also further agreed and highlighted that when exploring and understanding the relationship, the researcher needs to build relationships and get involved in the subject being studied. This implies that the current study researcher should visit the location and conduct research in the subject's natural working environment. This is not possible when conducting quantitative research (Tavallaei and Abu Talib, 2010).

Butcher *et al.* (1997) stated that environmental effects significantly affect individual development, especially when evaluating personal opinion and experience. This implies research to conduct the current study by assessing the subject's current working environment. For instance, conducting interviews at busy periods, both employees and management might have different attitudes than when not busy. Appropriate means of achieving true knowledge for the subject creates room for the participant by considering their environment and then depicting their opinion on 'how', 'why' and 'what' they think. This is only possible when a qualitative research approach is adopted. For example, intensity due to busy period can create a different outcome than when it is not busy, especially in the current study on retail SME's. To ensure views are not restricted, participants will be allowed to express themselves in their own words, enabling the researcher to gain true insight into participant personality (Guenette and Marshall, 2009).

Considering all the supporting factors for qualitative research, it was recognised that it offers effective assistance when exploring answers to the current study phenomena. As identified by authors like Tewksbury (2009) and Liamputtong (2010), qualitative data offers researchers opportunities to explore in-depth and create better and deeper insight into the phenomena being studied, which is not possible when adopting a quantitative research approach. Qualitative research broadens researcher insight to better

understand the subject being studied, assuming how it is supposed to be, which goes parallel with the current study. Hence, making the qualitative research approach appropriate for the current study.

3.5.3 Ethnography

Ethnography is one of the methods of qualitative research. According to Brewer (2005, p.11), ethnography allows researcher “.....to understand the social meanings and activities of people in a given field or settings....” Ethnography requires researcher to get deeply involved with the context and individuals studied by participating in day-to-day activities and by observing them. Delamont (2006) further pointed out that ethnography is where researcher spend long hours observing individuals in their original setting to get better insight into how each individual thinks, works, and reacts to certain situations. In addition to that, the researcher continuously takes on-field notes by getting involved in day-to-day activities and interacting with the individuals being studied (Silverman, 2005).

This research method offers the researcher a holistic view of the subject being studied as it is conducted in natural settings. However, this method can be time-consuming. Ethnography was one of the chosen methods by the researcher, but later in the research, it was realised that it is not suitable considering the time and COVID-19 constraint factors. In addition, getting involved with two e-retail companies and becoming part of their day-to-day activities was difficult for researcher to gain access to. Therefore, this research method is considered not suitable for the current study.

3.5.4 Grounded Theory

Grounded theory is another method of qualitative data. It was first discovered by Glaser and Strauss in 1967 and defined as “*the discovering of theory from data systematically obtained from social research*” (Glaser and Strauss, 1967, p.2). Charmaz and Belgrave (2011) further pointed out that ground theory provides guidelines to the researcher, aiming to construct a brand-new theory by systematically analysing and conceptualizing. Research starts from scratch and has no data whatsoever. Current research mainly focuses on studying the current employee engagement and performance management strategy employee by SME’s in UK. Thus, making this research method unsuitable for the current study.

3.5.5 Action Research

According to Parkin (2009), action research is where researcher not solely aim to understand the context of the study, such as problems, etc., but also apply desired changes into practice to see its effect. In the action research method, the researcher aims to improve existing concerning problems and transform them by acting through means by gathering individuals in groups being studied and collaborating with them by generating ideas for improvement into practice. Huang (2010, p.93) also further stated by saying that “action research represents a transformative orientation to knowledge creation in that action researcher seek to take knowledge beyond the gate-keeping of professional knowledge makers.” The researcher uses the action research method to solve practical concerns by seeking immediate solutions through collaboration. This method is unsuitable for the current study. This research aim to gain insight on the millennial retention issue faced by SME’s after the global pandemic. The current study does not seek to improve any immediate problem immediately, making it inappropriate for the study.

Narrative Research Method

According to Webster and Mertova (2007), narrative research method depicts individual experience by endeavouring past or historical event. Researchers using this method construct or reconstruct a story by addressing issues like cultural or human-centered issues. Researchers gain insight into how everyone perceives life or certain things through the story they tell. Dyson and Genisigi (1994) stated that everyone has basic stories to narrate important life events and considered it a fundamental way of organizing experience. Sarbin (1986, p.8) expresses a similar notion by stating, “human beings think, perceive, imagine, and make moral choices according to narrative structures.” Webster and Mertova (2007) considered this method ineffective when researching on complex issues as this research method have less scope when dealing with complex human issues. Therefore, this method was deemed not suitable for the current study.

3.5.6 Phenomenological Research

Lester (1999) pointed out four qualitative approaches to research: ethnography, hermeneutics, symbolic interactionism, and phenomenological research. For this study,

phenomenological research of qualitative approach to research will be used. According to Lester (1999), the phenomenological method will allow the researcher to effectively explore and study the perception of the individuals to be interviewed, such as their own experience. Other methods are effective, but they require qualitative research to be based on the personal perceptions of the researcher. However, this research aim is to identify the individual perception. Identifying individual perception will allow realistic outcomes to achieve and sometimes draw attention to different situations necessary to develop effective strategies. It will also allow the researcher to avoid biasness in research (Plummer, 1983).

Phenomenological research is well known among researchers when they aim to depict meaning/answers/understanding from the living experience of individuals. Van and Manen (1990) highlighted the fundamental purpose of this method by stating that the phenomenological method focuses on analysing and depicting common factors regarding the phenomena between all respondents. This method allows the researcher to gain a deeper understanding when evaluating an individual's experience. Therefore, this method was considered suitable for our research. Phenomenological methods allow the researcher to construct an open-end inquiry through direct response between the researcher and the subject being studied (Maxwell, 2013). Miles *et al.* (2014) further highlighted that the phenomenological research method assists the researcher in exploring the more profound experience of individuals by emerging certain themes or pattern.

There are three types of approaches in phenomenological research:

Phenomenological approach	Description
Lifeworld research	Explore the day-to-day experience of individuals life world through means of selfhood etc.
Post-intentional phenomenology	Consider phenomenon as a unit of analysis and consider phenomena to be multiple in existence and context, such as probably on

	the context of being produced or on the verge of being produced.
Interpretive Phenomenological analysis	It aims to provide a deeper understanding of phenomena being studied by examining an individual's life experience.

Table 3: Description of approaches in the phenomenological method.

Adapted by Neubauer *et al.* (2019)

Interpretive Phenomenological approach is chosen for this study as the current study aims to better understand individuals, such as both employees and management. Furthermore, this is the only approach, which allows the researcher to play an active role in the interpretive process.

3.5.6.1 Justification for Choosing Phenomenological Research Method

This section will highlight the rationale for choosing the phenomenological research method for the current study. According to Hall (2008), it is difficult to analyse which method is better or most effective, depending on the phenomena being studied or certain situations. Silverman (2005) also shared a similar opinion and stated that the research method significantly depends on the aim, objective, and questions of the research. The purpose of the current study is to gain better insight into millennials retention issue faced by SME's and to understand the current employee engagement and management performance strategy employ by them. Phenomenological research was recognised to be suitable for achieving this purpose of research as it allows for deeper understanding and gaining a holistic view of the research phenomena.

The phenomenological method is subjective in nature (Koopman, 2015) and is suitable with the constructivism research approach. In addition to that, as mentioned before, the phenomenological method believes that multiple realities exist, which further aids this research in gaining insight into the philosophical assumption that goes in line with the research phenomena. The phenomenological research method allows researchers to gain completely new insight into phenomena by understanding the individual experience. Therefore, this method is positioned completely to support the inquiry

purpose of this research. It will allow the researcher to answer questions like, Why are managers effective/ineffective in retaining millennials in the organisation? What are the challenges?

3.6 Data Collection Tool

The data collection tool is an important part of any research. This is because choosing an incorrect method can result in an ineffective and invalid outcome to achieve. According to Liamputtong (2013), the qualitative data method is gathered in words normally collected through the mean of speech or stories. Alase (2017) highlighted interviews (structured or semi-structured), participant sampling and data storage and management as important sources of data collection employed by the researcher when adopting the interpretive phenomenological approach. However, with all those approaches, the focus group was also used to collect the data. The rationalisation for using each adopted qualitative collection data method will be provided with the evidence sources below:

3.6.1 Interviews

An interview is one of the most common methods adopted in qualitative research. Interview allows the researcher to gain factual evidence by interacting with participant individuals, such as in the form of question regarding the research area and gaining in-depth understanding not only through means of words but also through the body language of the participant at the time of conducting interviews. According to Babbie and Mouton (2011), interviews will allow the researcher to better understand millennials and managers at the workplace by exploring the experience at the workplace. This also reinstates the opinion shared by Seidman (1998) which states that understanding the experience of participant assist researcher to comprehend their research context. According to Jamshed (2014), every interview consists of structure to some extent. An interview can be fully structured, semi-structured or even light structured.

3.6.1.1 Structured Interviews

According to Burns (2002), structured interviews are usually straightforward and adopted when conducting quantitative research. A structured interview usually consists of pre-planned questions where objectives and response are predetermined in a

category. This makes interviews easy to carry out as questions are clearly and concisely written with clear-cut options, thus making the research easy to analyse statistically. According to Preece *et al.* (2002), this type of interview is mostly suitable when goals are already identified, and questions are definite. Gill *et al.* (2008) also shared similar opinions by stating that structured interviews do not allow researcher with any room for further follow-up questions, which might assist researcher in exploring the study area in more depth. Thus, making this method unsuitable for the current study where the research aims to explore the study area in more depth to better understand the issues on millennial retention.

3.6.1.2 Unstructured Interviews

Unstructured interviews are more likely to be used by the researcher when conducting a study on a long term and minimum response in the study field. Such as when using ethnography as a mean of data collection. This is because they are more likely to gain data through conversation than interviewing (Jamshed, 2014). Ethnography is more towards the interest of the researcher and is controlled by the researcher. Furthermore, unstructured interviews are more likely to be used when researchers conduct focused interviews where they are aware of the participant and only focus on the key subject, when necessary, with participants. Unstructured interviews are unsuitable for this research, as the study focuses on getting in-depth knowledge of manager and employees experience at the workplace.

3.6.1.3 Semi-Structure Interview

Arksy and Knight (1999) considered this type of interview method a hybrid of structured and non-structured interviews. This allows the researcher to consist of both set and open-ended questions, thus benefiting both (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). According to Given (2008), semi-structured is a widely adopted data collection strategy where participants are asked pre-determined yet open-ended questions. This allows the researcher to focus on key topics and explore more by asking questions about the emerging themes. In addition, semi-structured interviews allow the researcher to explore areas that were not predicted by them earlier, which assists them in exploring the study area in much more depth than expected. These interviews are mostly

conducted once over 30 minutes to 60 minutes, or even more depending on the interview context.

According to Jamshed (2014), in the semi-structured data collection method, the researcher uses interview guides to optimize their interview time by systemically and comprehensively exploring participants while keeping focused on the study area. Questions in semi-structured interview comprises the research area's central question, which the researcher further improves by conducting a pilot study. Burns (2002) stated that a semi-structured interview is the only method that allows the researcher to set pre-identified location and time to conduct the interview, thus allowing the researcher to set interviews considering the availability of both interviewer and interviewee.

To conduct interview, a semi-structured interview method was used to collect data. According to Bryman and Bell (2015), a semi-structured interview will allow an in-depth understanding of the problems. The semi-structured interview also allows the interviewer to adopt a more flexible approach to the questions, such as changing direction throughout the interview and allowing emerging themes to appear. In addition to that, non-directional interviews will allow interviewees to talk freely without any hesitation and allow them to expand their answers, such as allowing them to express their emotions and their experience of working in the company (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). All interviews were audiotaped in accordance with the interviewee preference. Later, it was used to analyse and transcript the data out of interviews. Regardless of non-directional interviews, data was analysed by considering the objective of the study.

A pilot test was conducted in the current study as Benson and Filippaios (2016) highlighted the importance of pilot study by stating that it allows the researcher to conduct small initial research to check the viability of their pre-determined questions and allows any concerning issues to be identified before the actual research is conducted. The pilot study was conducted on a faculty research candidate at the University of West of Scotland. Pilot study conducted was developed based on the interview protocol chosen for the data collection process. Pilot work assisted the researcher to improve its overall interview procedures by taking out some of the questions that made the respondent uncomfortable and by identifying the confusing questions due to lack of clarity.

Structured Interviews	Semi-Structured interviews
Dictated by the set schedule	Guided by the schedule rather than dedicated by it
Consist of specific short question	Questions are asked to establish a rapport
Questions are asked exactly as scheduled	Allows researcher to ask questions as emerging themes arises
Questions are asked in the identical row	Question is asked in non-identical order
Have pre-recorded response to match respondent answer with	Questions are followed by participant interest or concern

Table 4: The key difference between Structure and Semi-structured Interview

3.6.1.4 Focus Group

According to Nyomba *et al.* (2018), a focus group is another widely adopted data collection strategy where a limited number of peoples are gathered in the group for discussion. Parker &Tritter (2006) stated that a focus group is sometimes considered a synonym, especially in semi-structured interviews. This is because interviews are usually one-to-one conversations with the participant where the researcher aims to investigate the study area. Whereas, in a focus group, the researcher acts more like a moderator rather than an investigator. They aim to use a focus group to comprehensively explore the study area by facilitating a group discussion on a small group of participants (Owidi *et al.*, 2015). In addition, focus group assist researchers to clarify, extend or even sometimes challenge the data collected by other means of data collection, such as interviews (Gill *et al.*, 2008). Thus, allowing the more effective outcome to be achieved.

A focus group was also used to collect data on the current study. According to Bryman and Bell (2015), a focus group will allow employees to group together and share their views and perceptions on the research topic. Group interviews were conducted to overcome the issues of some employees who hesitate to talk freely in one-to-one interviews. It also assisted the interviewer (researcher) gather diverse employee perceptions and efficiently interview large groups of people in a short, timely manner. To ensure that a realistic response and data was attained, employees were first interviewed on a one-to-one basis and then were gathered in a group to see if there is

any change in outcomes; that is, in terms of their perspective or in terms of identifying whether any new themes will emerge. Furthermore, to avoid any problem in the interview regarding the format of data, a pilot study was conducted.

3.6.1.5 Audio-taped

Most qualitative data consist of interviews as a data collection method, usually either video or audiotaped (Bailey, 2008). Most researcher use audio type to record the data with other means to record the data. Audios are mostly used to record the data as it allows the personal information to be secured, which can be difficult when video recording the data. Audiotapes are mostly recorded using a different portable device which is later than easily transcribed and stored. This is because handwritten notes are considered unreliable and can result in research missing some important points. Furthermore, audio recording allows the researcher to write less and focus more on the interview process. A recorded interview will allow the researcher to generate a verbatim transcript, which assists the researcher to focus on the study and analyse the data more promptly and effectively when establishing a rapport.

Audio taped was recorded only after receiving the participant's permission. Participant's comfort in terms of recording was considered throughout the process as some respondents might not be comfortable in recording as they may be concerned about how they sound etc. (Simons, 2012). Therefore, to overcome this, audio was playback at the start and end to satisfy the curiosity of each respondent. Like any other method, this method is not without its shortcoming, such as portable device failure or failure to record data in between the interview due to low voice, etc. Therefore, to overcome such issues, notes were taken alongside the audiotape to record important points. Extra equipment was kept ensuring it can be used just in case of portable device failure.

Audio taping can be time-consuming and can take a longer time to transcribe the data. Due to the amount of energy it takes to transcribe the data, sometimes a researcher uses someone else to transcribe it. However, this can cause invading the participant's personal information, which some participants may not be willing. In addition to that, other people might not be familiar with the researched area. Therefore, the researcher transcribed the data and handled the whole process to ensure effective outcomes to overcome such issues.

3.6.1.6 Field Notes

Field notes are usually taken when conducting interviews. These are mostly recorded in the handwritten form alongside audiotaped. However, it is difficult for the researcher to record non-verbal communication such as expression and body language when audiotaping. Therefore, in this study, field notes were taken alongside audio taping to gain effective outcome. Field notes importance was also highlighted by Pattons (1990) by considering them as important when collecting data using interviews. In this study, the researcher noted each participant's expression, tone, posture, and comfort level, especially considering each question asked while conducting the interviews. This also aided the researcher in using it as a backup plan at the time of recorded failure or when the participant refuses to grant permission for audio recording at a later stage.

In addition to that, it allowed the researcher to mark critical aspects of interviews, which played an essential part when transcribing the data, ultimately allowing the outcome to be more precise and effective. According to Bryman and Bell (2007), field notes are necessary when taking the interviews to gain effective outcomes. This is because reactions observed during interviews add up to information recorded, further assisting in transcribing the data in more in-depth detail.

3.7 Sampling and Participant Selection

Sampling is an important aspect of the research with the help of which whole methodology takes its place. Choosing a sufficiently representative and accurate sample ensures that the findings of a study are generalizable to the population being studied (Schreier, 2018). With the help of proper sampling, the aspects of methodology are visible. Sampling is an important aspect of primary research with the help of which the research assumes the type of participants to be chosen for the research.

3.7.1 Sampling Process

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

According to Liamputtong (2013), there are two major sampling methods: random sampling or non-random sampling.

3.7.2 Type of Random Sampling

3.7.2.1 Probability Sampling

A probability sampling is an widely used sampling format with the help of which the research is able to sample in a systematic way. Here the whole population can enter into the sampling. With the help of this sampling a reasonable amount of the population gets included and involved in the procedure. Here the researcher usually constructs a frame of the whole sample with the help of which the organization of the sample is possible (Lamm & Lamm, 2019). Here the selection process is very random which makes the inclusion of different types of sample easier. The sampling format is very free in its nature and with the help of this format a certain kind of bias is possible. The cost effective structure of the sampling makes it not so easily accessible. This type of sampling is also very time-consuming for the purpose of which the researcher often skips this. The generation difference that is visible in the sampling is huge. Most of the participants are millennial and they are seen to be working in the e-retail section.

3.7.2.2 Simple Random Sampling

In this type of sampling the inclusion is available to a great extent. As this type of sampling encourages the different types of population to get included, it is known as an inclusive form of sampling. This sampling also consumes a reasonable amount of time for the purpose of which the sampling procedure often gets delayed. Sampling is an integral part of data collection and this type of sampling enriches the type of data collection (Banning, 2021). The data collection method can be prone to errors, and the addition of complicated sampling often makes the data collection process difficult. In simple random sampling, the ensured inclusion of different sections of participants increases the prospects that the observed findings will be sufficiently representative of the actual phenomenon (Banning, 2021). The time that is invested in the whole procedure becomes worthy with the help of this sampling.

3.7.2.3 Systematic Sampling

In this sample, the researcher chooses a certain number, after which a random sample is selected. For example, the researcher may use every seventh person passing by (Taherdoost, 2016). In this type of sampling the whole procedure is very systematic. Here the researcher is able to create a better atmosphere with the help of sampling as the procedure of sampling is a systematic one. Here the researcher chooses the participants after every seventh or sixth of the names (Xu & Goodacre, 2018). This type of sampling is not very widely used. Here the researcher requires a reasonable amount of participants to choose from them. It is not very applicable in reality as the researcher in the present times usually does not have that much of a choice over the participants. The researcher here requires a certain amount of dominance over the participant access to get this sampling done. This is also not very scientific and beneficial for the research, and as such, it was excluded from further consideration for the purposes of the study.

3.7.2.4 Stratified Sampling Method

In this sample, the researcher divides the population into sub-groups and then chooses randomly from each group to be included in the sample. This is mainly used when researchers aim to gain data from different populations such as different company, gender, etc.

3.7.2.5 Cluster Sampling

In this sample, the researcher divides all population in group and then randomly choose from each group to be included in the samples such as specific industry or region etc. (Wilson, 2010). This sample is useful when the researcher aims to collect data from a large geographical area (Davis, 2005).

3.7.2.6 Multi-Stage Sampling

This is a step-by-step procedure where researcher conduct random sample from broad to narrow sample size. This is usually used by a large organization when surveying to save time and money. All these methods are suitable to be used when collecting quantitative data. However, the non-random sampling method is most effective for qualitative data collection (Taherdoost, 2016). A similar opinion was noted by Yin (2003), a similar opinion states that non-random sampling methods are useful when researchers aim to study life-phenomenon rather than statistic data.

3.7.3 Types of Non-Random Sampling

3.7.3.1 Quota Sampling

According to Davis (2005), in this sampling, participants are selected considering the pre-determined characteristic where the total sample will be equal to the characteristic distribution as a whole population.

3.7.3.2 Snowball Sampling

In this sampling method, few existing cases encourage further cases to participate in the study. However, they are more likely to be used when the research nature is secretive or inaccessible due to their nature (Breweton and Millward, 2001).

3.7.3.3 Convenience Sampling

In this sampling method, researchers select easily available participants or are already willing to participate in research, such as friends or family. This is the most favoured method of student researcher as it is easy to conduct.

3.7.3.4 Purposive Sampling

According to Maxwell (1996), purposive sampling researchers deliberately select certain settings or people to provide them with the required and important information that is not accessible through other choices.

Table 5: Advantages and Disadvantages of Non-random Sampling Methods by Taherdoost (2016):

Non-random sampling	Advantage	Disadvantage
Quota Sampling	Controlled by certain characteristics to select a sample	Biasness in selection
Snowball Sampling	Suitable when researching rare characteristics	Can be time-consuming
Convenience Sampling	Convenient, easy and less time consuming	Biasness in selection
Purposive Sampling	Easily understood and results projectable	It can be sometimes difficult to construct a sampling frame

3.8 Sampling of this Study

As mentioned earlier in the thesis, the UK economy consists of 99% of SMEs as the rate of SME's is relatively high in the UK. Therefore, it was decided to use the purposive sampling technique for this research by limiting the sample size of the current study by focusing on one of the UK cities and two companies within that city. By looking at the report of SME's contribution in different cities by Hampshire Trust Bank (2017), it was decided to research in Birmingham. The reason for this was because

according to the report, Birmingham was recorded to contribute £6 billion in 2016, and their contribution is expected to increase by 18% by 2025 as can be seen below.

Birmingham is an emerging place which is contributing towards the youth population. It has observed the very ups and downs of youth population with the help of which the researcher may be able to understand the employability of the youth population. The place has observed downfall of youth population in the employment in the previous times and in the years the involvement of youths has increased reasonably with the help of which the youth population is able to make a mark (Rahman, 2019). In this place, the employability of the youths is visible in a clarified way which makes it easier for research. In figure 5 the place holds a lower place than other, but it has significance in terms of youth population and their employment behaviour.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at the Hampshire Trust Bank.

Figure 5:Source: Hampshire Trust Bank (2017)

Furthermore, another reason was by looking at the working population and student rate (millennials). Birmingham's working population was noted to be 64.2% (Birmingham City Council, 2018) and Birmingham is considered the second-largest student portal (Davidson, 2015). Therefore, two SMEs from the e-retail industry in Birmingham were chosen to conduct the research. In addition, two SMEs from the same e-retail industry were chosen as samples for this research to ensure effective outcomes were achieved at the end of this research. Watch retailers were selected for this research as it would be a contrasting aspect and would help in comparing e-retail and watch organization to

understand the contribution of millennial there. In addition, the watch retailers were easy to access for the purpose of the research. Due to the constraints imposed by COVID and the limited time within which the study could be conducted, 14 participants were included in the research; 10 employees and 4 managers. The managers and employees were interviewed in this study to capture multiple realities and perspectives from both sides. In general, it allowed the researcher to gain a better insight into the current situations and the problems. Both organisations were contacted for the research and were formally approached through the formal procedure of UWS at the start of the research. They were interviewed at their convenient time only after their voluntary acceptance to participate in the research.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Before conducting any study, the researcher needs to consider any ethical implications involved with the study. Many authors, including Fouka and Mantzorou (2011) and Steiner and Steiner (1994), defined ethics as an essential part of the philosophy that assists researchers in making decisions on what is good or bad. Sieber (1998) and Whiteley (2002) also reaffirmed the importance of ethical consideration by stating that adopting ethical behaviour is essential to every researcher. This is because it assists them in creating a win-win rapport in which each respondent participates willingly. Therefore, ethical decisions should be observed throughout the process, starting from the design until the data collection and analysis process (Spicker 2011).

According to Sanjari *et al.* (2014), the nature of qualitative data is challenging ethically. It will result in many ethical concerns raised as it requires direct involvement on different stages with the people being considered for the study. Because of the sensitive relationship between the researcher and study group, it is essential to formulate specific ethical guidelines before and after the end of the research. Hammersley and Trainou (2012) further indicated that when research is conducted in the natural setting instead of a purposely designed study like the current study, it increases the need for ethical issue consideration.

Furthermore, Sanjari *et al.* (2014) indicated that conducting qualitative research tends to face difficulty in many aspects, such as data confidentiality, anonymity, consent from the study group, and research impact. This further reinforces the need to formulate practical guidelines and protocols for all the stages of the research. Therefore, some of

the ethical formulations were made to establish a relationship with the participant. A few of them are as follows:

- Every research requires a code of ethics to safeguard the participant's identity; therefore, guaranteed confidentiality should be maintained to avoid any unwanted participant disclosure (Barbour, 2014). Hammerseley and Traianou (2012) further indicates the significance of confidentiality by stating that no harm or humiliation should be caused to participants due to the researcher's tactlessness. Respect for privacy, confidentiality and anonymity was maintained through the current study. All data were recorded under the Data Protection Act 1998 of the UK. Recorded data were used for research purposes only and will be discarded after the relevant period of research. Anonymity, the confidentiality of participants, was significantly considered before publishing any research content (University of Sussex, 2012).
- Before the data collection, the researcher must gain informed consent from all participants (Nijhawan, 2013). According to Armiger (1997), informed consent is where participant willingly and consciously decides to take part in the study and at the same time provides apparent evidence mean to the researcher conferring their consent. Informed consent was taken before the research, and participants were made aware of the content of the study. For example, what data will be collected and how it will be used, so they will be aware of how the research might impact them, their potential role, study objective and how the following research will contribute to the knowledge of business context. In addition to all that, to avoid any miscommunication, it will be relayed in informed consent form in a comprehensive manner and language (University of Sussex, 2012). In addition to that, the consent method process was also applied, stating that participant can withdraw at any time or point of the study, thus, further reassuring participants.
- Participant safety is another important ethic code which the researcher should follow. Every research consists of some form of potential harm, thus, making it essential for the researcher to ensure that participant well-being will be confirmed throughout the research. To overcome this, various books such as Saunders *et al.* (2009) were taken into reference. Furthermore, interviews were

conducted with great care and only after gaining necessary ethical training before the data collection method. Additionally, UWS ethics codes and regulatory framework were followed throughout the research to prevent or reduce any participant harm. Considering the current pandemic protocol, interviews were conducted using mixed method; both face-to-face and social media platforms like Zoom and Skype ensuring the safety of participants.

- As the qualitative data is based more on text production and less on numerical output, researchers must remove any traditional approach to it as it can have a biased opinion or credibility (Sanjari *et al.*, 2014). Misinterpretation of data was avoided throughout the research and was investigated without any biased opinion to ensure validated outcomes. To avoid bias from the study, each participant opinion was listened to and analysed without any pre-judgment on the topic (Saunders *et al.*, 2009).

3.9.1 Quality Criteria of Qualitative data for this Study

This section will address the quality criteria of qualitative research methods. Credibility in qualitative research methods is not as straightforward as quantitative research. This is because the qualitative research method primarily focuses on presenting multiple realities and viewpoints (Lincoln and Guba, 2000), whereas quantitative data obstruct positivism.

Quantitative research focuses entirely on the ontological stance and believes that objective reality can be achieved and ascertained. Therefore, making it easier for quantitative researchers to take into consideration the concept of reliability and validity. On the other hand, for the qualitative researcher, validity and reliability become incompatible when considering it with ontological and epistemological concepts (Carpenter and Suto, 2008). Furthermore, Johnson and Waterfield (2004) reaffirm that qualitative data is expressive and constructed solely by considering the multiple realities, thus making it impossible to use the same rules and criteria for validity and reliability as quantitative data research.

Peskin (1993) further critically examined the quality of the qualitative research method and stated that there is no one specific model a qualitative study researcher can adopt. There is no promise or certainty of delivering the outcomes and no specific ground of

the study's design, process, and outcomes. Hence, making authors signifying the stress on qualitative data research in making decisions on suitable framework and research design for their study will result in the most effective outcome to achieve. Lincoln and Guba (2002) also shared and agreed with Peshkin(1993) opinion and stated that there are no specific criteria when measuring the validity and reliability of qualitative research methods. However, when studying the view of both researchers, it was recognized that both researchers considered credibility as the appropriate and meaningful benchmark for a qualitative research study. The quality of qualitative data significantly depends on the choice of research methodology, approach, and design and how effective and useful it is in producing meaningful data for the research.

Lincoln and Guba (1985) suggested trustworthiness and authenticity as the credibility of interpretivism/constructivism. They classified the assessment of trustworthiness into four rigour criteria further agreed by Carpenter and Suto (2008). Four criteria are credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability and have been accepted as the most adopted by business management quality researchers (Golafshani, 2003; McNulty, 2012). The current study will also adopt the four criteria proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1985) and Carpenter and Suto (2008). Authors like Raines (2008), Cresswell(2012) and Liamputtong (2013) pointed out that credibility is linked to the internal validity of the data, whereas transferability focus on the external validity of the data while the dependability and confirmability links with the objectivity and reliability of the research.

3.10 Credibility

According to Raines (2011) and Bryman (2012), credibility is connected to the question of how truthful and authentic outcomes can be considered. Padget (2008) also pointed out that credibility examines whether the explanation/information provided by the participants fit with the inquiry/description of the researcher. As stated earlier, credibility is linked to internal validity, as suggested by Lincoln and Guba (1985). This is further agreed by Van der and Durrheim (2007), and they pointed out that constructivism/interpretivism believes that multiple realities exist, and suggested credibility should be done based on how convincing and realistic outcomes are. To check the credibility of this study, the member checking technique will be used.

3.10.1 Member Checking

Lincoln and Guba (1989) considered member checking as the most useful technique when checking the study's credibility. Birtet *al.* (2016, p1) defined member checking as “*participant or respondent validation, is a technique for exploring the credibility of results. Data or results are returned to participants to check for accuracy and resonance with their experiences*”.

Doyle (2007) highlighted that member checking is all about verifying the truth and richness of the data. This method was also adopted in the current study. Once data was collected and transcribed, it was sent back to participant for feedback and confirmation, thus, increasing the credibility of the study.

3.11 Transferability

Bryman (2012) pointed out that transferability investigates how current study can be generalized or current outcomes can be applied to a different study/research. Padgett (2008) also agreed and shared a similar opinion and stated that transferability refers to the extent to which current study contexts can be applied to a different study. In the current study, researchers aim to provide an in-depth understanding of the nature of the study topic, objective, methodology and outcomes. It is anticipated that the outcome provided by the current study will benefit business managers and provide scope for further research or transferability of data where applicable and suitable.

A comprehensive description will be provided in this study to provide readers or other researchers with assistance in determining whether the current finding is transferable or applicable to their study (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In addition, in this study, context on SME's and current pandemic concern in the UK, observed behavior, and different HR dimensions will be provided, allowing readers to understand and depict how useful/similar current study is to their context (Erlandson *et al.*, 1993).

3.12 Dependability

Raines (2011) pointed out that dependability focuses on outcome uniformity and conformity of the study. According to Cohen *et al.* (2007), dependability concentrates on portraying and providing authentic and accurate data conforming based on the real-life experience of the participant. Mestry (2004) also shared a similar opinion and pointed out that dependability refers to the extent to which the study's finding is consistent and repetitive over time.

For this study, the recording technique was used to assist researchers in exploring and keeping track of the current study. Diary was kept throughout the research to record the research details, such as any emerging data or personal opinion due to observed body language. These records will assist the researcher in drawing out and presenting information with supporting documentation as evidence to prove the claim (Erlandson *et al.*, 1993).

3.13 Confirmability

Confirmability refers to the validity of the data. It ensures that the finding/outcomes are not misinterpreted and misrepresented by the researcher. In reality, attaining the full objective of the study is difficult or somewhat impossible. Lincoln and Guba (1985) highlighted that the confirmability of the study depends on the extent to which the study outcomes are derived as a result of the study and not through individual personal prejudice. They further suggested that confirmability in the study is attainable through confirmability assessment trials. Assessment trail in confirmability represents that process and choice made in carrying out the research are open for further discussion or criticized by others.

This study also takes into consideration the confirmability assessment trail. Supporting documents, including a sample of the consent form, sample of information sheet and NVivo thematic map, will be presented in the Appendix of the current study as evidence to show that outcomes/results are obtained purely based on participants. In addition to that, the support of supervisors was used throughout the research process to avoid steering in a certain direction when carrying out the research.

3.14 Data Analysis of the Study

This section outlines the step-by-step procedure followed by the researcher to analyse the data, explaining how data and findings were interpreted for the study. Vaismoradi *et al.* (2015, p.100) defined the characteristic of the thematic data analysis process by stating that it is "*the systematic process of coding, examining of meaning and provision of a description.*" Thus, indicating and recommending thematic data analysis researcher to follow specific analytical method.

Considering this, the current study adopted a thematic web-like network framework proposed by Attride-Stirling's (2001) to organize the standard mean of the current

research. The thematic analysis consists of three stages to organize data extraction, as shown in the Figure 6 below. The first stage is Basic Theme, where collected data is simple and only provide a little information. However, when these little data are combined, they start to complement each other. The basic theme focuses on revealing what is going on in the data text. The second stage is Organising Themes, where codes are summarized together to provide a bigger picture/theme. This stage aims to enrich the meaning of wider themes that complement several other organizing themes. The third stage is Global Themes, seen as macro themes that incorporate the head illustrations in the whole data and provides a complete or last hypothesis (grounded up hypothesis).

Furthermore, it presents a contention and statement about a given matter or sureness pointed toward summing up and making insight of bunches of data gatherings (groups) and sub-groups (Walker and Myrick, 2006). Finally, it summarises the overall themes and explains the transcripts, consequently giving meaning to the transcripts as a whole in the data analysis process. Therefore, the current study decided to use thematic network analysis to provide a clear indication of the analysis procedure from the text until the interpretation of the data.

Additionally, throughout the research, a qualitative analytical tool was employed to facilitate the prevalence and better disclosure within the qualitative research method, as suggested by Miles *et al.* (2014) and Attride-Stirling (2001). Therefore, the above three stages, alongside four stages of thematic analysis (illustrated in detail in Chapter 4), were used to carry out the data analysis process carefully.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Attride-Stirling (2001, p.388)

Figure 6:**Source: Attride-Stirling (2001, p.388)****3.15****Summary**

The above chapter provides an overview of the researcher's knowledge and decision on the research method and process adopted. A clear justification was given in this chapter for each method and stance adopted for the study, such as why constructivism was chosen as epistemology and why the qualitative research method was considered to be the most appropriate method. Furthermore, the data collection and analysis tool are discussed in detail to give a clear picture of the method and processes of the current study. Ethical concern considered while carrying out the research has also been discussed as well. Lastly, the quality issue of qualitative data was also discussed in-depth to ensure the outcome is valid and trustworthy.

4.**Chapter 4****Findings and Discussion****4.1****Analysis Introduction**

In this chapter, findings gained through semi-structured interview will be addressed and analysed. Research questions will be used to organize the analysis findings of the study, and themes will be identified using the NVivo coding method. Discussion of findings will include participants' interpretation and will then be related to the existing literature available. A unique code was assigned to each participant to ensure confidentiality of each participant is maintained, and transcription cited in the study will be highlighted in italics.

4.1.1 Data Analysis Step Flowchart

Figure 7:

Source: Author

4.2 Qualitative Analysis

The section focuses on analysing the collected qualitative data to provide concrete answers to the five research questions.

4.2.1 Participants' Profile

The qualitative data for this study was collected from 14 participants: 10 employees and 4 company managers. 15 interviews were completed in total; fourteen individual

interviews with one focus group discussion with employees.

Figure 8: Gender of participants

Seven of the 14 participants were males, 5 were females, and 2 of the participants gave no response to the question on their gender. According to Stanborough (2021), some people do not identify themselves as male or female in today's world but rather as non-binary identity. For example, they may refer to themselves as either neutrois, agender or pangender, which means they may identify themselves as neutral gender, gender, or gender.

Figure 9: Experience of the Participants

The majority of the participants have over three years of experience in their respective firms. Only 4 of the participants have less than three years of experience. Furthermore, the data reveals that all employees are Millennials, 3 of the interviewed managers have belonged to Generation X, and one belongs to the Baby Boomer generation.

4.3 Qualitative Analysis Process

The qualitative analysis was conducted using NVivo software, a qualitative software analysis developed by QSR international. The analysis followed a 4-step process as indicated in the diagram below.

4.3.1 Stage 1: Reading and Interpretation of Text

Figure 10: Analysis stage diagram

The collected data was read several times during this phase to get a brief overview of the data. In addition, a word cloud diagram was formed using NVivo to depict the most used words and phrases in the data. This is mainly to ascertain if the most used words align with the research objectives.

Figure 11: World Cloud Diagram of the study

The most used words in the collected data are employees, working, company, opportunities, etc.

4.3.2 Stage 2: Coding of text

In this phase, the qualitative data was carefully read, and meaning was ascribed to the phrases in the form of codes using NVivo. The data was read and studied repeatedly more than eight times. The initial coding reveals a total of over 246 codes, as indicated in the appendix. This was later reduced in the theme development course; codes that are irrelevant to the research objectives were removed. All 15 documents were coded using NVivo, as seen in the diagram coding tree diagram below.

Figure 12: Coding Tree Diagram

4.3.3 Stage 3: Theme Classification

The codes were grouped concerning the existing relationship between them to form themes. The analysis reveals a total of 36 themes, as shown in the thematic diagram below; As earlier indicated, the coding was done with NVivo. The themes and their corresponding codes are indicated in the appendix. The thematic analysis is divided into two sections, the employee data thematic analysis and the management data thematic analysis. The two sections will be aggregated in the discussion section to give succinct answers to the research questions.

4.4 Sentimental Analysis

A sentimental analysis was conducted on the responses to ascertain their level of satisfaction with their current job. The section will extensively discuss the very negative

and negative sentiments. This is done to ascertain areas that need improvement for millennial employee retention.

	Very negative	Moderately negative	Moderately positive	Very positive
e1	0	1	4	3
e2	4	1	4	1
e3	3	1	8	4
e4	0	4	8	3
e5	0	3	8	0
e6	2	7	11	2
e7	2	2	6	2
e8	2	3	7	5
e9	0	8	6	3
e10	1	2	4	4

Figure 13

Figure 14

4.4.1 Negative Sentiments

The negative sentiments on the job revolve around working long hours and excessive workload; One respondent (**E10**) stated that:

Yes, especially in festive periods. We work long hours in festive periods as being a small company we do not have enough staff so it can get really difficult sometimes to take a day off when needed.

Lyon and Kuron (2014) also pointed out that millennials' mentality has significantly changed after seeing their parents working for long hours. Seeing them working long hours and not investing much time in family has made millennials re-evaluate their work and life priorities. They do not like working long hours and prefer to have a work-life balance (Rubin, 2017). Singh and Rai's (2012) research on millennials also indicated that millennials do not prefer to work for an organisation where they must work long hours or are not provided with any flexibility. Their research also indicated that millennials put great importance on having work-life balance.

It also entails the company having unspecified objectives, which directly influences the work rate and motivation of the employees, having a specified objective gives them a sense of purpose.

E3: *They do, but it is always unclear as to what they are after. They don't have a specific objective, probably because they are still growing.*

This aligned with Spiegel's (2011) and Narayan (2014) literature, which highlighted that millennial prefer to have clear communication. They prefer to have a clear sense of purpose and objective at work.

The next negative sentiment revolves around inadequate training; participants highlighted that the training they receive is grossly inadequate; one respondent (**E3**) said "No", *They just provide some videos as instruction, but they don't offer proper training.* According to one of the Forbes authors Morin (2016), millennials look for quick training as they are quick learners. Therefore, they prefer to have more consistent and short training rather than weeklong. Sportelli (2015), another author of Forbes, stated that millennials have higher expectations regarding training. In addition to that, the author highlighted that millennial prefer to have more content in terms of training, not just technological based. This is because they recognize the importance of training and its impact on individuals, future career, and society as a whole. PwC (2020)

research on millennials also indicates that more than 30% of millennials look for organizations that offer effective learning and development opportunities.

Participants highlighted the inadequate communication between the managers and employees; they highlighted that the communication had been seldom, and the rate of meetings have been exceedingly low. For example, one respondent (**E6**) indicated that:

Relation with my manager is pretty good but recently we have been experiencing a communication gap. Not frequent meetings are happening. Our last in-depth meeting was done at the start of this pandemic crisis since then we did not have a proper meeting.

This communication gap slowly destroys any form of relationship between the management and the employees. The lack of communication means the goal and objectives of the firm will not be communicated to the employees. It will be difficult for hardworking employees to gain recognition in a work environment where communication is lacking. As mentioned earlier in the literature, millennials were raised with constant talk and conversation. Simmon's (2015) and Myers and Sadaghiani's (2010) research also supported the participant opinion by stating that millennials employee prefer to have transparent and open communication with the organisation as they want to feel as part of the organisation and prefer to be kept up to date with the situation whether the organisation is facing loss or profit. This is because when they are kept in the loop, they can have better ideas on the situation and are likely to put more effort when needed. Lack of appreciation for hard work is also a contributing factor to the negative sentiments.

E6 indicated:

Dissatisfying factors would be not being fully appreciated. Not enough perks are given and your salary if it does not reflect the hard work that you put in then obviously that could be quite dissatisfying.

E7 further indicated:

There is not much of an appraisal. Like if someone has done a good job then they should tell you like okay last week this and that happened, and you guys have done a good job.

SHRM (2009) study revealed that millennials look for close/friendly relationship with their managers and expect frequent feedback and appreciation. Buckeley *et al.* (2017) also suggested that millennials were raised in constant feedback. Therefore, they prefer to work in an environment that encourages discussion, feedback, and communication. Myers and Sadigiani (2010) research further indicated a similar finding that millennials prefer to work in an organisation where communication and feedback are rather accepting and encouraged. With criticism, millennials also expect to be appreciated for a job well done by their managers as they were raised as trophy kids by their parents and teachers in school, even for coming last.

One of the fundamental contributors to the negative sentiments is remuneration. Participants highlighted that their salary is inadequate compared to the hard work they put into the company, and they also lamented the lack of increase in their salary. They indicated the following by stating:

E2:

Well, there are many ways an organization can clearly express appreciation towards their employee that they could give him a bonus when he achieves the target or does something. They can give him a raise or if they are not financially strong, they can increase holidays or they can give a small gift as a token of appreciation. They can also offer promotions in terms of position in the company.

E6:

They can express appreciation by giving their employees more perks. By giving them good holidays, salary raise and progression opportunities.

E2 further indicated that.

Well, I am a very committed person, so I have already committed 5 years of my life to this company. But now I think it is time to move on and the reason is that I don't get reserve things like I don't get a pay raise that much and I don't get many bonuses. There is not much interesting work for me to perform or progress further.

According to the Corporate Leadership Council (2005), manager quality is one of the top requirements for motivation. Joshi (2012) also shared a similar opinion and stated that a salary increment is necessary to build loyalty among employees, especially millennials. Singh and Rai's (2012) research on millennials also indicated that 51% of respondents suggested leaving if they have a toxic boss. Their research highlighted that millennial do not like nitpicking managers and tend to leave or switch to different workplaces if they feel they are not being treated right or their performance is not being recognized. Singh and Rai's (2012) research further indicated on millennials that 42.55% responded that they are likely to leave if they see unfairness at their work. They prefer their appraisal to be based on performance and prefer individual-centric treatment. If they do not feel valued, then they are likely to leave the company. Landrum (2017) also shared a similar opinion. As highlighted in the literature review, when employees feel like they are not being valued, they are likely to put less effort toward the organisation's success.

The study by Robert Walter Group (2020) also indicated that organisations should focus on having personalized training at work to keep their millennial employees engaged at the workplace.

4.5 Thematic Analysis

4.5.1 Employee Data Analysis

Figure 15

4.5.1.1 Theme 1: Factors that Promote Engagement.

The theme is exploring the factors that can promote the involvement of millennials in the day-to-day activities of a firm. Additionally, the theme is exploring the factors that can be used to attract Millennials and actions adopted for employee retention.

Figure 16:

4.5.1.1.1 Attributes of an Ideal Work Environment

All participants want their work environment friendly; they all do not desire to work in a hostile environment. They believe their ideal work environment should have friendly colleagues and friendly supervisors. They should also have an excellent relationship with their managers and colleagues. They stress the need for a work environment where they can seek help from colleagues and seniors easily. This ultimately increases their productivity.

E1: *To have open communication and support from managers.*

E6:

Perfect environment for me is where you are respected and appreciated for the work you do. You will have friendly employees and management to work and you are motivated to work harder.

E9:

From the workplace would be just to create a nice atmosphere for the employees to work in and employees being able to speak freely about what is needed from management and also from fellow staff.

Research by Bibby (2001) on good jobs indicated that employees look for friendly and helpful colleagues more than the pay factor and prefer job security and a sense of accomplishment at the workplace. Gupta (2020) research on millennials also indicated that 80 % of respondents prefer to work in an organisation where they are treated with respect, followed by having friendly and helpful employees. The author tried to reinforce the respect factor as one of the critical factors recognized by millennials. One of the articles by Landrum (2017) in Forbes also suggested that millennials' happiness is highly interlinked with their relationship with their work colleagues. Millennials tend to be more productive when they have work friendships. Landrum (2017) pointed out that friendly work colleagues never existed before and has been more of a new generational thing. The older generation sharing personal information at work has been a taboo. In contrast, the millennial generation tends to share more of their details with their colleague “work best friend” more than ever before.

Participants further highlighted their desire to work in an environment where they are respected and appreciated for their input to the firm. Participants believe an ideal work environment should operate on the principles of teamwork, talent diversity, honesty, and integrity. They also believe the presence of healthy competition is an attribute of an ideal work environment. Some direct narratives of the respondent are as follows:

E1:

My perfect work environment would be the place where everything would be good, like, I would have good facilities regarding like salary wise and support

to do my work when needed in terms of training. Oh yeah! Another thing I would also prefer is to work with friendly and helpful co-workers. No extra panel from managers.

E6:

Perfect environment for me is where you are respected and appreciated for the work you do. You will have friendly employees and management to work and you are motivated to work harder.

E7: *I would describe that as one that is cantered on working as a team that'll allow every talent to flourish.*

As per the literature review, Tolbzie (2008) also highlighted something similar and stated the difference in generation attitude. The millennial generation prefers to work in a team. Jones and Barrett (2016) also agreed and stated that leaders must have strong team concepts, allowing and encouraging all employees to participate and show their talent, ultimately resulting in company talent and performance flourish. Safety, adequate training, and adequate remuneration were among the required attributes in an ideal work environment. Respondent indicated the following:

E8:

To be treated fairly, to be able to approach manager if there is any issue. For them to make sure it is safe place to work with all healthy and safety policy up to date and followed.

E10:

This was my first job so I personally didn't had much expectation other than to work for the company which offers training and opportunity to grow and learn new skills. But yes if you ask me now, I would still say the same as I still thrive to work for company which offers learning and development opportunities and better pay.

Speigel (2011) also indicated millennial expectation by stating training and leadership as one of the major factors for their retention. Simmons (2016) agreed with this and stated that the millennial generation expects continuous workplace training and demand high compensation.

Millennial employees expect their workplace to have provision for cultural and religious diversity. For example, a participant highlighted that she would like her place of employment to have a designated area for Islamic prayers.

E7: *I expect to have a good environment and have a small room assigned at the workplace where being a Muslim I can go and offer my prayers.*

Another respondent (**E3**) indicated that *I like the environment of my current organisation. It is mixed culture, and that's what I look for mainly.*

PwC (2021) research also had similar responses when they conducted a study on female millennials. Their research indicated 86% of their female respondents stated that they would prefer to work in an environment that offers diversity and inclusion. However, PwC (2021) research also shared that according to their research, only 71% of their female millennial respondents felt that their organisation talks about diversity but does not provide equal opportunity. Johansson (2017), one of the authors of Forbes, also pointed out that millennials are attracted to a diverse workforce as they have grown with the concept that diversity is important. In addition, they consider diversity as an ethical imperative. The article also highlighted that 47% look for diversity and inclusion when looking for a job.

Health and safety are qualities of an ideal workplace that cannot be compromised. Participants revealed that they expect their employers to provide them with a healthy and safe work environment.

E5: *Proper health and safety in place with a clean and organized workplace.*

E8:

To be treated fairly, to be able to approach manager if there is any issue. For them to make sure it is safe place to work with all healthy and safety policy up to date and followed.

Landrum (2017) also agreed and shared a similar opinion by stating that millennials consider safety a top priority. They decisively work on the safety expectation and always look to improve it. As a result, they have raised safety requirements and expectations much higher than any other generation. Easy and open communication with senior colleagues and managers with adequate support from the managers are part

of what is expected of an ideal workplace by millennials. One respondent (E2) highlighted that:

My expectation from the workplace is always that I should get a salary on time. I should be properly facilitated for my work, and no extra burden should be given to me.

Another, E4, indicated that:

When you work hard, you expect more encouragement and more confidence from your seniors and managers.

Lastly, E9 suggested:

From the workplace would be just to create a nice atmosphere for the employees to work in and employees being able to speak freely about what is needed from management and also from fellow staff.

4.5.1.1.2 Factors that promote the desire to stay.

Retaining millennial employees is a big challenge for firms; this is mainly because millennial's get bored easily, and they often seek opportunities elsewhere. However, firms can increase their rate of retention if they are offering the employees the following.

- They offer their employee's career progression opportunities.
- They offer the employees an increment in wages over time.

Big firms have a higher retention rate than small and medium scale firms mainly because the bigger firms have better career progression, training, and professional development opportunities.

As highlighted in the literature review by Boldonado and Spangenburg (2009), Adkins and Rigoni (2016), authors of Gallup, also indicated that 87% of millennials rate career progression and development as top requirements when looking for a job. Millennials do not like waiting, whether regarding feedback or their career progression and development. They want constant feedback, recognition, and remuneration. Additionally, millennials like to be proactive, and Adkins and Rigoni (2016) discovered

that 93% of millennials tend to leave the organization if they are not offered proactive tasks and opportunities.

Forbes' (2020) recent survey also indicated that 74% of millennials expect a pay rise every year. Their survey also indicated that millennials tend to switch to different jobs if they are not given frequent pay rises. Survey also indicated that millennials had negotiation skills, and 59% of millennials use this skill to get a pay rise. They claim they have better offers available when they did not. When participants were asked whether they will stay with their current organisation, they responded as below:

E3:

If they do little changes as I highlighted, then yeah, I would like to work for the longer term. I would also love to have a raise in terms of salary.

E4:

Due to this pandemic, I will say. But as I said earlier, I am looking for a job in large organizations as well on the side where I can utilize my skills more and have more career growth.

E5:

Even though I have been offered career progression within the company, I have not been offered much of a raise in terms of my salary and rewards.

E6:

If my current employees offer better training and progression and opportunities with great salary raise, then I will stay.

Hosie (2017) also agreed and shared his opinion by stating that millennials are used to being rewarded for some accomplishment as their parents raised them like that, so they expect the same when it comes to the workplace. Arruda (2017), one of the authors by Forbes shared in his article that 87% of millennials look for career progression when looking for a job. Recent research was done by Mayangdarastri and Khusna (2020) also highlighted the significance of career path and development for millennials and how essential a role it can play in millennial retention. The Millennial generation has been

recognized as one of the most impatient generations and looks for rapid recognition, salary, or promotion (Tulgan, 2009; Hoover *et al.*, 2016).

4.5.1.2.3 Alignment of Company Goals with Personal Goals

Employees are more likely to remain with a firm if some of the firm's activities align with their goals and convictions. Hence, they will find a sense of purpose with the firm, hence remaining with the firm. In addition, participants revealed that the firm's activities involving community service align with their personal growth and aspirations.

One of the respondents(**E9**) stated that:

Somewhat yes, I will say, as I said earlier, it is the product and service that we are providing, so it sort of helps the community, especially in these pandemic times, and that what I would say is my personal goal and aim to be more active in the society.

The importance of alignment of a company with employee goals has been highlighted by various authors in literature (Wellinset *al.*, 2005, Ayer, 2007; Cook, 2008). For example, Cook (2008) highlighted the importance of alignment of goals by stating that when employees are made aware of goals, they are likely to achieve them as they are likely to feel part of the goal. Spiegel (2011) also reinforced the need to communicate goals with employees to have effective outcomes and productivity.

Some of the participants also revealed that meeting the target of the company and the dogged drive for success by the management of the firm fuel their desire to continuously engage with the firm.

E1:*By encouraging me to hit daily targets and ensure my services are delivered effectively and efficiently.*

E2:*Well, the company and I both want to progress, and this is the only goal that aligns with my work.*

PwC (2011) research further suggested that managers must understand millennials' personal goals and professional progression for better retention. Harvard Business Review author Rigoni and Adkins (2016) pointed out that millennials tend to leave organisations if they are not provided with a sense of purpose or if the work does not fulfil their personal goals and values. They highlighted that millennial shop for those

goals which best align with their personal goals and needs. Another Harvard Business Review article by Anchor *et al.* (2018) indicated that 9 out of 10 millennials are willing to work for organisations that offer less pay and more meaningful work. Alesso-Bendisich (2020) also suggested in one of her recent Forbes articles that millennials look for purpose. They require focus and have a strong desire to do more and give back. Therefore, millennials look for companies that align with their internal values and a sense of purpose.

4.5.1.1.4 Impact of Leadership on Employee Retention

The leadership of any firm plays a fundamental role in the rate of retention. The participants revealed that the management can increase their level of engagement by making their role in the firm clearly defined; this will give the millennial employees a clear vision of what is expected of them, thereby making them perform optimally in this position. Also, managers can increase the productivity of millennial employees through constant encouragement and motivation. Respondent indicated as below:

E4: *Well, yes, my manager encourages me which makes me feel motivated to do my work better.*

E9:

I think sometimes for me it is also the little sort of the manager or the boss comes to you and say that you have done a good job. These little initiatives at work encourages me to want more and to do better because you know you will be recognized for job well done.

Myers (2010) also shared similar results and pointed out that millennials actively look to work with leaders who adopt a democratic leadership style at the workplace and offer opportunities to employees to show their skills by training and empowering them. According to Newman (2010), millennials look upon their leaders and are highly influenced by them. As they were raised with supervision, they expect the same at their workplace. They expect effective management and leaders to work with.

Garber (2012) shared similar opinions in the literature review and highlighted that organisation must engage with their employees effectively. Spiegel (2012) also suggested that leaders have effective communication skills. He highlighted that only

through effective communication managers can better engage with their employees. They will be able to communicate goals better and will be able to better understand their millennials employees needs and wants, ultimately resulting in having better employee retention. Jones and Barrett (2016) also highlighted that effective leadership is necessary for millennial retention. Millennial employees thrive better under a democratic form of leadership where the managers listen to the employees' opinion and use these opinions as a blueprint for decision making. This gives the employees a sense of control and a sense of belonging.

One respondent (**E2**) indicated: *But the good thing is that he does listen to us and analyses the data and see our point of view as well so I will say that is a good point.* (**E3**) also commented and stated that

They do listen but sometimes they delay my idea by saying oh we will tell you or after few months what was the idea. I don't blame them as they are very busy as well. But I am still very happy with it as they accept most of my ideas and I get to work with new product lines which makes me feel very comfortable with what I do.

Fries (2018) also highlighted in one of the articles in Forbes that millennials show less willingness to work in an organisation when their leaders do not meet their standards. They embrace a less hierarchical structure and prefer leaders who not only give feedback but as well as value their opinion. They look for transformational leaders and look for empowerment. A Millennials leadership survey conducted in 2015 also showed that 63% of the millennial generation prefer to have transformational leadership at the workplace. This is because transformational leaders offer challenges to their employees and empower them (Ward, 2020).

Millennial employees prefer to work with some form of liberty and flexibility. The participants revealed that the leadership of their respective firms gives them a certain level of flexibility and autonomy. The leadership gives them access to complete any given task in whatever way they deem fit with no compromise in the delivery's quality and deadline.

E3: *Yes, they do let me do my job in my way.*

E8:

They are quite good at sorting my working hours around my university and also actually in terms of being at work as there is no such structure on how to complete the task. So, sort of let you do it as long as it is done.

E9:

Yes, my manager offers me flexibility and freedom where he can. We are not forced to work like robots, when he can give us the flexibility to do certain things the way we want to do it then we do.

As highlighted by Moss (2016) in the literature review, millennials do not prefer to work in a structured environment and prefer a flexible environment. Capnary *et al.* (2018) also pointed out that the level of flexibility significantly influences millennials' retention and satisfaction and the work-life balance they are offered. According to a Forbes (2019) survey, 70% of UK employees are more attractive to a flexible work environment than a structured one. However, Burnford (2019) further highlighted that only 10% of companies advertise flexibility in their job description, and a huge gap can be seen in the demand and supply.

4.5.1.1.5 Professional Development

Professional development is one of the core attributes considered by millennials when seeking to join an organization. As earlier highlighted, career development is directly proportional to the company's size. A section of the participants highlighted that their respective firms offer them skill improvement and career development opportunities. However, these opportunities are sometimes limited and inadequate. Participants, when questioned about professional development they responded the following:

E3: *Yes, I have been given the opportunity for professional growth but as it is a small company, I don't see much growth in the future.*

E4: *Yes, I did. I have participated in many new business proposals and strategies compared to my last job.*

E10: *As I said earlier, this is my first job but yes, I have developed and improved my skills at this workplace.*

As highlighted by Baldonado and Spagenburg (2009), millennials prefer to work in an organisation that provides them with the opportunity for further professional development and career progression. They are not merely satisfied with pay and rewards incentive but instead look beyond the financial means and aim for continuous

learning and development opportunities. Recent research by Behesti in Forbes (2019) suggested that only those organisations have seen sustaining loyalty among employees, especially young millennials, who have been providing them with continuous learning and development opportunities alongside the contribution opportunity within the community.

Tulgan (2009) further suggested that to attract and retain millennials; managers must highlight the importance of the project and how it will allow them to develop and grow professionally. According to a recent research by LinkedIn (2018), 94% of employees tend to be loyal and stay longer to the organization, which are likely to invest in them through continuous training, learning and development opportunities.

Moss (2016), the millennial generation looks for opportunities for development than any other generation before. PwC (2011) research also pointed out that more than 35% of their millennial respondents were attracted to employers who offer continuous development opportunities. Beardwell and Clayton (2014) and CIPD (2018) also reinforced the importance of continuous development by highlighting that maintaining sustainability in employee's development will not only benefit employees in improving their skills and abilities but will also allow the organization to develop and sustain a high level of contribution and performance within the organization.

The effect of learning and development and its impacts on employees, especially the millennials generation, is still questionable.

A recent study by Ezikova and Martinelli (2020) reaffirms and suggests that organisations invest in professional development. Professional networking and development instil a feeling of connectivity among employees and eases their anxiety, resulting in customer loyalty and high organizational performance. Especially in the current pandemic situation and rapidly changing environment, millennials face constant personal & professional pressure and anxiety. Therefore, it becomes critical for senior managers to regard this concern of their employees by facilitating them with development opportunity to boost their morale and confidently lead and enhance them in this ever-changing environment.

Jacob (2020) also suggested that millennials value and embrace organisation that provides continuous professional development opportunities and flexibility at the

workplace. Another study by Gabrielova and Buchko (2020) indicated the importance of constant development by stating that the millennial generation and Generation Z actively look for development opportunities. Around 50% of Generation Z were participating in more internship programs and were actively involved in on-the-job-development opportunities.

4.5.1.1.6 Improving Employee Capability through Training

Some participants highlighted that the level of training they receive from their respective firms before assuming their job role is insufficient and often inadequate. They highlighted that they sometimes get assigned to advance level projects despite receiving only junior level training.

E3: *No, they just provide some videos as instruction, but they don't offer proper training.*

E6:

To perform the job we have been given all the tools and we have got the skills, But sometimes feel we are thrown at the deep end of the sea where the management will give you the certain task to do and expect results as a senior-level staff but you are not trained for it.

E7:

Basically, when I started this job, I just got trained in one day and after that they just threw me in a pool of water and just said to me to figure it out. So, I just figured it out along the way. I made mistakes and they did come up to me telling about the mistakes. So, after a couple of weeks, I trained myself.

The employees highlighted that they often rely on self-training and on the job experience to excel in their assigned role. Although they believe learning is an endless endeavour as technological advancement keeps moving at an unprecedented rate, they suggest that firms should engage their employees in frequent, constant, and continuous training. They reaffirm that this will inevitably increase their level of efficiency. Spiegel (2011) research also indicated that millennials have certain expectations from their employer and pointed out coaching, mentoring and effective leadership to be the most expected ones. A recent article by Overfelt (2017) in CNBC highlighted what

millennials look for when starting or looking for a new job and adequate training was on the top of the list. Research further indicated that only 40% of employees considered themselves to be adequately trained for their job.

According to Gallup (2018) research, millennials were struggling badly to improve their performance as they indicated that they are not being offered as much effective coaching as they need. Another recent article by Furstner (2019) in Forbes suggested that organisations consider training an investment. When offered onboard training, new employees tend to be more familiar with the organisation and are more aware of their job expectations. They are likely to add value and integrate into the company goals more quickly when they are familiar. The article further indicated that 94% of employees tend to stay longer with an organisation that offers continuous training and development opportunities. In addition to that, training allows employees, especially new employees, to be familiar with the corporate culture and encourages them to perform better and be more productive.

4.5.1.1.7 Work Recognition

Recognizing and appreciating the work of a dedicated and hardworking employee is one of the components that encourage employee engagement. In comparison, some participants highlighted that their diligence and hard work are recognized and well appreciated by the management with appraisal and incentives such as yearly bonuses, holidays, and words of encouragement. However, a significant proportion of the participants stressed that they get little or no recognition in their firms.

E1:

My manager does see a lot of positive results from my work and appraise me for my creative ideas in our weekly discussion.

E2:

Well, my manager thinks and appraises me by saying that I play an important part within the organization.

E3:

They do look at our work, but I don't think we get much appreciation. E3 further added that They do give yearly bonuses on Christmas and sometimes extra pay for the extra hours we do but not always.

E10:

They appraise for the job well done for tackling certain situations on the spot and in our weekly meetings when we achieve our targets. They do reward us once a year through bonuses or through small gifts as a token of appreciation for all the hard work we do.

As highlighted in literature in past studies, millennials thrive for continuous recognition at the workplace. EdAssist(2015)research also indicated that 41% of millennials prefer personal and professional growth over higher pay. Hosie (2017) also shared a similar opinion and stated that many organisations fail to satisfy their employees as they do not appraise them as much. Millennial parents raised them with continuous appraisal and rewarded them for even coming last. They are trophy kids; therefore, they have similar expectations at the workplace from their leaders. According to Miller (2019), recent research on the millennial generation by DaVinci Payments indicated that 79% of employees look for increased work recognition and are more loyal to the organisation when offered.

4.5.2.1 Theme 2: Feedback and Review Process

The first theme revealed that getting recognition for hard work and dedication is one factor that promotes millennial employee engagement. This theme explores the perspectives on the feedback mechanism in their respective firms and how the employee review process and feedback process can be improved.

Figure 17

4.5.2.1.1 Feedback Mechanism

Participants revealed in the interviews that their respective department's management often gives them feedback whenever they deliver a project or task. The medium of exchange used for receiving and giving feedback include.

- Feedbacks come only through word of mouth.
- Feedback comes in gestures and expressions.
- Meetings (interdepartmental and one to one meeting where the manager meets with the staff individually).

Some of the participants' responses are as below:

E5:

Feedback is usually given in the form of gratitude. They don't usually express themselves in words, but we can see in the form of their expression or pat on the shoulder.

E6:

We do receive feedback from our managers. Whenever you do well, then the manager does offer us an appraisal. Mainly wordily but that is what about it.

E10: *We are allowed to raise any concern in our meetings and go directly to the manager to raise any ongoing concern and discuss with them.*

Tulgan (2009) research findings also suggested that organisations are not used to providing frequent feedback to their employees and are more used to appreciating employees through gratitude and words of a job well done. Tulagn (2009) suggested that organisations recruiting millennials further agreed and re-suggested by Alsop (2008) that more feedback should be provided, especially to the millennial generation. As highlighted earlier, millennials are trophy kids and expect more frequent feedback.

Narayanan (2014) study also indicated similarly and suggested that millennials have a different outlook on feedback. They expect frequent feedback compared to other generations and expect appraisal more than mere words of a job well done. Furthermore, the participants revealed that they only get feedback whenever they make mistakes. In contrast, a significant section of the participants highlighted that the management of their respective firms does not avail them the opportunity for feedback. One participant stated:

E9:*He definitely allows us to give feedback. But whether those changes happen or not is a different question.*

Consequently, firms need to evaluate their feedback mechanism to promote retention in their respective firms. A recent study by Gallup (2020) also indicated similar findings that only 19% of millennials reported receiving routine feedback. However, 17% only agreed to be receiving meaningful feedback at work. They still reported routine feedback as better than nothing but expected more meaningful feedback, which will help them improve, learn, and grow as individuals, and be more productive.

4.5.2.1.2 How leadership handles feedback

The participants highlighted that giving and getting feedback from their employers gives them a feeling of inclusion and a certain level of responsibility. The management improves based on the gathered feedback. However, some of the participants highlighted that the management of the firms pay little or no attention to the feedback

they get from them. The management is often in the habit of not meticulously studying the feedback to understand the needs and requirements of the employees.

E2:

The thing is that leadership does not understand the need for our requirements and our needs. They do not have a proper approach to our feedback. Like for example, I am the IT person and if the IT person tries to explain something to the account's person, he won't get the things. Same way if the accountant explains something to me as an IT person, I won't understand his needs or feedback properly.

Hernandaz (2015) also indicated that millennials want more detailed feedbacks and expect open dialogue within the review process. This was further agreed and suggested by another study in Hearn (2017) that millennials prefer detailed feedback, unlike other generation. They prefer to know exactly where they are going right and wrong so that they can improve themselves. They not only want to receive feedback but also prefer to give their opinion and ideas to managers. Buckeley *et al.*(2017) also pointed out that in detail feedback should be kept in place for millennials as they prefer open communication and want their creative ideas to be heard. Therefore, they like to have open dialogue feedback.

A recent study by Paukert *et al.* (2021) also demonstrated that millennials desire meaningful work and feedback, allowing a constant dialogue with managers and appreciations. In addition, they look for continuous opportunities and work-life balance with access to effective coaching, mentoring and career progression.

4.5.2.1.3 Improving Recognition for Hard Work

As earlier established, millennial employees get the significant motivation to continuously work hard and stay engaged with the firm when their hard work and dedication is recognized and appreciated. Participants opined that firms' leadership could appreciate quality work by giving the hardworking staff bonuses and rewards in the form of holidays, vacations, salary increases, and incentives during festive periods.

E5: *Different type of bonus and rewards to show their appreciation for a job well done. Small gestures of gift at the time of festive period.*

E10: *By giving more bonuses and rewards really or maybe some extra days off as an appreciation for working hard.*

As indicated by Tulgan (2009) study, millennials look for more prompt rewards in the form of promotion or recognition. However, at the same time, some millennials might look for financial rewards. Developing an effective pay strategy is very important for managers as the inability to do so can result in millennials losing interest in jobs and leaving the company. As highlighted earlier, millennials are trophy kids. They like to be rewarded frequently, whether it be financial or non-financial.

Cafaro (2021) also pointed out in a recent study and shared similar findings that millennials have a different outlook on rewards and motivation. They look for financial rewards or promotions and rewards to enhance their experience and lifestyle through travelling opportunities, leisure activities, gift cards, etc. On the other hand, as suggested by many authors earlier, the Millennial generation looks for more prompt rewards.

4.5.2.1.4 Improving the Review Process

Participants suggested that the employee reviewing process should be revamped with the following.

- The daily appraisal should be implemented: They suggested that the management implement a system that appraises the works of the employees daily. One participant (E5) indicated that *I would prefer to have a daily appraisal*. Buckley *et al.* (2017) also suggested the same and recommended that millennials should be provided with constant feedback as they grew up like that in their school time. In addition, the author suggested providing millennials with more constant digital feedback as the millennial generation is more technological driven.
- Exhaustive feedback of products/service review: The firms' leadership should always give a thorough and expressive review of the service rendered or product selected after evaluation. This will enable the employee to identify the areas that need adjustments and make modifications accordingly. When asked about the employee review process, one interviewee (E10) suggested that:

I would prefer to have more one to one in detail meetings where we discuss more in detail about how we are progressing and how we can really improve. We do get feedback, but they are not in detail. They do inform us where we have gone wrong, but they don't discuss it in more detail.

Hearn (2017) and Gallup (2020) study also suggested that in-depth feedback should be given to millennials highlighting both positive and negative aspects to individuals. It will help them know exactly where they are going wrong and where they need to improve further.

- Frequent team meetings: Team meetings and interdepartmental meetings allow team members, managers, and senior staff to exchange information and indirectly review the employee's work.

E6:

In the review process I think it can be better if there are more one to one meeting, team meeting and other managers as it would allow to have more better communication with all departments. It will also allow managers to have better understanding on what each employees requires.

Consequently, the participants are seeking more meetings to enable easy knowledge sharing. Greenberg and Weber (2008) also agreed with it and highlighted that millennial prefer to work in a team and contribute as a whole team. Tolbzie (2008) recognized millennials as a generation which are more wired together and acknowledge teamwork. To manage millennials, effective leadership needs to be put in place with strong teamwork concept skills to drive them to be more productive. Grey (2018) study suggested similar outcomes regarding millennials working more effectively when working in a team.

- One to one meeting with managers: One to one meeting enables the employee to give employees a sense of privacy and closure. This enables them to divulge more information to the manager, and the manager will appraise the employee immediately. One to one meeting gives more details.

E9 suggested: *There are some mistakes or review which you should give in front of everyone so that others can learn from it. However, there are also some*

feedbacks that should be done or said behind closed doors. So, that's one thing I would definitely like to improve.

As suggested by Hearn (2017), in detail, feedback is necessary for millennials. Therefore, it becomes essential for managers to have one-to-one meetings put in place for discussion to be done privately with each individual to discuss the progress.

- Improving the training matrix for skill development: This involves implementing a system that highlights the professional and personal development journeys of individual employees.

E1 suggested that:

Review of the training matrix ensure a steady progression. I think by doing so, everyone will have a better idea of how they are progressing personally and what more skills are required to be improved or developed.

The HBR article by Rikleem (2020) shared a similar opinion and highlighted that the current pandemic worldwide forces organisations to consider their training matrix. In addition, millennials and now Generation Z face disruption in their education due to their course being converted into an online format. Therefore, organisations should start building the transition process more clearly and less disoriented, especially for the next generations, to avoid confusion when they join the workforce.

To maximize the opportunity for a successful mentorship program, employers should ensure managers understand the benefits of strengthened intergenerational relationships, dispel negative perceptions that could weaken engagement, and provide the needed time and resources.

Reverse mentoring was suggested as one of the means to improve the training matrix with mutually supportive relationships.

- Performance-based evaluation: Recognition and appreciation for hard work should be strictly based on the performance evaluation report, and this should be conducted at regular intervals.

E4:

Most of the companies give bonuses and keep performance indicators. Like for instance, who is doing better will get more bonus. It is all based on your performance, so I think performance-based evaluation would be good and the bonuses.

Perna (2021) in Forbes also suggested that:

If we've learned anything from 2020, Continuous learning is no longer just a stopgap to cope with the rapid changes overtaking the workplace; rather, it is fast becoming the resting pulse of companies embracing the new reality of work.

Authors like Burnes (2004), Marshak (2006) and Mann and Harter (2016) have been seen reinforcing the need to have effective performance management in the organisation. Many organizations fail due to ineffective performance management strategies in place as they tend to be using one strategy for all of their employees. However, this is no longer possible, and more individual-based performance evaluation and engagement must be set to ensure employees are engaged and motivated as individuals. This is because millennials have different expectations than previous generations and want their personal goals and professional career growth to be fulfilled at work through frequent appraisal and progressions.

4.5.3.1 Theme 3: Communication and Information Sharing

The theme is assessing the sufficiency of the strategies used for disseminating information. In addition, it is seeking the participants' perspective on how information sharing can be improved in an office setting.

Figure 18

4.5.3.1.1 Strategies used for Information Dissemination (Communication)

The responses of the participants point to the fact that the current information mechanism is inadequate. For example, participants explained that the current mechanism allows for little or no inter-departmental communication within the office. As a result, the information shared by the management is often inadequate, and the goals and objectives of the firm on projects are not always clearly defined.

E10: *I think more communication between different departments. There is good communication currently, but I still feel it is not enough.*

E5: *More communication between the department and another department.*

E4: *They do, but it is always unclear what they are after. They don't specific objective probably I think because they are still growing.*

E7: *There is no particular goal they tell me, so I tend to make my personal goals and challenges every day to just make my work a little more interesting for myself.*

The only identified method for information dissemination is through meetings, weekly meetings, and monthly meetings between employees and supervisors. Meetings are also organized for inter-departmental attendance, albeit it is largely inadequate. Gavatorra (2012) also highlighted the importance of communication and suggested it is critical to build trust and build common ground and focus among employees' organisations.

Millennials tend to get bored if the process is systematic, complex, and slow. Simmons (2015) and Myers and Sadaghiani (2010) also considered effective communication as an important factor to retain millennials. They prefer to have frequent communication to keep them aware of the changes, issues etc. Lack of transparency is one of the concerns raised by the millennial generation (Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010 and Hassel, 2018).

Myers and Sadaghiani (2010) further agreed with the findings. They suggested that organisations should have more open communication throughout the organisation as millennials prefer to be kept in the loop and be aware of the happenings around the organisation than just their department. In addition to that, by being aware of the other department, individuals like millennials tend to feel part of the success and failure and get more involved in improving the whole process. Millennials have been raised getting advice from friends and family. They expect the same in professional lives and tend to have good relationships with their colleagues and bond together to work as a whole, unlike the generations before them.

4.5.3.1.2 Improving the Information Dissemination (Communication) Process

The millennial employees feel that the dissemination of the information regarding the firms is extremely essential with the help of which the young employees are able to know about the jobs. The collection of information regarding jobs is easier for the millennial when they are available on social media (Samia, 2021). Considering the extent to which millennials use social media in their routine lives, it is important for employers to use the platforms to engage with current and prospective employees. The organizations which are unable to make their presence visible on social media are unable to gain a certain amount of prominence on it, hence improving their ability to communicate with current and prospective employees (Lu & Dillahunt, 2021).

When asked about how an organisation can improve itself, one respondent (**E3**) suggested that clearer objectives to have a clear idea of *what we are working towards*.

Also, participants believe that organizing social/outdoor events for the employees will significantly improve communication and foster positive relationships, hence improving the information dissemination mechanism between departments.

E1:

Planning more events and activities and strengthening connections between all the staff members in each department. I think communication between each department is necessary to ensure smooth running.

Communication is an important aspect that the participants highlighted. In many organizations, younger employees are unable to communicate effectively with leaders and managers during routine interactions as most of the upper-level employees are out of their age group (Lu & Dillahunt, 2021). It is conceivable that age differences between employees can contribute to miscommunication (Lu & Dillahunt, 2021). Millennials and other younger generations of workers tend to be more comfortable working in organizations where their generations are well represented among the workforce (Spranger & Chen, 2019). There is requirement for more meet ups and meetings for creating better communication with each other. The youth employees often face generation gap in their workplace for the purpose of which they often leave their jobs. The other employees who are older than them are unable to give them company and there is a problem of understanding.

E1: *Hold more frequent meetings with floor staff, team leaders and managers.*

E6: *I think they can improve by having more frequent meetings at work so both employees and management can put the perspective more clearly.*

Jansson and Tuuainen (2016) suggested that organisations should change their communication process to be more social media based as millennials are attached to technology, especially social media. Forming a group for discussion on social media will allow clear and speed up communication. Hoover *et al.* (2016) also agreed and shared similar opinions and suggested that organisations should have more fast-processing communication set up within the organisation.

As suggested here, the organizations may make their procedure of communication based on the social media. This may make the youth population more interested in the organizational communication (Chitra, 2021). Many young workers leave their organizations due to the lack of interest in organizational communication. With this in mind, it is conceivable that improving organizational communication can provide a greater incentive for younger workers to remain with their employers. The organization focus thus may remain in the social media communication with the help of which the

organizations are able to reach out to the youth. The youth want the communication to be more fast with the help of which they will be able to save a lot of time. Thus a focus on these aspects may pull the youth population towards the organization. Generation gap is also an issue which needs to be addressed in this context. The millennial often do not find interest in working in organizations which have too many older people working in it as communication does not occur among them in that level (Spranger & Chen, 2019).

4.5.4.1 Theme 4: Promoting Employee Dedication

The theme explores the factors that increase millennial employees' dedication and the factors limiting their performance on the job. This will provide a clear-cut path to how these factors can be addressed.

4.5.4.1.1 Motivating Factors

The employees reveal that they are motivated and more dedicated to their work if they are provided with excellent pay and learning opportunities. In addition, for some respondents, words of appreciation and encouragement from their managers will significantly increase their dedication and hard work.

E2: *A good pay scales. That is the only thing that drives me to work beyond my expectation.*

E10:

Appraisal I will say. Appraisal from manager for doing a good job motivates me to work even hard. E10 further added Also, sometimes a good learning and development opportunities encourage me to go beyond expectations.

The job role of the youth population needs to be very attractive with the help of which the population will be get attracted towards the job. An attractive job role can attract an employees to achieve it. In case of the existing organizations, they are unable to create a job role that is worthy. This is the main reason why the young employees do not feel interested (Anggraeni, 2018). In the present times the youth population has many desires for the purpose of which they desire to make the things better. When they do not get the desired things from their jobs, they do not get interested in it. There also remains a personal goal for the purpose of which the population keeps moving towards

better jobs. The lack of salary hike of the millennial is a reason for the purpose of which they keep on leaving the jobs and changing the organization. The participants have mostly left their job due to the lack of pay rise. On the other hand, the older managers have not left so many jobs as the millennial. This revelation reiterates the assertion that millennial workers are likelier to be driven by short-term goals like pay, and tend to leave their organizations if they feel that their short-term prospects are not being met sufficiently (Spranger & Chen, 2019). Therefore, organizations that seek to retain their millennial employees should consider attending to the needs that the generation of workers prioritize, such as remuneration (Spranger & Chen, 2019).

E8: *Because it would meet my personal goal in life. I don't need a lot of motivation to go beyond the expectation as it's just what I want to do.*

E9: *To be fair sometimes I think it is the customers. Sometimes you get nice customers who just want you to do better and to put a smile on their face.*

Organizations often offer different types of rewards to the employees for the purpose of which they get attracted to work in a certain organization. The organizations which have this type of system of rewards are more likely to get more young employees in their organizations (Rather, 2018). The people who do not have the tendency to receive rewards would not get interested. The millennials are more interested in awards and rewards as these interest them. The organization has been able to create a better atmosphere with the help of these rewards. The employee appraisal is the most important part of this which is affected by this.

Most of the millennial prefer better progress in their career with the help of which they will be able to move far. Thus, the organizations which provide better career progression are able to create a better condition for the millennial. Their preferences often do not get fulfilled for the purpose of which they get affected. The organizations which are able to give better training for future are more likely to get millennial support.

Another recent research done by Macpherson (2021) indicated a gap between meeting the millennials motivational needs. He suggested that organisations must take actions; otherwise, this negative trend due to gaps can expose organisations to a greater risk of failing. He further pointed out millennials as key performers in organisations in today's

world and considered them to have a trait of willingness to be successful. He recommended organisations to deep dive review their motivational strategy and suggested that they should explore improvement opportunities. Macpherson (2021) also indicated in his research that motivating millennial will have a big influence on organisation performance and reinforced organisations to facilitate the motivational needs of millennials for future success.

4.5.4.1.2 Demotivating Factors

Excess workload and inadequate training are two of the leading factors that discourage the dedication of millennial employees. They get discouraged when they are assigned tasks that exceed the scope of their training and knowledge. When they are made to handle excess workload due to staff shortage, excess workload increases stress and stress, ultimately provoking a reduction in their level of productivity.

E7:

Sometimes, I think I am doing too much alone. So sometimes doing too much alone make it very difficult to complete all the task. I would also blame my procrastination on this.

Furthermore, unhealthy competition amongst the employees may hinder their ability to put in their 100% in their given job role. This is mainly because their attention would be on limiting the success of their colleagues and not on delivering quality work. Hence, the inability of the management to provide the employees with what they need to function optimally within the organization.

E2:

Well, there are many obstacles Ahhh! One is the management as they don't understand the needs of the employee, and this is the main reason. If they would understand the need, they would do everything accordingly. Like we would get proper support to do our job.

Garrad and Chamorro-Premuzic (2016) also suggested that motivated employees will mean nothing if there is no healthy competition for workers. Millennials prefer healthy competition; however, at the same time, they do not want the organization to instill cutthroat competition within the organization as suggested by Greenberg and Weber

(2008). Millennials prefer to work as a team together and were raised in making contributions as a whole.

Ineffective engagement and communication have been significant issues reported by many authors like Mann and Harter (2016). On the other side, many authors have been significantly suggesting that organisations to improve their engagement and communication strategy, especially for millennials. When they feel they are not being treated right or their needs and voices are not being heard, they will likely leave the organisation. Even if they decide to stay, their productivity level will not be as good, ultimately resulting in organisations' goals not being achieved (Mazzeiet *al.* 2016, Stephens, 2020). Only by engaging effectively managers will be able to understand their employees' needs and satisfy them.

4.5.5.1 Theme 5: The Difference Between Old and New Generation Employees

Millennials are more creative when relatively compared to older generations, but they are not as consistent and dependable as older generations. As a result, the millennials are short-tempered, and the older generations often see themselves as superior to millennial employees; this inevitably creates a divide in the company. The management fixed the conflict occurring between the two generations by promoting millennials to management positions.

- The newer generation is more creative.
- The newer generation are short-tempered.
- The older generation is more consistent.
- Older people think they are superiors.

Authors like Lynch (2008) and Moss (2016) also highlighted the differences between generations and considered millennials more creative and the most different generation due to the difference in outlook. Millennials were recognized to be more social and technological driven. Moss (2016) highlighted the difference between generations and re-enforced management to consider their current strategies.

Conclusively, the analysis reveals that the training is an effective tool capable of motivating and demoting an employee; hence, firms must prioritize employee training. A department or an individual should be responsible for employee training. The

analysis also reveals that millennial employees prioritize professional and career development over remuneration. Some are seeking employment opportunities in bigger firms mainly because they offer career development opportunities. Firms seeking to retain millennial employees must access career development experts who can guide and counsel them in their chosen field.

Millennial employees are naturally technological; they all highlighted that the current system used in their place of work is archaic. Therefore, they call for the adoption of the modern system, an upgrade that conforms to the modern technological standard in their work process.

E10: *As I said earlier, I feel like we are lacking slightly behind in terms of hardware and software we use. So, a bit more up to date in advancement in technology will be good.*

Communication was highlighted as an inadequate factor that hinders employee engagement, especially in communicating the firm's goals and objectives. Employees suggest that firms must prioritize effective communication. There should also be an increase in interdepartmental communication; this can be achieved by organising indoor and outdoor meetings and events. The frequency of these meetings (including one to one) should also be increased.

Participants believe that the employee of the year award is a work recognition award that promotes hard work and diligence amongst employees. However, one of the participants highlighted that award only create unhealthy competition amongst employees. Millennial employees believe their job should provide them with health care benefits and provide them with wages that match their potential and value; some participants believe they are underpaid. They believe a salary increase will provoke an increase in their level of engagement. Repairing damaged infrastructure in the office environment is also an action that can increase millennial employee engagement. The firms should also implement structures that make hardworking employees visible, allowing easy identification and appreciation. Finally, the process of excess workload can be solved by employing and training more people.

As highlighted in the literature review, authors like Geyer (2016) were seen to be criticizing millennials as egoistic and short-tempered generations. On the other hand, authors like Grey (2018) encouraged and embraced millennial generations and

considered them critical for future success. Gavtorta (2012) also suggested open communication to build common ground with the millennial generation.

4.6

Management Data Analysis

Figure 19

4.6.1 Theme 1: Understanding the difference between Millennial Employees and Others

The analysis reveals that managers have a solid understanding and characterization of millennial employees. They reveal that millennial employees are more adaptive and creative than older employees. They are complex but have an embedded ability to adjust to change with ease.

M1 indicated that: *Oh well, they are very well complex, but one thing they have in common is they are very creative.*

Tolbzie (2008) also revealed in his study the differences between the generations and highlighted the attitude and outlook of each generation. He considered the millennial generation to be more socially formed and believe in working and making a difference together as a whole than as an individual. Hewlett *et al.* (2009) and Grey's (2018) studies also revealed similar findings and considered millennials as creative, responsible and more solution-oriented generations.

In addition, the authors considered millennials as confident and optimistic generations. Managers stressed that millennials are fast learners with a perpetual hunger for knowledge consumption. This inherently makes them more knowledgeable on average than older employees, largely because of their understanding and access to the internet. In addition, they are technologically driven, and they understand social media more than the older employees. This means they understand a faster way of communication than older employees.

One of the respondents, **M4**, stated that:

They are quick learners, to be honest. However, I do find them quite hasty at a time. They look for quick progression opportunities and get bored easily if you do not manage them carefully.

Hoover *et al.* (2016) also shared a similar opinion and stated that millennials are quick learners and complexity avoiders. Hoover *et al.* (2016) considered millennials to be quick solution seekers as they are technology-driven and tend to be impatient and look for quick solutions through Google, etc. The authors further agreed with the findings of faster communication by stating that millennials do not like complex and business communication procedures and tend to leave the organization where they find the system and procedures too complex.

The managers explained that millennials have a low attention span, and they generally have the habit of not staying with firms in the long term. Also, they thrive when given some liberty and flexibility in their job role; this is partly because they sometimes complete projects using methods outside the recommended zone and work better when allowed some time flexibility.

M3:

Yeah, I mean, if you take most of the workforces now are depending on the job at hand. They work flexible hours; they tend to work from home more now than ever before, especially with the virus going on. Which in turn proves the point that they can work from home.

Moss (2016) also shared a similar opinion and suggested that organizations should have more flexibility at their workplaces. They suggested that millennials tend to perform

better when offered empowerment and flexibility. In addition, when millennials are offered flexibility, they tend to stay loyal and longer within the organisations than those who do not.

4.6.2 Theme 2: Recruitment and Retention

Participants highlighted that recruiting millennials is a daunting and complex endeavour. They highlighted that they prioritize attitude over educational and professional qualification. They believe that recruiting millennials based on educational qualification alone is a dangerous act that can jeopardise any company's operations. Hence, selecting an individual who enjoys teamwork, who is willing to work and whose goals align with the organisation's goals is more important than qualifications. This, however, does not negate the importance of qualifications.

M3 suggested: Recruitment wise is experience, more relevant attitude and the attitude of individuals are more important. People with a can-do attitude as opposed to not my job, someone with the right attitude and right approach to what job need to be done. I would prefer an individual with the right attitude and approach over a degree.

This finding agrees with CIPD's (2018) statement, where they suggest that organizations should focus on having good recruitment and reinforced organizations to have clear ideas on the relevant skills and abilities required. Harvard business study research (2017) also suggested similar findings and stated that a rise in need of education qualification requirement in the job posting was seen. However, at the same time, their study revealed that having a person with a degree will not certainly result in or guarantee that a person has the right skills or abilities to do the job better than the candidate with no degree. Therefore, they suggested organizations focus on the abilities and qualifications both, as suggested in the findings.

Employee retention is difficult with millennial employees; some managers believe it is impossible to retain millennial employees. One way of retaining a millennial is to keep close tabs with the employee after leaving the company and offer them appointments whenever they seek to move away from their new firm.

M3 suggested that:

Once every 4-6 months for a coffee or a bite to eat. If they are smart enough, they will come back to you after they got bored of the other job after few years, which means they will be coming back with more experience and more relevance than before they left you so really depends on how you are looking at the people that are leaving.

As identified by authors like White (2016) and SHRM (2016) surveys, organizations are constantly facing employee retention issue, especially millennials. Hanrahan (2021) also agreed with the finding and suggested that organizations should have an honesty and trust culture. Her article also heightened that 41% of millennials tend to leave/switch to different jobs in the period of 2 years. However, just as the current finding suggested, she also reaffirms that organisations should create a valuable and long-term culture with them regardless of which they can grow within and feel like a part of it. She also suggested that organizations should keep in touch with them even after leaving and suggested inviting them consistently to company events. Employing fresh graduates and giving the employees a level of liberty and flexibility also promotes employee retention. The managers further highlighted that recognizing and rewarding hard-working millennials will increase a firm's rate of retention.

M3:

I think the earlier you can recruit them from university or college, the greater the chance is that you would keep them longer with you. Because once they are gone to 2-3 employers, they have already been indoctrinated by another way of thinking, another way of doing so, it becomes much more difficult to try and get them to do what you require them to do.

Putter (2019) also shared a similar opinion to findings and suggested in one of his articles in Forbes that organizations, instead of focusing too much on millennials' expectations and retention, should focus more on what they can learn from the millennial's generation. They should focus more on utilising their skills and learning from them to improve overall organisations. Instead of focusing too much on employees' experience, they should focus on growing and developing them. Many organisations struggled to retain employees because of their inability to understand them and have too much expectation. Many studies have shown millennials' tendency to leave the organisation within a year or two.

However, they have not realized the importance of creating a valuable culture within the organisation. As highlighted and suggested by Hanrahan (2012) earlier, organisations should create a culture and provide their employees with an opportunity to network even after they leave their organisation. This is because millennial generations are recognized to be very social in nature and prefer to have more networking in their lifestyle and tend towards their loyalty and attraction for them to come back to the organisation.

4.6.3 Theme 3: Training and Support Philosophy

Participants explained that while it is essential to invest in the professional development of their millennial employees, it is one of the riskiest investments to ever undertake. This is because millennial employees are not always committed to a firm on a long-term basis; they are likely to leave the firm after gaining professional knowledge.

M3:

I think there are too many organizations that are not prepared to train employees, they are not willing to invest in them. My argument is why have employees if you are not prepared to invest in them. Most people I think they do not invest in because what if they learn all these skills for them and they leave. I always say would you rather have uneducated employees that are not going anywhere and stuck with you them employees with skills and may leave.

A recent study by Anderson in Linekdin (2020) pointed out that regardless of most of the research, which indicates that millennials tend to leave work within a year or two, organisations should focus on developing their employees' skills, especially for millennials retention. His research further indicated that millennials are frequently scrambling about paying their mortgages and student loans, so when provided with good culture and developing opportunities, they tend to stay with an organisation for a longer period—especially considering the catastrophic economy caused by the pandemic issue COVID. Therefore, organizations should fully utilize their employees in such a pandemic and should offer more flexibility and developing opportunities. This is because pandemics have dramatically changed millennials' outlook as they prefer to

stay employed within an organisation for a longer period if they are offered effective training, development, and career progression opportunities (Rikleem, 2020).

Deloitte (2020) recent study also indicated similarly and pointed out that pandemics have a dramatic impact on millennials' loyalty. Their research indicated that more millennials reported staying within the organisation for at least five years if provided with flexibility, training, and training developing opportunities. Training should be provided to employees struggling to function in their role, and adequate welfare is provided for those with personal problems; employees whose skills are no longer needed or those whose skills are inadequate for the job role are discarded.

M1:

Well, in our organization, we have consultant in place to deal with struggling employees. They provide them support including their personal life and with their career and that include providing them with appropriate training.

M3:

In all fairness, if somebody is struggling because they haven't got the ability, then you are far better than letting them go. But if someone has got the ability but struggling and you can see the potential then obviously give them the support, they need in order to achieve the result you require.

M4:

As I said, I evaluate each of my employee's performance on a weekly basis. If I see any employee struggling or doing less than usual, I always try to go and speak to them to see if they need any support or further assistance.

The managers highlighted that they understand the importance of training, and they have implemented different training options.

- Field training
- Online training
- Seminars and workshops

These findings were similar to a current study done by Vodaphone (2021), which highlighted that as millennials are digital natives and social in nature, companies should offer them more online and event training. Especially considering the current pandemic COVID-19 situation, companies like Vodaphone have been encouraging more digital platforms for training their employees. Their research indicated that 67 % of the young generation reported not receiving sufficient career advice and opportunities. Therefore, to support their employees and society as a whole, they create a new range of online education programs and training support for their employees to cope up with digital skills and learning, especially in the COVID-19 period, where workplaces have been impacted significantly and have adjusted dramatically to a more digital economy.

4.6.4 Theme 4: Communication Strategy

The managers also believe that communication between managers and employees defines the success and failure of any endeavour, and communication helps build trust. The goal statement and vision of the firm must be well defined, and it must appeal to the employees. Other strategies for communication include.

- Monthly meetings
- One to one meeting

M4:

Communication is the key, really. You just need to listen to them and build a friendly relationship with them so that they can talk freely about issues. That's why I try to have lunch with them when possible and chat with them as much as possible.

As highlighted significantly by Gavatorra (2012) in the literature review, communication is critical to building understanding, loyalty, and common ground for millennials. As highlighted by many authors (Spiegel, 2011; Narayanan, 2014), millennials seek continuous feedback and communication opportunities in the form of managers giving them feedback and providing their managers with the feedback. They want to be kept updated with their progress and want their opinion to be heard and encouraged at the same time (Buckeley *et al.*, 2017 and Myers and Sadigiani, 2010).

4.6.5 Theme 5: Employee Evaluation and Performance Monitoring

Employee evaluation and performance monitoring are necessary for keeping track of career development and employee engagement. The managers highlighted that they give the employees weekly targets and appraise them at the end of each week. Those who delivered top-quality work are recognized and rewarded. Furthermore, the software was implemented to track employee performance; the outcome of the software evaluation is often used to identify the areas of strengths and weaknesses of employees. This allows them to maximize the employee's potential to benefit the firm by assigning roles based on their areas of strengths.

M3:

There are numerous aptitude tests like the BRIGGS test. Most companies don't bother going through that. I always run people through the test that gives me an indication of whether they are manual workers or thinkers and doers. What proportion in that and then evaluate. If I got the right person in the right job.

M4:

We have software in place to see how each employee is performing and how much work they have done every week. In addition to that, I try to go and see them for a quick chat now and then to see how they are progressing.

Employee evaluation and feedback are critical for millennials (Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010; Hassel, 2018). They want to be kept in the loop and want to know what they are doing right and where they are going wrong. They want clear communication with how they are progressing and prefer to be up to date with progression as a source of motivation. As highlighted on several occasions, career progression is critical for millennials and actively looks for their progression level. Belle (2016) also shared similar opinions and pointed out that millennials expect their manager or leaders to set a performance bar for them.

As the millennial generation is digitally native and driven, organizations need to use digital platforms to continuously indicate their progress. This is especially essential in the current pandemic situation where the economy is being driven significantly digitally. Actively monitoring them will allow managers to keep track of their

employees and will allow them to engage effectively with their employees. In addition to that, they will be able to see any struggling and disengaged employees and will be able to provide them with the effective training and support they need at the right time (Belle, 2016).

In addition to that, it is very important to have for leaders and managers to provide their employees with clear guidelines on bonuses and promotions opportunities. A study by the Robertwalter group (2020) also suggested that 71% of millennials expect clear guidelines from their employers, and only 40% of millennials reported being informed of those guidelines. Participants highlighted that performance evaluation is optimized through the following actions.

- Employing only people with the necessary skills

M3:

It is having the people around you with necessary skills. Lot of employer's fear bringing in people who know more than themselves. They fear they might lose their job, or they might steal their business away. My own way of thinking is that it is important you bring that are far more knowledgeable than yourself. People who are going to elevate your business to the next level. What you don't want to be doing is bringing people that you are teaching. If you are bringing people that are smarter than you then you should be learning from them.

- OKRs can be used to measure employee performance.

M3:

One of the things that I have recently started adopting is that the OKR. So, if you do a bit of research on OKRs, which is objective and key results, so goals are generally very broad. It is then defining the objective and creating the set of key results which are related to that specific objective you are trying to achieve. By sharing that with everyone at workplace through various software which are available now a days, organisation can see how everyone is progressing toward those key results in different department. Everyone from top down will be able to share and will be able to see who is stuck in what so you can help and support them.

Conclusively, the analysis revealed that managers understand the millennials generation well and understand their different outlook and requirements of flexible working style. The manager revealed recruitment as a complex process and advised other managers to place in a wise recruitment process with correct job fit requirements to ensure correct attitude and skills individuals are hired, consequently reducing turnover. They believe unfit recruitment can be dangerous to the organization and can hinder the organization's overall process. The manager also revealed that the retention of millennials is one of the issues they faced. However, they believe that offering flexibility, autonomy, and financial rewards tend to reduce employee turnover.

Almost all managers revealed training and development as an essential investment, especially for millennial employees. However, at the same time, they reveal the risk involved with it especially considering the millennial 'job hopping' attitude. Communication was also revealed as an important factor for building a relationship with employees. They believed that ineffective communication of goals and objective have an impact on employees, especially millennials.

Lastly, they revealed that employee evaluation is necessary for effectively managing the performance of their employees. They suggested software like OKR for effective employee performance monitoring, especially millennials, and suggested aptitude tests like Briggs to be implemented to effectively evaluate employee's performance.

4.7 Summary

Chapter 4 consists of the findings and analysis of the study. This chapter provides a comprehensive exploration of the engagement and management performance experience of 14 participants (10 employees and 4 managers) in the UK e-retail (SMEs) industry. QSR thematic analysis approach was used to extract meaning and interpret data collected from 14 participants. Themes were represented using four stages of thematic analysis. They were organised using Attride-Stirling's (2001) thematic network approach. 25 themes were identified, out of which 10 were key themes (5 employees and 5 managers), and 15 were subthemes. All themes' findings were analysed, discussed, and reviewed using the existing literature content collected in Chapter 1.

5.

Chapter 5

Conclusion, Recommendation, and Suggestion for Further Research

5.1

Introduction

Chapter 5 is the last chapter of this thesis. The current study so far collected, reviewed, and analysed the theoretical literature related to the study. The findings were discussed in the later chapters to gain current and practical knowledge for the field study. This chapter primarily focuses on highlighting the contribution, significance, implications, limitations, and suggestions for future research in the field. Firstly, conclusion and recommendation will be discussed. The second section will discuss and highlight the contribution of the study. Thirdly, some implication for the managers will be offered in this chapter. Lastly, the limitation and strengths of the study will be discussed alongside some guidelines for future research. Reflection will also be briefly discussed at the end of this chapter.

The study was chosen in the light of the millennial's retention issue, which has significantly risen in the past few years due to an ineffective approach to engagement with employees and has been perceived to affect the overall organization performance. As a millennial researcher, I believe this study will contribute to the development of the HR (Human Resources) system by identifying the areas of need that must be changed/updated to enhance the commitment and performance level of the employees (millennials) within the organisation especially after the global pandemic.

A qualitative research method has been employed to unveil some of the research findings to identify those areas in-depth. Existing knowledge on HR and the millennials generation was analysed to understand the background on the commitment and performance issues, consequently revealing the lack of managerial understanding of millennials as the root of engagement, retention, and performance problems. Research conducted was limited to two e-retail organisations in Birmingham. Two of the same

businesses (online watch companies) were chosen to ensure effective and comparable results. All these processes helped gain insight into some of the research questions of the current study: “how an organization can improve its employee engagement and management performance strategy to enhance millennial retention and commitment.”

5.2 Conclusion and Suggestions

The study was undertaken with consideration for several factors. First, the study focused on studying how the increase in millennials impacts organisation current employee engagement and performance management. Second, the study explored how successfully or unsuccessfully the organizations in question were utilizing their millennial workforces. Millennials have attracted the attention of many authors like Ng *et al.* (2010), DeVaney (2015), and Liu *et al.* (2019) and how dramatically they are changing the current work due to differences in perspectives and expectations, even more after COVID-19, consequently facing retention issues by managers worldwide.

The findings of the research focus on the e-retail sector and its millennial employees, and the resultant discussion and conclusion likewise apply mostly to millennial workers. The current study indicates that some organisations are not so concerned about needs and expectations of the employees, which leads to poor job satisfaction. A major number of employees prefer to leave the company when they find that their efforts are not being recognised by the company properly. Owing to this revelation, companies need to give high importance to the needs of the employees in order to keep the millennial workers satisfied and to retain them in their organizations for longer.

However, a lack of research has been in the context of SMEs (e-retail sector) in UK to date. Previous research has primarily focused on industries like, hospitality, Facebook and Google context (large organizations), but little or no research has been conducted in the context of SME’s (Umoh, 2017). Thus, this study is undertaken to fill the gap and fulfil the need to better understand retention, engagement, and management performance through SMEs where resources and time are limited. Second, considering the growing number of SMEs in the UK further signifies the importance of research especially considering the current pandemic crisis and fill the gap of no existing knowledge or research undertaken in the dramatically growing SMEs in the UK economy (Rhodes, 2017; UK Export Finance *et al.*, 2017).

Thirdly, the E-retail industry (SME's) increase during the current pandemic crisis further signified researchers' field of study and raised the need even more in identifying the retention concern faced by managers worldwide. Considering these factors, it became apparent to the researcher to conduct the study on millennials considering the growing SMEs in the UK economy and take on the journey to determine the implication of employee engagement and management performance on their retention. Consequently, attaining the need for objectives has led researchers to identify, explore, and gain insight into various HR dimensions in the context of employee engagement, management performance, and different generation perspectives when sourcing and collecting information on the theoretical background of the field study. Furthermore, data collection from the sampling population of 15 in two e-retail SME'S in the UK via qualitative research has led to a more current exploration of the current strategies from both employees and management. Thus, data collected from the sampling population in combination with existing literature was used to address the current study's research question and attain its objectives.

Study objectives addressed are as follows:

- **To identify the issues SMEs faces in retaining millennial in the workplace.**

Firstly, it was significant for the researcher to consider millennials' expectation and motivational factors at the workplace. Thus, the expectations and differences between a set of generations at the workplace were explored and understood. Considering the existing literature and based on the current research findings, expectations were influenced by personal factors. Findings suggest that millennials motivating factors vary for everyone. However, some similarities were inconsistent with some prior studies (Kumar and Govindrajo, 2018). The finding suggested that some of the significant motivational factors for employees are career development opportunities, modern technological adoption system, effective communication, and remuneration.

Almost all the participant highlighted the need for more learning and training with career development opportunities. They were offered some training opportunities, but less of career progression was offered to them. Some participants even revealed that they are willing to leave their current

employment if they were to offer opportunities in larger organizations, which provides more career progression and less structural hierarchy.

Technological advancement need was also indicated by most respondents, especially considering the e-commerce nature of the business. They indicated the need to update technology to make the process faster and smoother.

Almost all of the participants significantly highlighted the communication factor. The participants indicated the need for clearer and more open discussion (two-way communication) with the managers. They also indicated that inadequate communication was made, especially in the context of interdepartmental.

Aggregately, the participants of the study supported the remuneration as well. The majority of participants expressed that they would be very happy to work in an organisation that focus highly on work recognition along with appreciation. The organisation needs to provide quick promotions, extra day off, flexible timing, good salary and many more. On the other hand, other participants has said that they want monetary rewards as well such as increment in salary, bonus and many more according to their job performance. Some existing employees who are working in one company for a long time has said that they would prefer to leave the current company if they get better pay along with remuneration opportunities in some other company. Overall, findings indicated the need to implement a better and more effective structure for millennial retention.

- **To gain knowledge on the current strategy of the SMEs in the e-retail sector in retaining the millennial employees.**

Findings carried out indicated that both e-retails consisted of millennials generations of employees.

Based on the findings collected, it was revealed that career development, training, and communication were the major factors motivating millennial employees. Considering those findings, it was identified that career and development culture with effective leadership should be put in place to engage

effectively with the millennials within the organisation. Developing culture is where organisations shape and guide their employees to grow. This will benefit both managers and employees as employees will be allowed to grow fulfilling their personal needs. Managers can support and guide them to grow in ways needed by an organisation or assist in achieving its aim and objective. This aligns with the existing literature supporting and highlighting that millennials are significantly influenced by the learning and training opportunities they are offered. Reinforcement on career development and its relevance and impact on HR has been highlighted by many authors in the existing literature (Buckley *et al.*, 2016).

Due to limited resources and time, SMEs are less envisaged to incorporate developing culture within the organisation, facilitating employees' career progression values. As evidence suggested, millennials have high expectations from their managers, especially when it comes to career and development advancement opportunities. It is, therefore, suggested and expected that increasing career and development activities would allow organisation to increase its employee's commitment level and satisfaction.

All these factors were also surprisingly highlighted by one of the SME's management participants, which suggested that some SME's managers fear losing their current employees to other organizations that sometimes fails to develop their employees to benefit organisation needs. Instead of focusing on resources and time, a participant suggested that SMEs should focus more on developing and building a positive relationship with their employees. The current study, alongside some of the existing literature, also indicates a positive impact of career and development culture on organisation's retention, engagement, and performance.

From the current study, it has been understood that generally, organisations generally seek to address the needs of their workers, even if this desire is merely dictated by the need to ensure optimal productivity (Anitha & Aruna, 2016). That is why they try their best to keep their employee satisfied by offering their promotion, good salary and many more. They introduce effective leadership in

order to keep their employees motivated and satisfied in their organisation. On the other hand, it has also been observed that some of the organisation are more concerned about the profit of the company rather than employees. These type of companies faced huge issue to retain their employees and build a strong and trustworthy relationship with the employees. They force their employees to work hard without recognising their efforts properly. They use their employees as taken for granted which led them towards poor employee retention.

Finding suggests that a low level of training and development opportunities experienced by the SME employees can lead them to have low motivation, consequently resulting in less engagement within the organisation. SMEs should also understand that organisation that facilitates its employees career development and progression tends to continuously transform itself to meet the dramatically changing need to remain competitive in the market. Thus, indicating that its positive impacts on employees, especially on millennials, weigh more than negative.

In addition to having effective culture within the organisation, findings also suggested that it is important to have effective leadership. Without effective leadership, it is impossible to create and sustain valuable culture within the organisation. Leadership strongly impacts employees, especially millennials, as they look and depend highly on them. To implement employee-driven policies, leaders/managers must have extensive knowledge about the behaviour of the employees. Only by Implementing those policies can managers instill career development support for their employees. Findings indicated the need for better communication and remuneration.

Only effective leaders can create and instill culture within the organisation, which allows all employees to participate and identify hardworking individuals. Furthermore, effective leaders incorporate and develop high-performing culture characteristics by instilling teamwork, trust, and open communication. This further aligns with the existing literature, which indicated these characteristics as major contributors for millennials' retention and engagement within the

organisation (Maiers, 2017; Balda and Mora, 2011 and Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010).

- **To understand the relation between employee engagement and performance management of the millennial employees in the UK SMEs of e-retail sector**

The finding suggested that when managers keep track of their employee career development and engagement, they are likely to evaluate their employees and monitor performance more effectively. The manager participant indicated the interconnection between the two by highlighting and suggesting that when managers actively keep track of their employee's performance, they are likely to be well aware of each employee's strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, when any of their employee's progress weakens, it informs them directly about the disengagement and allows them to provide any necessary support at the right time which may hinder their current employee's performance or debar them from giving their best performance.

Thus, showing that there is an interconnection relationship between employee engagement and management performance. When one is weakened, other dimensions get directly/indirectly impacted by it. Furthermore, the above evidence aligns with the existing literature (Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010; Hassel, 2018). Therefore, managers must ensure that they position effective engagement strategy and effective management performance strategy in place. Similarly, when asked about what drives them to go beyond expectations, employee participants indicated that they are likely to put more effort when their needs are looked upon by managers. Managers are only likely to understand each employee's need and motivating factors when engaging with them effectively. Some employees suggested pay as the motivating factor to go beyond the performance, whereas some indicated work recognition and learning and development opportunities to be the major contributor to their performance. Surprisingly, some employees even revealed a personal passion for being the immense motivator to do better at work. Thus, the necessity for managers to understand and engage effectively with employees to fully utilise them.

- **To understand the performance management strategy of the millennial of the e-retail sector of the SMEs of the UK.**

Communication and continuous feedback were suggested by findings collected by both employees and managers. Almost all the employee participants raised the need for more feedback and clear guidelines of visions and goals. Both can be achieved by having strong leaders in positions with effective communication skills.

As millennials, employee participants highlighted technology advancement as one of the factors of concern. Based on this evidence, organisations should consider updating their communication, feedback, and monitoring performance by positioning and implementing software. This is consistent with the existing literature that suggests that organizations should keep themselves up to date with the advancement of technology to remain competitive in the market.

As millennials are technologically driven, organizations must adopt those technological advancements to complete their skills and abilities. One employee participant suggested organisation consider using WhatsApp as a means of communication. This further indicates that millennials look for faster communication through social platforms to keep them in the loop. This is consistent with existing research, which indicated and encouraged organisations to use the social platform to give instant feedback and speed up the communication process (Hoover *et al.*, 2016; Clarke, 2018).

One of the managerial participants also suggested that organisations should use software like OKR (objective and key results) to monitor and manage employee performance effectively. Using OKR software will allow organizations/leaders to monitor their performance and track any disengaged employees. It will also enable them to communicate goals, objectives, and visions to their employees. Furthermore, software like OKR further assists managers/leaders in rewards and appraisal procedures by recognizing their star employees. Thus, consequently allowing managers to effectively manage their employee's engagement and performance at the same time.

On the other hand, it will also assist employees to have clear guidelines on objectives and targets to work at and keep track of their progress through online platforms. This will assist the organisation in fulfilling the millennial employees' need for continuous progress feedback and recognition at work as their hard work will be seen on the platform by other employees and management thus, ultimately removing the element of unfairness at work. This evidence is consistent with some of the existing documents that highlight organizations like Google using such software to better manage their employees (Sun, 2017).

However, at the same time, it is not suggestible for organisation/leaders to completely rely on those softwares and skip face-to-face meetings. With daily appraisal through platforms, managers should still organize one-to-one and frequent team meetings to discuss important factors and give any personal feedback to each employee. One employee participant indicated their dissatisfaction with the current review process and highlighted that they prefer their managers to discreetly give feedback. This further indicates the need for more one-to-one meetings to better understand and communicate between employees and management.

Frequent team meetings should also be organized through social events to ensure communication between interdepartmental is made effectively. However, considering the current pandemic, organizing social and outdoor events has become difficult. Therefore, managers should arrange frequent team meetings via online platforms like Zoom and arrange some game or quiz activity to encourage more communication between the department and instill understanding between all the organization members.

The above suggestion can only be implemented if strong leaders are in place and have extensive knowledge of their employee behavior and up-to-date technology. This aligns with the existing literature by Spiegel (2011) and Garber (2012). Their inability to use the software can result in ineffective use of software and may consequently result in ineffective performance management. Therefore, leaders with technological advancement skills should be put in place,

or training should be provided to keep them updated with technology. Their inability or lack of understanding of software will not only result in ineffective use of software but as well as ineffective use of resources and time. Similarly, millennials employees are technologically driven; they should be provided with the training on the platform.

- **To explore the interconnection between employee engagement and management performance with millennials' job satisfaction and retention in SMEs.**

As discussed above, some of the demotivating factors causing millennials employees to leave their current employment were lack of increment, recognition, learning and development opportunities, career progression, ineffective communication, and technological advancement. All these factors were the major concerns highlighted by the participant and can be improved by implementing effective employee engagement and management performance strategy.

Lack of pay rise and work recognition can be improved by implementing OKR software. OKR software will provide managers with the active progress of each employee and allow them to recognize high-performing employees, consequently allowing for better work recognition and appraisal. Feedback and communication via online platforms have become essential, especially considering the current pandemic where employees work from home and daily feedback cannot be given.

Employees can record their progress on the software so that their managers can keep track of their work and recognize them for the job well done. In addition to that, effective engagement and communication play a significant role in this. By communicating and engaging, managers will be able to understand the personal motivating factors of each employee. This is because findings carried out indicated that each employee has different motivating factors and needs. A small number of the respondents recorded a lack of increment to be the reason for looking for different employability.

Communication can be improved by using social platforms, as suggested by some of the participants. For example, one participant shared the dissatisfaction of lack of communication by indicating that managers did not communicate clearly enough about the changes or provide guidelines when the sudden shift to working from home was made during the current pandemic crisis. In addition, lack of communication can cause employees to form confusion or may lead them to lose track of goals and visions. Therefore, effective communication is vital for motivation, engagement, management performance, and employee retention.

Findings further indicated that most participants were willing to leave their current employability for larger organizations that offer more career progression and learning and development opportunities. Therefore, as suggested above, developing, and learning culture should be implemented with effective leaders in place. Lack of technological advancement was another dissatisfaction factor for millennial employee participants; therefore, new software and hardware should be implemented to overcome dissatisfaction and improve the organization's overall procedure and efficiency.

Safety concern was also significantly revealed by the employees, thus, consequently raising the need for healthy and safety protocols to be readjusted and reconsidered especially considering the current pandemic crisis. Additionally, flexibility to work from home was also signified by some of the employees alongside the assurance of job security in the global pandemic which further signifies the need for better communication at the workplace.

Improving all these factors will result in increased employee satisfaction which in turn will improve retention. Thus, indicating an interconnection between engagement, management performance, retention, and satisfaction of millennials employees.

5.3

Contribution

Previous studies conducted on the issues of millennials retention were usually done considering one context of HR. For instance, some researchers focused on analysing generational differences, while some focused solely on either engagement or the

motivational factors of the employees (Men and Reuben, 2017, Stewart *et al.*, 2017; Morrell and Abston, 2018; He and Rung: 2019). Nevertheless, they explored some context and practical challenges faced by managers in employing millennials. However, they did not explore the interconnection of employee engagement and management performance on retaining the millennial generation especially after the global pandemic crisis.

It has been understood from the study that employee engagement and organisational performance are interrelated to each other. The organisation needs to focus on the performance management in order to improve the performance of the employees by motivating and encouraging them to work better by offering them rewards, bonus and many more. The human resource department is responsible for understanding the needs and wants of the employees (Spranger & Chen, 2019). They have to interact with to understand their expectation with the aim of satisfying their demand, which would enable them to improve their performance and fulfil the organisational goal. The current study reveals that, due to pandemic situation many companies have cut salary for their employees, which has forced them to leave the company. Due to this reason the unemployment rate has been increased to a huge extent.

Conducting this study in the UK economy has made several contributions to the knowledge. It filled research gaps on the UK economy and fulfil the criteria of further research on SMEs for the retention of millennials (Tarmann, 2017; Kumar and Govindarajo, 2018; Bellucci, 2020). The study primarily focuses on the SMEs (e-retail) sector of the UK economy, henceforth making the current research findings beneficial for SMEs in the UK region and contributing knowledge towards the retention of the millennial generation. Without a doubt, the contribution of SMEs in the UK region is phenomenal. A rare focus has been made on how SMEs can improve retention and better performance through individual motivation, engagement, and performance. Findings gained on employees' motivation, engagement, and management performance are crucial for SMEs' development and betterment. They are growing and becoming a major economic development agent and employability in the UK economy.

The current study foresees the need of organisation implementing a culture and up-date-software which will facilitate them in improving career progression and learning and development opportunities, consequently raising the importance of effective human

resource practices for the effective retention of millennials. In addition, many researchers have signified the importance of HR practices and their positive impact on employee motivation and performance (Rich *et al.*, 2010; Rainer and Rainer, 2011, Desjardin 2010).

Little to no research has been done on studying the retention issues focusing the employee engagement, and management performance especially after the global pandemic. Thus, extending managerial implication in COVID-19 for the SMEs top managers seeking to optimize their retention, engagement, and performance. Finally, policy/strategy makers can benefit from the finding of the current study. They can change or update their current employee engagement and management performance considering the suggestion made after thorough analysis. This study also supports the existing literature and views of researcher on employees and managerial behavior and practices conducted before in the context of employee engagement. Additionally, it provides further suggestions to the existing literature. It highlights some of the major characteristics researchers and managers should consider when conducting further research or drawing or updating existing strategies.

5.4 Implications

Over the years, increased growth of online retailers (SMEs) has been seen and is expected to grow within the next few years, especially considering the current pandemic crisis faced worldwide. Hence, increasing the need to study retention issues of millennials in the SMEs sector especially considering they are becoming a large source of employability in the worldwide economy. Leaders and organisation are required to pay attention to the dramatically changing work environment. They must evaluate the rapidly changing expectation and need of millennial in the dramatic changing environment of COVID-19.

The present study suggests that HR managers can overcome retention issues by paying more attention to the organisation's culture. HR can implement a career development culture within the organisation by making career plan and engagement provisions. They can support career engagement by positioning strong leaders and consultants to support each employee by managing their long-term career plans and keeping up with the

challenges. They can have a training matrix to see their employees' current strengths and weaknesses and draw on-going training or cross-training, especially in SMEs.

One participant revealed real-life implications to tackle generational differences by indicating that organizations should consider positioning millennials as managers to tackle the generational conflict. Participant further highlighted that doing so has resulted in better management and less conflict between the current workforces by overcoming the egoistic and superior attitude of Baby Boomer or other generation employees.

Further, the study revealed the need for organisations to pay more attention to their hardware and software. As millennials are technologically driven, up-to-date technology should be offered to speed up the overall processes and procedure. Findings suggested that HR should not neglect technology advancement. Failure to offer technological advancement will have a detrimental impact on the ineffective utilization of millennial skills and abilities, which in turn affect their performance and organizational achievements. They can implement software like OKR and other social media platforms to communicate better, plan, and monitor each employee's progress.

Additionally, considering the current pandemic situation, technological advancement has become a necessity for organisation survival. The current pandemic has raised the need for flexible work practices, which increased the need to use social platforms to communicate and online technology platforms to monitor each employee's output and productivity level. It was realized that already technologically advanced organizations faced less difficulty in coping with the dramatically changing environment caused by COVID-19 than those who did not keep themselves up to date with technology. Thus, investing in online software essential than ever before.

The present study significantly suggested effective communication and friendly relationship with employees should be formed to improve retention, especially millennial employees. One manager participant suggested that when a friendly relationship with employees, especially millennials, is maintained even after their exit, they increase their re-attraction. The manager indicated this would result in two benefits, first employees will be coming with even more experience, training, and development, and second, an overall costly recruitment process can be avoided due to

re-recruitment. In addition to that, an effective recruitment process considering the right fit for the job was also revealed as an important factor by management participants, contributing significantly to employee retention.

Study further signifies the need of health and safety concerns. Considering the current pandemic situation, managers should offer flexible work practices alongside the construction of safety protocols at work, such as change in workplace structure which supports government guidelines of social distancing and work from home when possible and only calling employees at the workplace premises when essential. Offering safety will enhance millennial satisfaction and motivation as they will feel their health and safety is considered as priority by the managers.

5.5 Limitation of the Study

A significant number of efforts have been made to provide true insight into the field study. However, there are some limitations to the study, which are as follows:

5.5.1 Theoretical Limitation

The major theoretical limitation in this study is that when the research was initially started, only limited information on millennials' implications and retention was available. However, while carrying out the research, more data became available and published. Considering the time and word limitation, it was impossible to involve all the arising aspects in literature. However, some recent statistics have been included in the data analysis to ensure current findings (2020) are not entirely ignored. Second, considering the time and word restriction, research was narrowed down, and only some major aspects of employee engagement and performance managers were included considering the research objectives.

5.5.2 Methodological Limitation

Although efforts have been made to fully eliminate any assumptions and biases of the researcher, however, in reality, there may be some risk of researcher biases. This is because a single individual handled research data collected for this study. Furthermore, due to time and COVID-19 restriction, it was difficult for the researcher to approach other analysts to overcome researcher biasness in the thematic analysis, as suggested

by Ryan and Bernard (2003). Additionally, since the researcher belongs to the millennial generation, it may unintentionally expose biases and construction of findings based on personal experience or opinions.

Another limitation in the methodology of this thesis was the mode of interview. Considering the current pandemic safety protocols, some interviews were conducting using social media platforms like Zoom and Skype, consequently, eliminating the body language benefit to the researcher. Body language of some participants was not included in the data analysis process, thus, limiting the interview research method.

As the study has focused mainly on interview, the researcher has faced some barriers during data analyse due to the unclear opinions of the participants. It was really a time taking procedure but due to the time limitation of the project the data analysis has been affected. The research need to give more time on data analysis so that every single interpretation of the participants may have been analysed systematically. In order to minimise this issue, the research have to start the data analysing earlier in order to make the research much relevant. Apart from this the researcher can also add more focused group as it is more effective than interview. Focused group provide more clarity of the findings. It would have helped the research in understanding the unmet and met demands. There were also many problems related to COVID which disrupted the data collection process. Also, the pandemic has impacted the situation of job of the millennial which is evident in the aspects of the research. Getting the right participants was not easy during this time.

5.5.3 Sample Size

The sample size was another limitation faced by the researcher. Initially, it was anticipated to interview 25 employees and 6 managers. However, due to the current pandemic crisis, the sample size was reduced significantly to 14 participants (10 employees and 4 managers). Additionally, the research initially aimed to collect two focus group interviews, but due to time and COVID restriction, it could only undertake one focus group interview. However, a reduction in the sample size did not reduce the quality of data. All the interviews were conducted comprehensively, adequately addressing the research questions and objectives of the field study. Bryman and Bell (2017) also suggested that qualitative research quality does not depend on the number of samples but on the richness and representativeness of the data collected by those samples.

5.6 Suggestions for Future Research

Considering the above limitations, further research should be carried out focusing on any other arising context eliminated in this study due to time constraint. Especially when considering the current global crisis, further research should be carried out to understand the impact of these crises on the millennial workforce. Some of the recent research has indicated that millennials are staying longer with their current employment than usual. However, no in-depth statistical data has been carried out to show how true is that. Therefore, further research should be carried out.

Additionally, as generational Z are slowly entering or are on the verge of entering the workforce, research should understand any differences between their expectations. Again, the current pandemic situation is impacting them significantly, and their expectation may change. Therefore, making it necessary for further research to be carried out on them.

Furthermore, considering the nature of the current study, a purely qualitative research approach was used. No statistical analysis has been made limiting the research application. Therefore, the future researcher should consider conducting statistical research on the current findings and statistically measure the relationship between management performance and employee engagement with millennial retention in SMEs. Lastly, considering the current pandemic, the sample size used was small and may limit the potency of the current study. Hence, suggesting further research to be carried out considering a larger sample size.

5.7 Reflection

Since the start of the study, I was conscious that being a millennial and researching on millennial generation may have some influence on the study. Some of the existing literature links to my current experience as a working millennial; however, some did not. Furthermore, as an international student from developing countries, I realized that my opinion may vary from the participant living in a developed country like the UK. Therefore, as a researcher, I abstained from using any of my opinion and biasness.

Almost four years of doctoral study journey provided me with a tremendous amount of knowledge. Initially, the actual time, effort, and skills required to complete the study

were never realized when making a start. Collecting and organizing the literature review took a generous amount of time in this research. Limited data on millennials were present simultaneously, whereas a large context was available on employee engagement and management performance. Therefore, extra time was taken to carefully choose the important and relevant context for literature using a conceptual framework. The data collection process was not difficult; however, a sudden pandemic crisis delayed and complicate the process of data collection process more than usual. The data analysis was one of the most difficult parts of this research because it was challenging to understand the NVivo software. It took me a while to understand how to code the data and themes on the software.

However, once a satisfying level of understanding and knowledge was gained, I quickly analysed the data. Interview protocols were learned and observed, which further assisted me in mitigating any element of personal biases from the study. Regardless of difficulties and delays, it was a rewarding process for me. Delay caused by COVID-19 allowed me to gain a broader perspective on the study. More recent research and literature were published, further adding to the literature review, and considered in the data analysis.

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7. Appendices

7.1 Appendix A: Participant Information Sheet

Research project title:

Implication of Employee Engagement and Management Performance on Millennial Retention: A study of SME's in UK.

Research investigator: Fatima Amjad

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

Personal details withheld.

About the Project

This research aim is to explore on how small-medium enterprise can improve their relationship with millennial by establishing effective employee engagement and management performance. It is essential for every enterprise to attract and retain millennial as they are taking active part in organizational activities. Therefore, this research objective is to develop effective strategies specifically for SME's on how they can retain high level of millennial within the organization.

Your participation will allow researcher to shape their study. By speaking with your management team and employee, I will be able to answer my research question with much more knowledge.

Who is responsible for the data collected in this study?

- Fatima Amjad will be conducting this research for her doctorate thesis under the supervision of relevant university members, such as, Bronwyn Betts.
- Interview will be undertaken to gain understanding on how organizations are dealing with multi-generation workforce and how effective they are in doing so? Manager's interview will be conducted via semi-structure interviews

whereas, employees will be interviewed via one-to-one session as well as focus group.

- Data will be recorded through voice recorder or video depending on interviewee's preference. Data collected will be stored for 6 years and then it will be disposed of under the Data Protection Act, 1998.
- Voice recorded data will be kept in electronically password protected file in the University server. If for some reason, researcher needs to store this electronic data at a different server, then it will be store in an encrypted manner to ensure data is kept secure. Any data containing personal identification will be destroyed as soon as participant agrees to be part of research or until the end of summary report of research, if participant agrees to be part of research till the end.
- Research will also be reviewed and passed by the ethics committee at West Scotland University.

What is involved in the study and what actions will be required?

1. If you are willing to volunteer in the research, you will be required to fill the consent form and return it via email.
2. There will be an interview, which will not last any longer than 45- 60 minutes. It will be one off interview and will not require second interviewing.
3. Time, date, and location will be set according to your convenience to meet. I can travel to you, however, if for some reason meeting is not possible than we can conduct interview via telephone call or Skype call.
4. Data collected will be analysed and summarized by comparing it with the existing theories, in aim to answer my research query.

Will your participation in this research remain anonymous?

If you agree to take part, your identity will be kept confidential as anonymous and will only be used for data research purposes.

What are the risks involved in this study?

You may feel uncomfortable answering some questions, however, discussion can be made in advance to overcome any hesitance and to avoid any question if necessary. As far as possible your contribution will be kept confidential. You will have the opportunity to remove any information or images at any stage of the research.

What are the benefits for taking part in this study?

You may enjoy taking part in this research especially being relevant to your industry (SME's). This primary research once completed will provide guideline to managers on how they can improve and will add up to the knowledge of the business domain as outcome will be applicable to enterprises of all field.

What are your rights as a participant?

Taking part in the study is voluntary. You may choose not to take part or subsequently cease participation at any time. You will be able to withdraw within 14 days from the interview time and won't be forced to give reason for withdrawal.

Will I receive any payment or monetary benefits?

You will receive no payment for your participation.

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP -----

Title of Project: Implication of Employee Engagement and Management Performance on Millennial Retention: A study of SMEs in UK.

Name of Researcher: Fatima Amjad

Email Address of research investigator:

[Redacted email address]

Personal details withheld.

Please tick initial box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

3. I understand that data collected might be examined by the relevant member of university of West of the Scotland, when necessary, I hereby give permission for them to have access to information provided.

4. I agree to be *audio recorded*.

5. I understand your anonymity will be maintained.

6. I agree for my information to be audio collected and used for the writing of Fatima Amjad doctorate research (2019-2021). I allow her to compare collected data against other existing research/case studies to evaluate correlative theories and strategies for the purposes of the project mentioned in the information sheet.

I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Researcher

Date

Signature

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP -----

7.3

Appendix C: Sample Employee Interview Questions

1. Can I start by taking your age?
2. How long you have been working here?
3. Describe your perfect work environment?
4. What is your expectation from the workplace?
5. What attracted you to work for this company?
6. What is the most interesting part of your job?
7. In what way does leadership energize you to come to work?
8. Does your job provide you with meaning and purpose?
9. In what ways does autonomy from your manager play into your everyday workflow?
10. Describe the way that the company goals align with your work?
11. What is one thing you would change about your job?
12. What kind of relationship you have with your current management?
13. Do you think there is an open and honest communication between you and your management?
14. Are you aware of needs, goals, and challenges of your current workplace?
15. What can your company do to increase transparency?
16. Do you have everything you need to perform the job in terms of training?
17. Do you see professional growth and career development opportunities for yourself in this organization?
18. What personally drives you to work beyond expectations?
19. Do you think you have progressed or improved or developed skill as compared to your last workplace?
20. What obstacles are currently in your way in achieving success at the office?
21. How does your manager recognize your work within the organization?
22. What type of feedback do you receive from your manager?
23. What is one thing you'd like to change about the employee review process?
24. What is the nature of the feedback you receive from your manager?
25. Why do you feel or not feel that leadership takes your feedback seriously?

26. What opportunities are you given to provide your manager with feedback?
27. Name one way in which company communication could improve.
28. How satisfied are you with your current employment?
29. What are some ways in which the organization can more clearly express employee appreciation?
30. What are the dissatisfying factors you wish to highlight?
31. What have you seen recently that made you think, "I wish we had done that at work?"
32. Any tensions that arise in your personal life due to work-life balance.
33. What two or three things could the company do to help you better manage your work-life balance
34. Name one way in which company communication could improve.
35. What improvement you think organisation can make
36. Do you see yourself working for this company for long term?
37. If no, why?

1. Can I start by taking your age?
2. How long you have been working/managing this organization?
3. How would you describe your work environment?
4. Who are millennial generation?
5. Do you have experience of working with them?
6. How would you describe them?
7. How millennial generation differ from other generation? To what extent, millennial generation are significant to your organization?
8. What recruitment strategy you use to attract them?
9. How successful your recruitment strategy is?
10. What culture you have within your organisation?
11. Do you offer flexible culture within organisation? If yes, why and do you think it has positive impact on your organisation?
12. What strategy you adopt to satisfy and retain them? Pay, reward, appraisal, flexibility
13. What are your engagement and support strategies?
14. How do you go about developing the people you manage?
15. How do you help your employees become committed to a job or to the organization?
16. How do you deal with struggling employee?
17. How often do you think it is necessary to meet with your employees?
18. What sort of employee training do you offer?
19. How do you develop trust and loyalty in your employee?
20. Are you transparent with your employee?
21. How do you communicate needs, goals, and challenges of your workplace?
22. How do you offer your employees with career and growth opportunities?
23. How would describe your relationship with your employees?
24. What do you do to ensure objectivity when you evaluate your employees?
25. How often do you evaluate your employees?
26. How do you evaluate your department's overall performance?
27. When you evaluate employee's performance, what approach do you take?

28. How do you plan for performance improvements?
29. How do you measure performance in your area?
30. What have you found to be the best way to monitor the performance of your work and/or the work of others? Share a time when you had to take corrective action.
31. What are the biggest challenges you face when employing Millennial within the organisation?
32. To which extent your strategy is successful in employing and retaining millennial?
33. What improvement you think can be made to existing strategy?

7.5

Appendix E: NVivo Code

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Employees	0	0	1/12/2021 11:45 PM	BM	1/12/2021 11:45 PM	BM
Attributes of an ideal work environment	0	0	1/10/2021 10:55 PM	BM	1/10/2021 10:55 PM	BM
Adequate salary	1	1	1/11/2021 10:27 PM	BM	1/11/2021 10:27 PM	BM
Adequate training	1	1	1/11/2021 10:27 PM	BM	1/11/2021 10:27 PM	BM
Cleanliness	1	1	1/10/2021 10:55 PM	BM	1/10/2021 10:55 PM	BM
Excellent communication with managers	1	1	1/11/2021 9:54 PM	BM	1/11/2021 9:54 PM	BM
Friendly environment	8	9	1/10/2021 10:56 PM	BM	1/11/2021 9:59 PM	BM
Good work facilities	1	1	1/11/2021 10:26 PM	BM	1/11/2021 10:26 PM	BM
Healthy competition	2	2	1/10/2021 10:56 PM	BM	1/11/2021 10:17 AM	BM
Honesty and integrity	1	1	1/11/2021 8:53 PM	BM	1/11/2021 8:53 PM	BM
Presence of diversity	1	1	1/11/2021 5:11 AM	BM	1/11/2021 5:11 AM	BM
Respect and appreciation	2	2	1/11/2021 11:38 AM	BM	1/11/2021 4:22 PM	BM
Safe work environment	1	1	1/11/2021 9:22 PM	BM	1/11/2021 9:22 PM	BM
Talent diversity	1	1	1/11/2021 8:53 PM	BM	1/11/2021 8:53 PM	BM
Teamwork	1	1	1/11/2021 8:53 PM	BM	1/11/2021 8:53 PM	BM
Desire to stay	0	0	1/11/2021 6:32 AM	BM	1/11/2021 6:32 AM	BM
2 years or more	1	1	1/11/2021 6:32 AM	BM	1/11/2021 6:32 AM	BM
No	3	5	1/11/2021 4:13 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:39 PM	BM
Seeking oppotunities in bigger organizations	1	1	1/11/2021 10:54 AM	BM	1/11/2021 10:54 AM	BM
Yes	3	3	1/11/2021 11:32 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:55 PM	BM
Factors hindering success	0	0	1/10/2021 11:36 PM	BM	1/11/2021 5:14 AM	BM
Feedback mechanism	0	0	1/11/2021 6:26 AM	BM	1/11/2021 6:26 AM	BM
Goal alignment	0	0	1/10/2021 11:10 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:10 PM	BM
How leadership handles feedback	0	0	1/10/2021 11:41 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:41 PM	BM
Impact of autonomy	0	0	1/10/2021 11:09 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:09 PM	BM
Impact of job on work-life balance	0	0	1/10/2021 11:49 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:49 PM	BM
Impact of leadership on employee retention	0	0	1/10/2021 11:03 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:03 PM	BM
Impoving communication	0	0	1/11/2021 11:45 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:45 PM	BM
Improving recognition for hardwork	0	0	1/10/2021 11:46 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:46 PM	BM
Improving the review process	0	0	1/10/2021 11:39 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:39 PM	BM
Information dissemination	0	0	1/10/2021 11:29 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:29 PM	BM
Job satisfaction	0	0	1/11/2021 6:27 AM	BM	1/11/2021 6:27 AM	BM
Leadership and work attendance	0	0	1/11/2021 10:35 PM	BM	1/11/2021 10:35 PM	BM
Level of satisfaction with job	0	0	1/10/2021 11:44 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:44 PM	BM
Millenial workplace expectations	0	0	1/10/2021 10:58 PM	BM	1/11/2021 5:12 AM	BM
Older generation employees vs newer generation	0	0	1/11/2021 6:33 AM	BM	1/11/2021 6:33 AM	BM
Positives of the job	0	0	1/10/2021 11:02 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:02 PM	BM
Professional development	0	0	1/10/2021 11:32 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:32 PM	BM
Relationship with manager	0	0	1/10/2021 11:27 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:27 PM	BM
Remuneration	0	0	1/11/2021 6:20 AM	BM	1/11/2021 6:20 AM	BM
Suggested improvements	0	0	1/10/2021 11:48 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:48 PM	BM
The job provides meaning and purpose	4	4	1/11/2021 10:57 AM	BM	1/11/2021 10:44 PM	BM
The work provides nor meaning and purpose	0	0	1/11/2021 10:44 PM	BM	1/11/2021 10:44 PM	BM
Training sufficiency	0	0	1/10/2021 11:30 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:30 PM	BM
Work recognition	0	0	1/10/2021 11:37 PM	BM	1/10/2021 11:37 PM	BM
Working beyond expectations	0	0	1/10/2021 11:35 PM	BM	1/12/2021 9:19 PM	BM
A good remuneration	1	1	1/11/2021 11:11 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:11 PM	BM
Job security	1	1	1/11/2021 11:12 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:12 PM	BM
Learning oppurtunity	1	1	1/11/2021 11:11 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:11 PM	BM
Love for customer satisfaction	3	3	1/11/2021 11:16 AM	BM	1/11/2021 11:13 PM	BM
Managers appraisal	3	3	1/10/2021 11:35 PM	BM	1/11/2021 11:12 PM	BM
Passion and love for job role	2	2	1/11/2021 6:11 AM	BM	1/11/2021 11:13 PM	BM
Work-life balance management	0	0	1/12/2021 11:34 PM	BM	1/12/2021 11:34 PM	BM
Management	0	0	1/12/2021 11:47 PM	BM	1/12/2021 11:47 PM	BM